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**BIG DATA
OCEAN**

BigDataOcean

“Exploiting Oceans of Data for Maritime Applications”

D2.1 - Analysis Report on Big Data Components, Tools and Methodologies

Workpackage: WP2 – Stakeholders’ Identification, Maritime Data Value Chain
Definition and Project Methodology

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Partners

	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Decision Support Systems Laboratory, DSSLab <u>Co-ordinator</u>	Greece
	Exmile Solutions Limited (EXMILE)	United Kingdom
	Rheinische Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität Bonn (UBONN)	Germany
	Centro de Investigação em Energia REN – State Grid, S.A. – R&D Nester (NESTER)	Portugal
	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)	Greece
	Ubitech Limited (UBITECH)	Cyprus
	Foinikas Shipping Company (FOINIKAS)	Greece
	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella (ISMB)	Italy
	Instituto de Desenvolvimento de Novas Tecnologias (UNINOVA)	Portugal
	Anonymi Naftiliaki Etaireia Kritis (ANEK)	Greece

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Executive Summary

This document reports the initial activities of BigDataOcean (BDO) concerning stakeholders' identification, requirements elicitation, and definition of the maritime data value chain through the work developed in Tasks 2.1, Task 2.2 and Task 2.3. Being an ample report that sets the baseline for BDO technical activities, it includes four main results:

- 1. State-of-play analysis of the Big Data landscape** in terms of tools and methodologies that can be integrated into the BDO services and platform infrastructure. Through a careful selection and adoption of each technology, the system backbone will be interoperable with the most popular and established data processing technologies and will be adaptable to various systems. In detail, 10 different topics, and related technologies have been analysed, covering domains such as Data Formats and Encoding, Data Storage or Analytics. Its suitability to BDO, as well as its positioning in the Maritime Data Value Chain, later described, among other aspects, has been investigated;
- 2. BDO requirements engineering methodology.** A mixed approach that, in the early stages of the project follows a traditional waterfall method until the first mock-up of the minimum viable product and the architecture are specified, and then applies agile methods promoting various elicitation and development sprints thanks to the feedback loops. To ensure consistency and an integrated approach that is valid and capable of synchronising the requirements coming from the different pilot cases, this document also presents a comprehensive methodology for the BDO requirements engineering. It is adapted from existing approaches and follows five main phases, namely: 1) a Preparation phase to support the stakeholders' identification, data sources and value chain characterisation; 2) the requirements Elicitation phase to gather the main set of industrial needs for the BDO solutions; 3) the Analysis phase to rework the requirements into a form of user stories that express the functional and non-functional needs; 4) the Specification phase, defining a minimum viable product and making the bridge with the proof-of-concept; and finally 5) the Validation phase to verify the completeness of implementations. D2.1 targets the activities of the first 3 phases;

- 3. Integrated Maritime Data Value Chain,** defining all the activities needed to transform the BDO concept to a product, and incorporating all the steps to extract value and insights from collected data of all BDO pilot cases, namely: *Data Acquisition* to identify the infrastructure required to support data collection; *Data Pre-Processing*, to enable the data exploration and transformation into linked information for data analytics; *Data Curation*, to assess the quality of the data; *Data Storage* for storage in a persistent and scalable way; and *Data Usage*, covering the business activities. Each BDO pilot case has its own instantiation of this value chain and a specific stakeholders' framework; hence a defined and integrated maritime data value chain has been described in the document. A total of 15 different types of stakeholders and their corresponding datasets have been identified and described as part of that value chain;

4. BigDataOcean Requirements. After having the stakeholders properly identified, four requirements workshops have been organised to validate the value chain, to work on the future scenarios and To-Be services, and to elicit a set of raw requirements for the BDO system. In total, 62 requirements have been elicited and they have been divided into business, functional and non-functional requirements. Clear technology gaps for the BDO system have been identified in the areas of Data Curation and Data Usage.

The deliverable has been resubmitted following the comments received during the BigDataOcean first review meeting, updating the state of play landscape and providing a detailed specification of the datasets to be used for each pilot and across the value chain.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
4Vs	Volume, Velocity, Veracity and Variety
AIS	Automatic Identification System
BDO	BigDataOcean
CEP	Complex Event Processing
CPS	Cyber-Physical Systems
DBMS	Data Base Management System
ESB	Enterprise Service Bus
HCMR	Hellenic Center for Marine Research
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO/IEC	International Organisation for Standardisation/International Electrotechnical Commission
IT	Information Technology
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
LinDA	Linked Data and Analytic tools for SMEs
M2M	Machine to Machine
MDA	Maritime Domain Awareness
MGI	Marseille Gyptis International
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisation
OMG MDA	Object Management Group Model-Driven Architecture
OMG MDD	Object Management Group Model-Driven Development
OSMOSE	OSMOsis applications for the Sensing Enterprise
PlantCockpit	The Open Source for an unified visualisation and control of production
PSC	Port State Control
RE	Requirement Engineering
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SOCIB	Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System
WP	Workpackage

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

This deliverable reports the initial activities of BigDataOcean through the work developed in Task 2.1, Task 2.2 and Task 2.3, whose goals are:

1. **Task 2.1** – State-of-Play Analysis on Big Data Components, Tools and Methodologies, where the activities to be performed include:
 - a. State-of-the-Art analysis on existing technology, including open source/ commercial methods, components and tools that can be integrated into the project services and platform backbone infrastructure;
 - b. Each of technology will be analysed and evaluated based on experimentation and the partners own experience (e.g. technology in-place and experience from previous projects), reporting benefits, limitations, suitability to the BDO platform, licensing, etc.;
2. **Task 2.2** – Maritime Data Stakeholders, Information Sources and Needs Identification, where the activities to be performed include:
 - a. Identification and reporting on the set of stakeholders that are potentially interested and can benefit the maritime data value chain;
 - b. Identification of various (open) data and information sources to be taken into consideration for the needs of the project approach;
 - c. Close collaboration with the end users of the project in order to identify and report the needs that will guide the BigDataOcean design and implementation;
3. **Task 2.3** – Definition of Integrated Maritime Data Value Chain, namely:
 - a. Definition of the integrated maritime data value chain;
 - b. Correlation of all the individual maritime-related stakeholders in an integrated value chain, bringing forward the value that one can add to each other, under a seamless collaboration and mutually beneficiary prism.

1.2 Structure of the Deliverable

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** provides an overall introduction of the deliverable objectives and positioning within the project;
- **Chapter 2** provides a state of the art analysis and evaluation on the existing methods, components and tools in Big Data that can be integrated in the project. This analysis provides the Big Data landscape;
- **Chapter 3** describes in detail the methodology for the Identification of BigDataOcean Scenarios and Requirements;
- **Chapter 4** identifies the different stakeholders involved in each BigDataOcean pilot scenario and their relationship in an integrated value chain;
- **Chapter 5** details the requirements elicited and includes a preliminary gap analysis considering the state of the art and the envisaged scenarios;
- **Chapter 6** reports summary and conclusions;

- Several **Annexes** are included as part of this document, presenting the Requirements Questionnaire, the Data Source Definition form, as well as the results from the requirements workshops.

1.3 Document Progress and Status

The document is listed in the Description of Action as a public deliverable due at M3 of the project. It has been submitted as planned, and later updated (M19) following the comments received during the BigDataOcean first review meeting. In this update, particular attention and content has been provided in the following sections:

- Chapter 2 “Big Data Technology Landscape”, which was updated to provide a better and more focused view of the candidate technology to be used as support to the pilots and is suitable for the BigDataOcean solution.
- Chapter 3 “Requirements Engineering Methodology”, which has been updated to provide more details regarding how relevant datasets identified in the preparatory stage are analysed and selected. The feedback loop, initially envisaged through serious games, has been replaced by the agile “game storming” approach.
- Chapter 4, which was initially focused on the identification of the stakeholders and the maritime value chain, has been updated to provide a detailed specification of the datasets to be used for each pilot and across the value chain.

1.4 Positioning within the project

Work package 2 follows a two-cycle approach, providing results in two different moments of BDO. In the beginning, both deliverables D2.1 and D2.2 make the baseline needed for the technical developments to be performed by WP3 – WP6, available for the rest of the project. As illustrated in Figure 1-1, (1) the initial analysis on the state of play, (2) the needs and requirements coming from the different stakeholders, as well as (3) the integrated value chain is provided by D2.1. The WP2 deliverable is D2.2 at M06 that complements this initial baseline with the (4) minimum viable product and (5) draft BDO Methodology. Finally, the second cycle of WP2 iterated through the same activities, but its results are condensed in a single document, D2.3 at M18.

Figure 1-1: Two cycles approach for WP2.

A different view on how the results of D2.1 are integrated with the remaining project activities is detailed in the requirements methodology presented in section 3 of this document, where different steps of the methodology are implemented across the several tasks of BDO.

2 Big Data Technology Landscape

BDO concept addresses a rather innovative combination of state-of-the-art scientific fields and relevant technologies (e.g. analytics, rules engines, data curation, Big Data technologies, linked data repositories, trust, security and privacy providers and cloud storage, among others). Powerful tools that exist or are in their early adoption phase will be used as the scientific and technological cornerstones of BDO. Thus, to ensure the “win-win” situation amongst maritime end users and data providers, the Big Data landscape needs to be revisited and analysed to ensure a proper technological baseline for the project.

The technology has been analysed and evaluated based on experimentation and the partners own experience (e.g. technology in-place and experience from previous projects). This has enabled to build a targeted pool of tools for the proposed architecture (D4.2 and D4.3) and for the BigDataOcean Platform (D5.3 - D5.6) while also ensuring interoperability with the most popular and established data processing technologies, hence being compatible to various different operation systems that one can nowadays meet.

Figure 2-1: BDO Technology Landscape Taxonomy.

This section presents the undergoing effort of identifying existing methods and tools that constitute the pillars on which the project's technical implementation will be founded. Figure 2-1 depicts the taxonomy of the topics selected as relevant for the BDO Big Data solutions. The topics selection process considered the expected technological challenges related with the development of a platform like BDO, where Query Processing, Stream Processing and Analytics assume special importance. Each topic has been briefly described and decomposed in a set of state-of-the-art solutions.

While the **definitive selection of specific tools is not the objective of the state-of-the-art analysis conducted here**, the information comprised in Sections 2.1 - 2.10 constitutes a knowledge base for the future BDO development providing an indication of which can more suitable for the BigDataOcean solutions. Results are presented along this chapter on summary tables that provide an easy form of visualising the experience of the consortium; the main features of the tool/ solution; benefits and limitations in the frame of BDO; suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots; licencing, and; positioning in the Data Value Chain.

Not all solutions analysed are applicable in BDO, some might only be applicable in certain application specific services, and others are of definitive interest but will not be selected for the implementation. It was considered that such a comprehensive analysis on the Big Data landscape could contribute to both research and industrial communities. In the next sub-sections, it is possible to find the landscape of the technologies considered more relevant and of interest to integrate in the set of BigDataOcean solutions. With regards to the first version of D2.1 submitted at M3, this second version of D2.1 has significantly changed in terms of the technology presented, filtering out much of the technology that was considered inappropriate after a more careful analysis of the pilots and their needs.

2.1 Data Formats and Encoding

Data acquisition and data usage, two fundamental phases of the Big Data value chain, are fundamentally linked with data formats and encoding. Indeed, data acquisition is the approach to gather and measure information from a variety of sources, in this case, gather information from the maritime data value chain (Zhang, Zhang, Ren, Ma, & Wang, 2016). To ensure the quality of collected data and its proper usage, it is needed to analyse the best data strategies for data formatting and encoding.

Another major aspect closely related with the data acquisition and data usage is interoperability. When organisations need a system or a product to work with other systems without special effort on the part of the customer, they need interoperability. This is what IEEE (Geraci et al., 1991) defines as interoperability. Of course, more detail can be added to this statement, e.g. enabling cooperation and data exchange among products or systems (Aliprandi, 2011). Following these two statements, it is possible to identify that the interoperability plays a pivotal role in ensure collaboration among all the involved actors in a value chain such as the maritime one. In the context of the BDO, the most relevant type of interoperability that is related with data formats and encoding is the technical one. Semantic interoperability is also relevant but is more connected with the section 2.2 "Metadata Repositories and Semantics".

The technological barrier exists because of one or more ICT mismatches, e.g. due to incompatible interfaces between the different systems, or simply due to different formats and encoding of data with also leads to communication barriers. In this situation, a data integration engine is needed, to enable an effective and efficiently link between different formats. In the domain of BDO, there are several

standards used for data encoding and representation, each one with a defined objective. To integrate data following these standards, it is necessary to understand their structure and rules. Below, it is possible to find some of the standards used in BDO.

- **NetCDF (Network Common Data Form)¹**: a set of software libraries and self-describing, machine-independent data formats that support the creation, access, and sharing of array-oriented scientific data used in climatology, meteorology and oceanography applications (e.g., weather forecasting, climate change) and GIS applications;
- **GeoJSON (Geospatial data interchange format based on JSON)²**: an open standard format designed for representing simple geographical features, along with their non-spatial attributes. It is based on JSON, the JavaScript Object Notation;
- **GML (Geography Markup Language)³**: The GML is the XML grammar defined by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) to express geographical features. GML serves as a modeling language for geographic systems as well as an open interchange format for geographic transactions on the Internet. It can integrate all forms of geographic information, including not only conventional "vector" or discrete objects, but coverages and sensor data;
- **KML (Keyhole Markup Language)⁴**: an XML notation for expressing geographic annotation and visualisation within Internet-based, two-dimensional maps and three-dimensional Earth browsers. KML shares some of the same structural grammar as GML;
- **Avro⁵**: a remote procedure call and data serialisation framework developed within Apache's Hadoop project. It uses JSON for defining data types and protocols, and serialises data in a compact binary format. Its primary use is in Apache Hadoop, where it can provide both a serialisation format for persistent data, a wire format for communication between Hadoop nodes and from client programs to the Hadoop services.;
- **Parquet⁶**: Apache Parquet is a free and open-source column-oriented data store of the Apache Hadoop ecosystem. It is compatible with most of the data processing frameworks in the Hadoop environment;
- **ORC⁷**: a self-describing type-aware columnar file format designed for Hadoop workloads. It is optimised for large streaming reads, but with integrated support for finding required rows quickly. Storing data in a columnar format lets the reader read, decompress, and process only the values that are required for the current query.

Table 2-1 presents the summary of tools and solutions related to the Data Formats and Encoding topic.

¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NetCDF>

² <http://geojson.org/>

³ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/gml>

⁴ <https://developers.google.com/kml/>

⁵ <https://avro.apache.org/>

⁶ <https://parquet.apache.org/>

⁷ <https://orc.apache.org/>

Table 2-1: Data Formats and Encoding tools and solutions summary

Tools/ solutions	Overall Qualitative Evaluation		Suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots		License	Related with Data Value Chain Topic
	Benefits	Limitations	Score	Description		
NetCDF	It can directly read the data and determine its structure, the variable names and essential metadata such as the units, which means that the information needed to ensure accurate work is available with the data itself. High compression	Initial learning curve for the inexperienced netCDF user; Limited number of external numeric data types; Dataset size limitation	High	NetCDF is the format used for some main data sources (i.e. Copernicus) and files of this type are currently handled in the data injection	-	Data acquisition and data usage
GeoJSON	Multiple vendors adopt it. (widely used single format)	No construct for topology, whether for compression or semantics. (possible but not yet implemented)	High	NTUA is currently using this format in several map visualisations and map related functionalities	-	Data acquisition and data usage
GML	It responds well to compression	It can be verbose. Generally, not preferred by GIS specialists (not so commonly used)	Low	The identified datasets are not using this format	-	Data acquisition and data usage
KML	Commonly used	Limited number of KML Layers on a Map Maximum uncompressed KML file size 10Mb	Low	The identified datasets are not using this format	-	Data acquisition and data usage
Avro	Direct mapping to and from JSON; Compact Format; Very Fast. Responds well to compression. Rich, extensible schema language defined in pure JSON. Best notion of compatibility for evolving your data over time	Potentially slower serialisation. To read/ write data a schema is needed	Medium	Could be an option if a file-based Big Data Storage solution is preferred	Apache License 2.0	Data acquisition and data usage
Parquet	Efficient data compression; Less data scanning on search; Parallelisation in reading and writing. Extremely fast on queries	Not indexed	High	Can be used for executing fast queries while maintaining a very efficient compression on the data existing on the BDO platform	Apache License 2.0	Data acquisition and data usage

2.2 Metadata Repositories and Semantics

Data management and data usage includes all the tasks required to properly manage data during the whole data life-cycle, e.g., data integration, curation, storage, and query processing. As discussed in the previous section, in the context of BDO, data sources may be heterogeneous (e.g., unstructured, structured) and represented using different data formats. Additionally, they may suffer of interoperability issues (e.g. the same real-world entities are represented differently in two datasets). To produce a Big Data repository to support the maritime Big Data scenarios, data integration as well as semantic interoperability issues needs to be solved. An approach is to apply metadata repositories and semantic technologies.

Defining controlled vocabularies to be used in the semantic description of the BDO datasets, requires the application of semantic enrichment of heterogeneous data, improving the representation of data provenance, as well as data meaning, or relation among different data sources. Techniques for semantic enrichment will allow BDO data to be “semantified” using existing controlled vocabularies or ontologies. This section presents existing approaches for solving semantic interoperability and integration problems among heterogeneous datasets.

- **LOV⁸:** LOV is the Linked Open Vocabularies. Vocabularies in LOV include definitions of a set of classes (types) and properties (predicates) to describe e.g. things in a given domain or industry.
- **LinDA⁹:** it is an open-source package of Enterprise Linked Data tools to semantically describe and integrate data. It transforms CSV/RDB data to RDF (Resource Description Framework, a standard model intended for interchanging data on the Web); semi-automatically maps data to standardised vocabularies; and provides suggestions for the mapping process through an API (Suggest API);
- **Ontario:** a SPARQL query engine for a data lake. Ontario provides semantic enrichment and data integration on-demand, during query processing. Data sources in a data lake are described in terms of RDF predicates. Ontario can decompose and process queries against heterogeneous sources (e.g., CSV, RDF, JSON) in their original format. It leverages RDF molecules metadata to efficiently perform query decomposition, source selection, query planning, and query execution.

Table 2-2 presents the summary of tools and solutions related to the Metadata Repositories and Semantics topic.

⁸ <http://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov/>

⁹ <http://linda-project.eu/tools/>

Table 2-2: Metadata Repositories and Semantics tools and solutions summary

Tools/ solutions	Overall Qualitative Evaluation		Suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots		License	Related with Data Value Chain Topic
	Benefits	Limitations	Score	Description		
LOV	LOV allows reusing well documented vocabularies; it supports ontology search, assessment and mapping	LOV does not include Value Vocabularies; and relies on third party projects to get the information of use of vocabulary in published datasets	High	Relevant for mapping of data to standardised vocabularies	N.A.	Data usage
LinDA	Semi-automatic mapping to existing vocabularies; Possibility to save transformation mappings	Requires manual configuration to map to vocabularies	Medium	Relevant for mapping of data to standardised vocabularies	MIT license, open source	Data usage
Ontario	Heterogeneous sources are kept in raw format and can be accessed using native query engines.	Research tool. No all the SPARQL filters are implemented; Wrappers need to be implemented by each of the data sources.	High	Research tool. No all the SPARQL filters are implemented; Wrappers need to be implemented by each of the data sources.	GNU/GPL v2	Data Usage

2.3 Data Storage

The problem of data storage, as well as its partitioning and distribution, is one of the core technological challenges for Big Data technologies. As discussed, data is represented using different data models. In addition, BigDataOcean should be able to manage both streamed and static data acquisition. With several technological solutions available for addressing this particular problem, the purpose of this section is to clarify the differences of various Big Data storage tools that could be used in the context of BDO. The most prominent tools that are reviewed are:

- **HBase¹⁰**: an open-source, non-relational distributed database provided by the Apache Foundation that is modeled after Google's Bigtable. It is a column-based NoSQL Data Storage. Creates collections of one or more key/ value pairs that match a record;
- **Cassandra¹¹**: an open-source distributed database management system designed to operate across multiple commodity servers, originally developed for Facebook. Cassandra is a column-based NoSQL data storage. It creates collections of one or more key/ value pairs that match a record;
- **PostgreSQL¹²**: a mature open-source Relational Database Management System that is based on the object relational DBMS Postgres, with great support for geospatial data;
- **MongoDB¹³**: an open-source, cross-platform document-oriented NoSQL database;
- **VoltDB¹⁴**: an open-source ACID-compliant¹⁵ in-memory RDBMS, a Distributed In-Memory NewSQL RDBMS;
- **Microsoft SQL Server¹⁶**: a relational database management system with extensive support for data warehousing;
- **Apache HDFS¹⁷**: the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) is used to scale a single cluster to hundreds (and even thousands) of nodes. It is a distributed file system that handles large data sets running on commodity hardware;
- **Greenplum¹⁸**: an advanced, fully featured, open source data platform. It provides powerful and rapid analytics on petabyte scale data volumes. Uniquely geared towards Big Data analytics, Greenplum Database is powered by the world's most advanced cost-based query optimiser delivering high analytical query performance on large data volumes.

Table 2-3 presents the summary of tools and solutions related to the Data Storage topic.

¹⁰ <https://hbase.apache.org/>

¹¹ <http://cassandra.apache.org/>

¹² <https://www.postgresql.org/>

¹³ <https://www.mongodb.com/>

¹⁴ <https://www.voltdb.com/>

¹⁵ ACID stands for *Atomicity, Consistency, Isolation and Durability*, as described in the ISO/IEC 10026-1:1998 (Information technology — Open Systems Interconnection — Distributed Transaction Processing — Part 1: OSI TP Model), Section 4.

¹⁶ <https://www.microsoft.com/pt-pt/sql-server/sql-server-2016>

¹⁷ <https://hadoop.apache.org/>

¹⁸ <https://greenplum.org/>

Table 2-3: Data Storage tools and solutions summary

Tools/ solutions	Overall Qualitative Evaluation		Suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots		License	Related with Data Value Chain Topic
	Benefits	Limitations	Score	Description		
HBase	Extremely powerful and reliable when used to keep data of very large sizes; Good performance when maintaining large collection of unstructured data for long time; Using Open TSDB on top of HBase gives the opportunity to retrieve time-series analytics	No ACID properties; Single point of failure.	High	Cross data operations and joining operations cannot be implemented with an acceptable performance behaviour therefore this technology proved not suitable for the BDO platform.	AL v2.0	Data storage
Cassandra	No single point of failure ensures 100% availability; Operational simplicity for lowest total cost of ownership; Best-in-class scalability of NoSQL platforms; Support of geo-spatial data	No ACID properties	High	Cassandra offers high query performance on specific queries but has limited capabilities and performance on custom queries, joins and aggregation functions. Therefore, it is not suitable for the general BDO front-end services. Nevertheless, Cassandra can be used for enhancing the performance of the pilot services through the setup of specific pre-joined queries.	AL v2.0	Data Storage
PostgreSQL	ACID properties; Supports triggers and foreign keys. Mature product. Easy to use; Supports geospatial data through the PostGIS	Big Data operations are not fully supported; Complex solution for partitioning data	High	Based on the benchmarking tests against BDO data, PostgreSQL was proven a very good option given the requirements, therefore it is used in the current version of the platform	BSD license	Data Storage
MongoDB	Support for Geo spatial data; Capable to maintain large amount of unrelated complex data sources. Well established document-based solution. Applicable in use cases in which data stores have deeply nested complex data structures.	No ACID properties. Atomic operations are allowed only inside a single document.	Low	Based on the benchmarking test against BDO data, PostgreSQL was preferred from MongoDB due to the extremely low performance on join queries	AGPL v3.0 and a commercial edition	Data Storage

VoltDB	High-throughput database with SQL and ACID transaction support; In-memory analytics for real-time visibility; Elastically scale out the cluster with no downtime	MapReduce is partially supported (i.e., through an API for user-defined methods); Foreign key constraints not supported	Low	VoltDB was considered not suitable due to its partial support to MapReduce and low penetration of the software to the market	Commercial and Open-source edition	Data Storage
Microsoft SQL Server	ACID properties; Supports triggers and foreign keys. Mature product. Easy to use.	Big Data operations are not fully supported; Supports only horizontal partitioning of tables across files.	Low	Overall initial benchmarking against AIS data showed that PostgreSQL performed significantly better (1,5x times better) than SQL server.	Commercial (restricted)	Data Storage
Apache HDFS	HDFS is highly reliable and fault-tolerant and provides a strong durability guarantee through its replication and node decommissioning mechanisms. Very high bandwidth to support MapReduce workloads	Sometimes may not present 100% availability.	High	Apache HDFS is being used for storing the raw datasets uploaded in the platform. Could be an option for the BDO Big Data Storage, if a file-based storage solution is chosen.	Apache License 2.0	Data Storage
Greenplum	Excellent for data analytics. Very fast for query processing.	Not suitable for real-time data.	Low	Could be an alternative for the BDO Big Data Storage.	Apache License 2.0	Data Storage

2.4 Query Processing

To provide a platform that allows for accessing data from the BDO Big Data repository, an efficient and effective query processing engine is required. This section presents state-of-the-art approaches that perform query processing over different infrastructures and data models. There are many distributed SQL query engines running on top of Apache Hadoop, which propose different technical solutions but since share a lot of common functionality. For instance, **Spark SQL** is a Spark component on top of Spark core that provides a way of querying and persisting structured and semi-structured data. It uses DataFrames and contains an internal query optimiser. **Apache Pig** is a quite mature platform for writing programs that can run on top of Hadoop and uses its own domain-specific language. **Apache Impala** uses its own parallel processing architecture on top of HDFS instead of MapReduce jobs. Also, **Presto** is a distributed SQL query engine – quite like the others – however, it does not use MapReduce and is very well optimised for fast performance. **Apache Drill** and **HAWQ** are two recent distributed SQL query engines with some additional features in comparison to the previous engines, such as support for the Apache Kudu columnar database (Apache Drill) and support for machine learning algorithms (HAWQ). The main characteristics of the previous characteristics are the following:

- **Spark SQL:** Module for structured data processing. It allows relational queries expressed in SQL, HiveQL, or Scala to be executed using Spark. At the core of this component is a new type of RDD, SchemaRDD, composed of Row objects, along with a schema that describes the data types of each column in the row. A SchemaRDD can be created from an existing RDD, a Parquet file, a JSON dataset, or by running HiveQL against data stored in Apache Hive;
- **Hive¹⁹:** Apache Hive is a data warehouse software that facilitates reading, writing, and managing large datasets residing in distributed storage using SQL;
- **Pig²⁰:** Apache Pig is a platform for analysing large data sets. It consists of a high-level language for expressing data analysis programs, coupled with infrastructure for evaluating them;
- **Presto²¹:** an open source distributed query engine with simple and extensible architecture for running interactive analytic queries against data sources of all sizes ranging from gigabytes to petabytes. Presto was designed and written from the ground up for interactive analytics and approaches the speed of commercial data warehouses while scaling to the size of huge organisations supports pluggable connector to provide metadata and data for queries. It avoids unnecessary I/O latency overhead. Analysts can create custom user-defined functions to migrate easily. Has vectorised columnar processing;
- **Apache Drill²²:** is an open-source software framework that supports data-intensive distributed applications for interactive analysis of large-scale datasets. Drill has a schema-free JSON document model similar to MongoDB and Elasticsearch, without requiring a formal schema to be declared;
- **HAWQ:** is an advanced enterprise SQL on Hadoop analytic engine built around a robust and high-performance massively-parallel processing (MPP) SQL framework evolved from Pivotal Greenplum Database. Hence, it combines the key technological advantages of MPP database

¹⁹ <https://hive.apache.org/>

²⁰ <https://pig.apache.org/>

²¹ <https://prestodb.io/>

²² <https://drill.apache.org/>

with the scalability and convenience of Hadoop, reading and writing data from and to HDFS natively.

- **Impala²³**: Impala enables users to issue low-latency SQL queries to data stored in HDFS and Apache HBase without requiring data movement or transformation. It provides low latency and high concurrency for queries on Hadoop. Impala is integrated with Hadoop to use the same file and data formats, metadata, security and resource management frameworks used by MapReduce, Apache Hive, and other Hadoop software. Impala provides support for: most common SQL-92 features of Hive Query Language (HiveQL) including SELECT, joins, and aggregate functions; HDFS, HBase, and Amazon Simple Storage System (S3) storage; common data access interfaces including JDBC, ODBC, Hue Beeswax and the Impala Query UI; and impala-shell command-line interface.

Table 2-4 presents the summary of tools and solutions related to the Query Processing topic.

²³ <https://impala.apache.org/>

Table 2-4: Query Processing tools and solutions summary

Tools/ solutions	Overall Qualitative Evaluation		Suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots		License	Related with Data Value Chain Topic
	Benefits	Limitations	Score	Description		
SPARK SQL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Efficient caching data in memory between iterations. - Spark RDD are designed to handle the failure of any worker node in the cluster. (zero data loss) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires lots of RAM to run in-memory, thus is quite high. - Comparatively high latency. 	High	Spark SQL is used for query processing executed on top of large datasets and is one of the alternatives considered in BDO for processing Big Data.	Apache license v2.0	Data pre-processing and Curation
Hive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It easily integrates with other critical data center technologies using a familiar JDBC interface - Familiar SQL interface - Offers great scalability and extensibility - Very good performance over huge datasets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sub-queries not supported - Does not offer real time queries and row level updates - Not designed for the online data processing 	High	Apache Hive is used for query processing executed on top of large datasets and is one of the alternatives considered in BDO for processing Big Data.	Open source, Apache License v.2	Data pre-processing and Curation
Apache Pig	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Ease of programming -Optimisation opportunities -Extensibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implicit Data Schema: Data Schema is not enforced explicitly but implicitly. - Delay in Execution: Unless either intermediate or final results are dumped or stored the commands are not executed. - Not Mature: Pig is still in the development. 	Medium	Apache Pig is used for query processing executed on top of large datasets and is one of the alternatives considered in BDO for processing Big Data.	Apache license v2.0	Data pre-processing and Curation
Presto	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specialised SQL operations - Easy to install and debug -Simple storage abstraction -Quickly scales petabytes data with low latency. 	Presto has a limitation on the maximum amount of memory that each task in a query can store	Medium	Presto is used for query processing executed on top of large datasets and is one of the alternatives considered in BDO for processing Big Data.	Apache license v2.0	Data pre-processing and Curation

Apache Drill	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Schema-less query execution for data exploration - In place analytics across historical and operational data - ANSI SQL compliance - Integration with Hive for interactive queries on existing Hive tables - End-To-End security for Data accessed, processed and analysed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not easy deployment. - There are not much of aggregate functions. - Limitations on Join - It has no schema, so it might create some confusion. 	Medium	Apache Drill is used for query processing executed on top of large datasets and is one of the alternatives considered in BDO for processing Big Data.	Apache license v2.0	Data pre-processing and Curation
Apache HAWQ	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full ANSI SQL compliance - High performance - many times faster than other Hadoop SQL engines - Hadoop native and easy access of HDFS data and external system data (e.g., in HBase) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumes many resources - Low maturity 	Medium	HAWQ is used for query processing executed on top of large datasets and is one of the alternatives considered in BDO for processing Big Data.	Apache license v2.0	Data pre-processing and Curation
Apache Impala	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Familiar SQL interface - Ability to query high volumes of data ("Big Data") in Apache Hadoop - Ability to share data files between different components with no copy or export/ import step - Distributed queries in a cluster environment, for convenient scaling and to make use of cost-effective commodity hardware. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - There is no support for Serialisation and Deserialisation in Impala. - No custom Binary Files. It only read text files. - There is no support for transactions in Impala - There is no support for indexing in Impala 	Medium	Impala is used for query processing executed on top of large datasets and is one of the alternatives considered in BDO for processing Big Data.	Open source, Apache License v.2	Data pre-processing and Curation

2.5 Stream Processing

Stream processing is the processing of (unbounded) data that is coming in real-time or near real-time, continuously in a standard interval. Some of the most important characteristics associated with stream processing that have to be taken into account for selecting the best-fitting solution include Delivery Guarantees (guarantee that an incoming record will be processed), Fault Tolerance (ability to recover after network or node failures), State Management (ability to preserve and update state information), Performance (latency, throughput and scalability), Advanced Features (support for event time processing, windowing, etc.), and Maturity (high adoption, e.g. in the industry). The aforementioned factors are being considered for comparing the alternative frameworks and software solutions for stream processing. In order to find the best fitting solution for processing streaming data in BDO (e.g., data coming from weather stations, geospatial data from vessels, etc.) the following technologies have been considered:

- **Spark Streaming²⁴**: it is a high-performance data processing platform; enables scalable, high-throughput, fault-tolerant stream processing of live data streams. A distributed stream processing engine, is an extension of the core Spark API that enables scalable, high-throughput, fault-tolerant stream processing of live data streams. Data can be ingested from different type of sources and can be processed using complex algorithms expressed with high-level functions;
- **Flink²⁵**: Apache Flink is a framework and distributed processing engine for stateful computations that can run over both unbounded and bounded data streams;
- **Kafka²⁶**: Apache Kafka is an open source distributed streaming platform for building real-time data pipelines and stream processing applications;
- **Samza²⁷**: Apache Samza is a distributed stream processing framework; it uses Apache Kafka for messaging and Apache Hadoop Yarn to provide fault tolerance, processor isolation, security and resource management;
- **Storm²⁸**: Apache Storm is a distributed real-time computation system, able to reliably process unbounded streams of data.

Table 2-5 presents the summary of tools and solutions related to the Stream Processing topic.

²⁴ <http://spark.apache.org/streaming/>

²⁵ <https://flink.apache.org/>

²⁶ <http://kafka.apache.org/>

²⁷ <http://samza.apache.org/>

²⁸ <http://storm.apache.org/>

Table 2-5: Stream Processing tools and solutions summary

Tools/ solutions	Overall Qualitative Evaluation		Suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots		License	Related with Data Value Chain Topic
	Benefits	Limitations	Score	Description		
Spark Streaming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very fast streaming processing - Different machine learning operations - Good at iterative, interactive and event stream processing 	Consumes a lot of memory (needs large systems resources);	High	SPARK Streaming has not been utilised so far within the project. It is already part of Apache Spark that is included in the architecture. In the future BDO architecture Apache SPARK streaming can read data from Kafka to combine streaming with batch and interactive queries	Apache License 2.0	Data acquisition and Pre-processing
Flink	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It can deal with both unbounded and bounded streams - It is distributed and scalable - It offers low latency and high throughput - It can operate both in-memory and on-disk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not so big community as e.g. Spark - Not so mature open source project compared to the alternatives 	High	Flink is very suitable for the BDO use cases that include streaming data and can be integrated into the BDO platform with small efforts.	Open source, Apache License v.2	Data acquisition and Pre-processing
Kafka	Kafka is capable of handling high-velocity and high-volume data using not so large hardware. It is capable of supporting message throughput of thousands of messages per second. Moreover, Kafka is able to handle these messages with very low latency of the range of milliseconds	The quality of the solution depends largely on the business code hosting the Kafka infrastructure. Several iterations of development are required to achieve mature support for the use case.	High	Kafka has been evaluated as the most suitable tool for the automatic ingestion of BDO streaming data	Apache license v2.0	Data acquisition
Samza	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good in maintaining large states of information - Fault tolerance - Low latency, high throughput - Mature and tested at scale 	- Tightly coupled with Kafka and Yarn	High	Flink is very suitable for the BDO use cases that include streaming data and can be integrated into the BDO platform with small efforts.	Apache License v.2	Data acquisition and Pre-processing
Storm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Good performance compared to the alternatives (Flink, Samza) for real-time processing - The most mature project compared to the alternatives; Low Latency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It does not support batch processing - No advanced features like event time processing, aggregation, windowing, etc. 	High	Flink is very suitable for the BDO use cases that include streaming data and can be integrated into the BDO platform with small efforts.	Apache License v.2	Data acquisition and Pre-processing

2.6 Analytics

Data analytics is the advanced analytic techniques operating on data sets, giving us support to discover what has changed and how to react. Inside the BDO, the data analytics is responsible for the specification, execution and distribution of the Big Data on both active and historical data of the system (Russom, 2011). It relates different type of data as public data from governments, local authorities, and other non-profit organisations involved in the maritime ecosystem as well as published data from other teams in BDO. In the end, this tool needs to be useful to the different pilots of the projects that have the aim of achieving the different goals of the pilots, as fault prediction, proactive maintenance, mare protection, etc.

In the last decade, there has been a gigantic increase in amount of information and data stored in electronic format (Rangra & Bansal, 2014). This data is growing day by day, starting to be a concern since the obtained data may not be in the desired format. Data mining is an essential tool to analytics, being the process of extraction of predictive information from large data masses, while analysing it from different perspectives and summarising it into useful information. In BDO it brings benefits to facilitate near-real time analysis over the maritime datasets collected during the different projects pilots, in order to assess its performance in different usage context and data types

Machine-learning techniques are also fundamental for the Data Analytics process aiming to improve the accuracy of the developed algorithms and systems based on intelligent adaptive systems. In the BDO context, Machine Learning tools will be used to fine-tune the performance of the designated algorithms and prediction models developed for the project's pilots. Machine Learning is a very broad research area, having many solutions available in the literature.

In this context, the following tools and systems are analysed:

- **Apache MLlib**: Spark's machine learning library, is easy to use, designed for high performance and easy to deploy. It includes a wide set of machine learning algorithms.
- **R-Programming²⁹**: a language and environment for statistical computing and graphics. It is a GNU project which is like the S language³⁰ and environment;
- **Weka³¹**: is a collection of machine learning algorithms for data mining tasks;
- **Apache Mahout³²**: is a simple and extensible programming framework for building scalable algorithms;
- **H2O³³**: is an open source, in-memory, distributed, fast, and scalable machine learning platform for enterprises;
- **TensorFlow³⁴**: is a Machine Learning system with Python and C++ APIs.

Table 2-6 presents the summary of tools and solutions related to the Analytics topic.

²⁹ <https://www.r-project.org/about.html>

³⁰ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/S_\(programming_language\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/S_(programming_language))

³¹ <http://www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/ml/weka/>

³² <http://mahout.apache.org/>

³³ <http://www.h2o.ai/h2o/>

³⁴ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

Table 2-6: Analytics tools and solutions summary

Tools/ solutions	Overall Qualitative Evaluation		Suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots		License	Related with Data Value Chain Topic
	Benefits	Limitations	Score	Description		
Apache MLib	Classification, Regression, Clustering, Collaborative Filtering, Feature extraction, transformation, dimensionality reduction, and selection.	Difficult to implement sophisticated algorithms. Not very mature yet. It consumes a lot of memory and requires large resources	High	This tool is one of the fundamentals for the BDO platform that will be used from the project's pilots.	ALv2.0	Data curation and Data usage
R-Programming	Purely statistical	Less specialised for data mining, requires knowledge of array language	Low	R has several libraries that could be useful to the pilots. However, there are other solutions that due to their scalability are preferable.	GNU General Public License	Data pre-processing, Data curation, and Data usage
Weka	The algorithms can either be applied directly to a dataset or called from your own Java code. Weka contains tools for data pre-processing, classification, regression, clustering, association rules, and Visualisation. It is also well-suited for developing new machine learning schemes.	Poor documentation, weak classical statistics, poor parameter optimisation, weak CSV reader	Low	Weka can be used as a Machine Learning Library for the pilots. Particularly for Pilot 1 and Pilot 3 where predictive analytics and classification techniques are foreseen.	GNU General Public License	Data curation and Data usage
Apache Mahout	It includes a wide variety of premade algorithms for Collaborative Filtering, Classification. Clustering, and Dimensionality Reduction; It also supports a vector math experimentation environment with R-like syntax	Requires strong programming and statistical analysis skills	High	This tool can complement other ML tools (e.g., Apache MLib) for the purposes of the project's pilots. Its latest version introduced a generalised linear algebra engine that runs on top of Spark which can be used together with MLib. Furthermore, Mahout has a wide variety of algorithms	ALv2.0	Data Pre-processing, Data Curation and Data Usage

				implemented, which may not be available in MLib.		
H₂O	Supports various algorithms for data science (e.g., K-Means, GLM, DRF, Naïve Bayes, etc.)	None	High	H ₂ O offers fast and scalable implementations of Machine Learning algorithms. The fact that it can be combined with R, Python and Scala on top of Hadoop/ Yarn or Spark make it an attractive solution for all the pilots of BDO	ALv2.0	Data curation and Data usage
TensorFlow	Numerical computation using data flow graphs	Not very mature yet (i.e., still under development).	Low	This is a powerful tool for numerical computations, but it is mostly used for deep learning applications and thus it is not that suitable for the project's pilots	ALv2.0	Data curation and Data usage

2.7 Analytics Execution Environments/ Notebooks

Analytics Execution Environments are services that enable the remote submission and execution of SPARK jobs for distributed and parallel processing for Big Data. Notebooks offer the ability to both write and execute SPARK code interactively within a single integrated environment, as well as utilise external libraries and visualise input data and analysis results:

- **Zeppelin³⁵**: a web-based notebook with rich language Backend, that can be used for visualisation and exploratory analysis;
- **Jupyter³⁶**: a web-based notebook with Python, R and Scala languages Backend, that can be used for visualisation and exploratory analysis;
- **Apache Livy³⁷**: this is a service that enables easy interaction with a Spark cluster over a REST interface. It enables easy submission of Spark jobs or snippets of Spark code, synchronous or asynchronous result retrieval, as well as Spark Context management, all via a simple REST interface or an RPC client library;
- **Spark Job Server**: Spark Job Server provides a RESTful interface for submitting and managing Apache Spark jobs, jars, and job contexts.

Table 2-7 presents the summary of tools and solutions related to the Analytics Execution Environments/ Notebooks topic.

³⁵ <https://zeppelin.apache.org/>

³⁶ <http://jupyter.org/>

³⁷ <https://livy.incubator.apache.org/>

Table 2-7: Analytics Execution Environments/ Notebooks tools and solutions summary

Tools/ solutions	Overall Qualitative Evaluation		Suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots		License	Related with Data Value Chain Topic
	Benefits	Limitations	Score	Description		
Zeppelin	Enables end user interaction if programming knowledge exists. Predefined web page reports	Requires programming knowledge in order to interact with data	High	This tool is highly relevant to all the pilots and will give the means to BDO users to define custom queries and experiments to be executed in the platform	Apache license v2.0	Data pre-processing, Data curation and Data usage
Jupyter	Enables end user interaction if programming knowledge exists; Predefined web page reports	Requires programming knowledge to interact with data	High	Similarly to the Zeppelin, this tool is also highly suitable to cover the needs of all the pilots in BDO platform	Free for use AS IS	Data pre-processing, Data curation and Data usage
Apache Livy	Restful API for remote spark job execution on a cluster. Simple configuration. Both interactive and batch job execution	Some overhead for session initialisation	High	Apache Livy is integrated in the current version of BDO platform for remote spark job execution	Apache license v2.0	Data pre-processing, Data curation and Data usage
Spark Job Server	Restful API for remote spark job execution on a cluster	More complex configuration	Medium	Could be an alternative for remote spark execution	Apache license v2.0	Data pre-processing, Data curation and Data usage

2.8 Visualisations

Computer based data visualisations are designed to provide users with insights into their data, their inherent structure and relations, thus augmenting human situational awareness and decision making. They provide an ability to comprehend large amounts of data, supporting the perception of emergent properties and the formulation of hypothesis (Munzner, 2014). There are many ways to create a visual encoding of data as a big picture. Visualisation design is full of trade-offs, and most possibilities in the design space are ineffective for a particular task, so validating the effectiveness of a design is both necessary and difficult. Visualisation designers are required to consider three very different kinds of resource limitations: those of the system, of human perception, and of the means of display.

Visualisation literature and design is focused on designing idioms that help users carry out tasks effectively. Visualisation software and tools support numerous Visualisation idioms from static idioms such as bar charts or line charts to much more complex idioms supporting interactions. It is important to keep in mind that there is no visualisation suited for all possible datasets. To overcome this drawback, modern visualisation tools provide collections of visualisations organised in code libraries and business intelligence frameworks. Each category has its advantages and disadvantages; thus, code libraries (mostly written of JavaScript) provide integration flexibility but require programming skills to be integrated in a system. Some of these tools are the following:

- **Leaflet.js**³⁸: open source JavaScript library used to build high performance interactive maps;
- **D3.js**³⁹: a popular a JavaScript library for producing dynamic, interactive data Visualisations in web browsers.;
- **amCharts**⁴⁰: a Javascript Library that offers capabilities of visual representation of data in websites and applications, allowing the creation of flexible pie, column, line, and a number of other chart types;
- **Mapbox**⁴¹: a large provider of custom online maps for websites and applications. Since 2010, it has rapidly expanded the niche of custom maps, as a response to the limited choice offered by map providers such as Google Maps.

Table 2-8 presents the summary of tools and solutions related to the Analytics Execution Environments/ Notebooks topic.

³⁸ <https://leafletjs.com/>

³⁹ <https://d3js.org/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.amcharts.com/>

⁴¹ <https://www.mapbox.com/>

Table 2-8: Visualisations tools and solutions summary

Tools/ solutions	Overall Qualitative Evaluation		Suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots		License	Related with Data Value Chain Topic
	Benefits	Limitations	Score	Description		
Leaflet.js	Can be used on top of D3.js to create interactive maps	Native support only for EPSG 3857 projection	High	Leaflet is currently integrated to the BDO architecture for map visualisation.	BSD-2	Data usage
D3.js	Can be used with numerous of open source libraries in a custom visualisation framework. There are almost one thousand custom visualisations online based on D3.js ⁴²	Not easy integration.	High	D3.js can be an option for charts visualisations, although requires quite an effort to be integrated.	BSD-3/ Free for use AS IS	Data usage
AmCharts	Multiple Line-Charts and Column-Charts.; Can handle real-time data representation; Interactive and responsive charts	-	High	AmCharts is currently integrated to the BDO architecture for charts visualisation	Free single website & commercial license	Data usage
Mapbox	Standardised data flow for large organised projects. Very fast loading due to custom tile generation. Relative ease of customisation of map tiles	System is too complex for simple projects or maps. Has a steep learning curve for developers used to other APIs. Free API call limitations	High	Mapbox is currently used for base map layers in the current version of the platform	Commercial, with a standard number of fee-free requests.	Data usage

⁴² <https://bl.ocks.org/mbostock>

2.9 Cluster Management

Cluster management is an external service, incorporating a backend graphical user interface or command-line software, which is responsible for managing and configuring each node of the cluster in order to perform the task or tasks assigned to it. Cluster management is performed by the cluster manager that works together with the cluster management agents running on each specific node of the cluster. Cluster management can vary from low-involvement activities such as sending work to a cluster to high-involvement work such as load-balancing and availability. In the Big Data Frameworks, the cluster manager is responsible for acquiring resource on the cluster and allocating them to a specific job that is scheduled. The purpose of the cluster manager is the applications to leverage from the allocation and deallocation of various physical resources such as memory for client running jobs, CPU memory, etc. Within the context of BDO the main cluster management services that will be evaluated are the following:

- **Spark standalone cluster manager**⁴³: a simple cluster manager available as part of the Spark distribution. It provides high availability for the master with configured amount of memory and CPU cores, is resilient to worker failures, has capabilities for managing resources per application, and can run alongside of an existing Hadoop deployment and access HDFS (Hadoop Distributed File System) data.
- **Hadoop YARN**⁴⁴: is a distributed computing framework for job scheduling and cluster resource management, with high availability for masters and slaves, support for Docker containers in non-secure mode, Linux and Windows container executors in secure mode, and a pluggable scheduler. YARN combines a central resource manager that reconciles the way applications use Hadoop system resources with node manager agents that monitor the processing operations of individual cluster nodes.
- **Apache Mesos**⁴⁵: a distributed systems kernel, has high availability for masters and slaves, can manage resources per application, and has support for Docker containers. It can run Spark jobs, Hadoop MapReduce, or any other service application. It has API's for Java, Python, and C++. Apache Mesos is a cluster manager that focuses on effective isolation of resources and sharing of applications across distributed networks or frameworks. Mesos is an abstraction layer for computing elements such as CPU, Disk, and RAM. It runs on every machine with one machine designated as the master running all the others.

Table 2-9 presents the summary of tools and solutions related to the Cluster Management topic.

⁴³ <https://spark.apache.org/docs/latest/spark-standalone.html>

⁴⁴ <https://hadoop.apache.org/docs/current/hadoop-yarn/hadoop-yarn-site/YARN.html>

⁴⁵ <http://mesos.apache.org/>

Table 2-9: Cluster Management tools and solutions summary

Tools/ solutions	Overall Qualitative Evaluation		Suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots		License	Related with Data Value Chain Topic
	Benefits	Limitations	Score	Description		
Spark Cluster Manager	Keeps track of the available resources (nodes) available in the cluster Allocates resources based on the core. By default, an application will grab all the cores in the cluster	Poor resource scheduling capabilities	High	Spark Cluster manager is not considered as a candidate for the BDO platform due to the lack of capabilities.	Apache License v2.0	Data storage, Data usage
Hadoop YARN	Offers scalability, high availability, fault tolerance. Central resource manager for Hadoop system resources. Dynamic allocation of cluster resources improves linear-scale storage and processing in a cost-effective way	None	High	Hadoop YARN can be considered as candidate technology for the resource management and the application scheduling	Apache License v2.0	Data storage, Data usage
Mesos	Executes Spark Jobs and Hadoop MapReduce. APIs available for Java, Python and C++. Effective isolation of resources and sharing of applications across distributed networks or frameworks. offers an abstraction layer for computing elements such as CPU, Disk and RAM	Mesos can manage all the resources of the infrastructure but not application specific scheduling	Low	Resource management is performed at infrastructure level thus it is not considered suitable for the BDO platform	Apache License v2.0	Data storage, Data usage

2.10 Security

Security in terms of protection of personal/ sensitive information within the context of BDO will be handled through a two-fold prism, which includes: 1) Data Access Control, and 2) Security of data across their whole lifecycle, from storage, to transit and to use. The forthcoming subsections introduce these categories, as well as a description of the state-of-the-art tools that will be evaluated to employ the most appropriate ones to safeguard security and privacy of information in the context of the project.

2.10.1 Data Access Control (Authorisation)

Access control in general includes authorisation, authentication, access approval, and audit. Authentication and access control are often combined into a single operation, so that access is approved based on successful authentication, or based on an access token. Authentication methods and tokens include passwords, biometric scans, physical keys, electronic keys and devices, and other means. Within the context of BDO, the main Data Access Control tools/ protocols/ frameworks that will be evaluated are as follows (see **Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε.**):

- **XACML Protocol⁴⁶ (eXtensible Access Control Markup Language)** - The standard defines a declarative fine-grained, attribute-based access control policy language, an architecture, and a processing model describing how to evaluate access requests according to the rules defined in policies. XACML is primarily an Attribute-Based Access Control system (ABAC), where attributes (bits of data) associated with a user or action or resource are inputs into the decision of whether a given user may access a given resource in a particular way. Role-based access control (RBAC) can also be implemented in XACML as a specialisation of ABAC. XACML is an authorisation protocol and as such it is not bound to a specific tool. However, several reference implementations can be considered as an instantiation of an XACML protocol;
- **Balana WSO2 reference implementation⁴⁷** - is an Open source XACML implementation which supports XACML 3.0, 2.0, 1.1 and 1.0 version. WSO2 Balana is based on Sun's XACML Implementation. It was the first open source reference implementation of the XACML protocol, and supports the entire lifecycle of authorisation processing;
- **PaaSword Framework⁴⁸** - is also a reference implementation of XACML competitive to Balana, offering on top of the features of Balana, an additional set of libraries that help the user implement the authorisation policies within the java source code. PaaSword has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation Programme Under Grant Agreement No. 644814.
- **Attribute Based Access Control (ABAC)⁴⁹** – is an access control paradigm whereby access rights are granted to users through the use of policies which combine attributes together. The policies can use any type of attributes (user attributes, resource attributes, object, environment attributes etc.). This model supports Boolean logic, in which rules contain "IF, THEN" statements about who is making the request, the resource, and the action. The differentiation of ABAC is the concept of policies that express a complex Boolean rule set that can evaluate

⁴⁶ https://www.oasis-open.org/committees/tc_home.php?wg_abbrev=xacml

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/wso2/balana>

⁴⁸ <https://www.paasword.eu/>

⁴⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Attribute-based_access_control

many different attributes. ABAC provides dynamic, context-aware and risk-intelligent access control to resources allowing access control policies that include specific attributes from many different information systems to be defined to resolve an authorisation and achieve an efficient regulatory compliance, allowing enterprises flexibility in their implementations based on their existing infrastructures.

- **Mandatory Access Control (MAC)**⁵⁰ – is a type of access control by which the operating system constrains the ability of a subject or initiator to access or generally perform some sort of operation on an object or target. In practice, a subject is usually a process or thread; objects are constructs such as files, directories, TCP/UDP ports, shared memory segments, IO devices, etc. Subjects and objects each have a set of security attributes. Whenever a subject attempt to access an object, an authorisation rule enforced by the operating system kernel examines these security attributes and decides whether the access can take place. Any operation by any subject on any object is tested against the set of authorisation rules (aka policy) to determine if the operation is allowed. MAC-enabled systems allow policy administrators to implement organisation-wide security policies. Under MAC, users cannot override or modify this policy, either accidentally or intentionally. This allows security administrators to define a central policy that is guaranteed (in principle) to be enforced for all users.
- **Role Based Access Control (RBAC)**⁵¹ - is an approach to restricting system access to authorised users. It is used by the majority of enterprises and can implement mandatory access control (MAC). RBAC is a policy neutral access control mechanism defined around roles and privileges. The components of RBAC such as role-permissions, user-role and role-role relationships make it simple to perform user assignments. Although RBAC is different from MAC access control framework, it can enforce this policy without any complication.

2.10.2 Data-At-Rest/ Data-In-Storage Security

Security of data in storage is the first of the three parts of the data lifecycle that will be dealt with in the context of the project and is used as a complement to the terms data in use and data in transit which together define the three states of digital data. Data that falls under this category could include files stored on a company's local hard drive, copies of the file stored on onsite and offsite backup tapes and files on the servers of the storage area network (SAN). Data in storage security refers to the preservation of the security, privacy and integrity of data that is stored physically in any digital form. It deals with any type of security around the storage architecture and the data stored on it. Within the context of BDO, we will evaluate the main software solutions and approaches associated with data-in-storage security, as well as the inherent support of security solutions of the Big Data Frameworks that are candidates for adoption and deployment. All solutions are analysed below and summarised in **Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε.:**

- **Symmetric Encryption Algorithms**⁵² - Symmetric-key algorithms are algorithms for cryptography that use the same cryptographic keys for both encryption of plaintext and decryption of cipher-text. The keys may be identical or there may be a simple transformation to go between the two keys. The keys, in practice, represent a shared secret between two or more parties that can be used to maintain a private information link. Some examples of popular

⁵⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mandatory_access_control

⁵¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Role-based_access_control

⁵² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Symmetric-key_algorithm

symmetric algorithms (symmetric-key algorithms) include AES, Blowfish, DES, IDEA, RC2, RC4 etc. AES is not a tool but a symmetric encryption algorithm which has many reference implementations (i.e. tools/ libraries) for many programming languages;

- **Message Authentication Codes (a.k.a. MACs) and Digital Signatures**⁵³ - In cryptography, a message authentication code (MAC) is a short piece of information used to authenticate a message—in other words, to confirm that the message came from the stated sender (its authenticity) and has not been changed in transit (its integrity). A MAC algorithm, sometimes called a keyed (cryptographic) hash function (which is somewhat misleading, since a cryptographic hash function is only one of the possible ways to generate a MAC), accepts as input a secret key and an arbitrary-length message to be authenticated, and outputs a MAC (sometimes known as a tag). The MAC value protects both a message's data integrity as well as its authenticity, by allowing verifiers (who also possess the secret key) to detect any changes to the message content;
- **Broadcast Encryption (Single Sender)**⁵⁴ - Broadcast encryption is the cryptographic problem of delivering encrypted content over a broadcast channel in such a way that only qualified users can decrypt the content. The challenge arises from the requirement that the set of qualified users can change in each broadcast emission, and therefore revocation of individual users or user groups should be possible using broadcast transmissions, only, and without affecting any remaining users;
- **Asymmetric Encryption**⁵⁵ - Asymmetric algorithms (public key algorithms) use different keys for encryption and decryption, and the decryption key cannot (practically) be derived from the encryption key. Asymmetric algorithms are important because they can be used for transmitting encryption keys or other data securely even when the parties have no opportunity to agree on a secret key in private. Types of Asymmetric algorithms (public key algorithms) include RSA, Diffie-Hellman, Digital Signature Algorithm and more;
- **Attribute-Based Encryption**⁵⁶ (ABE) - is a relatively recent approach that reconsiders the concept of public-key (PK) cryptography. In traditional PK, a message is encrypted for a specific receiver using the receiver's PK. Identity-based cryptography and in particular identity-based encryption (IBE) changed the traditional understanding of PK cryptography by allowing the PK to be an arbitrary string, e.g., the email address of the receiver. ABE goes one step further and defines the identity not atomic but as a set of attributes, e.g., roles, and messages can be encrypted with respect to subsets of attributes (key-policy ABE - KP-ABE) or policies defined over a set of attributes (cipher-text-policy ABE - CP-ABE). The key issue is, that someone should only be able to decrypt a cipher-text if the person holds a key for "matching attributes" (more below) where user keys are always issued by some trusted party.
- **HDFS Encryption**⁵⁷ - HDFS (Hadoop Distributed File System) Encryption implements transparent, end-to-end encryption of data read from and written to HDFS, without requiring changes to application code. Because the encryption is end-to-end, data can be encrypted and decrypted only by the client. HDFS does not store or have access to unencrypted data or

⁵³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Message_authentication_code

⁵⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Broadcast_encryption

⁵⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public-key_cryptography

⁵⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Attribute-based_encryption

⁵⁷ https://www.cloudera.com/documentation/enterprise/5-4-x/topics/cdh_sg_hdfs_encryption.html

encryption keys. This supports both, at-rest encryption (data on persistent media, such as a disk) and in-transit encryption (data traveling over a network);

- **Spark Security**⁵⁸ - Spark currently supports authentication via a shared secret. Authentication can be configured to be on via the spark authenticate configuration parameter. This parameter controls whether the Spark communication protocols do authentication using the shared secret. This authentication is a basic handshake to make sure both sides have the same shared secret and can communicate. If the shared secret is not identical they will not be allowed to communicate.

Table 2-10 presents the summary of tools and solutions related to the Security topic.

⁵⁸ <http://spark.apache.org/docs/latest/security.html>

Table 2-10: Security tools and solutions summary

Tools/ solutions	Overall Qualitative Evaluation		Suitability for BDO solutions and to support the pilots		License	Related with Data Value Chain Topic
	Benefits	Limitations	Score	Description		
XACML Protocol	It is the soundest authorisation architecture since it can emulate all known authorisation schemes i.e. MAC, DAC, RBAC and ACL	It is quite complex to be implemented and integrated in an already existing legacy application	High	XAMCL will serve as the basis for the implementation of the Access Control mechanism of the BDO platform	Not subject to licensing	It is related to all phases where data access must be granted
Balana WSO2 reference implementation	It provides reference implementation of all architectural modules required in order to perform authorisation (PEP, PIP, PDP etc.)	Its performance and throughput are relatively low	Low	Balana is not suitable for BDO as it lacks in performance.	Apache 2	It is related to all phases where data access must be granted
PaaSword Framework	It supports semantic reasoning during the policy evaluation. Furthermore, it is more efficient than Balana since it is built on top of a scalable expert system (Drools)	It is more complex to integrate it in an existing product	Low	PaaSword is not suitable for BDO as the integration is rather difficult	BSD	It is related to all phases where data access must be granted
Attribute Based Access Control (ABAC)	Provides dynamic, context-aware and risk-intelligent access control. Allows the definition of multiple access control policies with a combination of attributes. Offers flexibility in the definition of access control policies	Effort to define the appropriate attributes and policies. Increased level of complexity	Medium	ABAC should be considered as a candidate for the access control mechanism of the BDO platform though the high complexity and effort needed for definition of the framework should be evaluated	Not subject to licensing	It is related to all phases where data access must be granted
Mandatory Access Control (MAC)	Definition of security attributes for subjects and objects Definition of authorisation rules based on the security attributes	Complexity of security policies especially for the objects that need to be "trusted" and placed outside the access control framework	Low	Due the complexity of the security policies this model is not considered as a candidate for BDO platform	Not subject to licensing	It is related to all phases where data access must be granted

	Security policies are centrally controlled					
Role Based Access Control (RBAC)	Rights are granted to roles rather than individuals; Users are assigned to roles; Relationships between roles can be defined.	The need for customised privileges and role inheritance might increase complexity.	Medium	RBAC should be considered as a candidate for the access control mechanism of the BDO platform	Not subject to licensing	It is related to all phases where data access has to be granted
Symmetric Encryption Algorithms (AES etc.)	Extremely fast and (up-to-now) and practically unbroken	The key that is used during the symmetric encryption process has to be protected	Low	The AES is not suitable for Big Data platforms as it introduces a significant decrease in the performance of the platform, especially in the analysis process	Not subject to licensing	Data storage
MACs and Digital Signatures	Very fast Several MAC algorithms can be combined	The key that is used during the symmetric encryption process has to be protected	Low	The Message Authentication Codes and Digital Signatures are not suitable for Big Data platforms as they introduce a significant decrease in the performance	Not subject to licensing	Data storage
Broadcast Encryption (Single Sender)	Adaptivity since revocation can be performed in each content transmission	The problem of rogue users exists	Low	Broadcast encryption is not suitable for Big Data platforms as it introduces a significant decrease in the performance of the platform, especially in the analysis process	Not subject to licensing	Data storage
Asymmetric Encryption (Public Private Key Encryption)	It provides maximum security guarantees	Very Slow and Computational intensive	Low	Asymmetric Encryption is not suitable for Big Data platforms as it introduces a significant decrease in the performance of the platform, especially in the analysis process	Not subject to licensing	Data storage
Attribute-Based Encryption	Attribute-based encryption (ABE) can be used for log encryption	Attribute-based encryption systems suffer mainly from two drawbacks: non-efficiency and non-existence of attribute revocation mechanism	Low	Attribute-Based Encryption is not suitable for Big Data platforms as it introduces a significant decrease in	Not subject to licensing	Data storage

				the performance of the platform, especially in the analysis process		
HDFS Encryption	HDFS encryption can provide good performance and existing Hadoop applications are able to run transparently on encrypted data	No significant limitations when it comes to using Apache Hadoop as the Big Data framework	High	HDFS offers encryption at different layers depending on the requirements and needs. The options for encryption on the Application-level, Database-level or Filesystem-level should be considered	Apache	Data storage
Spark Security	Transparent usage of the module from SPARK framework	Only authentication is supported; not encryption at all	High	Spark Security is offering authentication, event logging mechanisms, SSL configuration and SASL encryption thus it is considered a suitable solution for the BDO platform	Apache	Data storage

3 Requirements Engineering Methodology

The requirements engineering methodology developed for the BDO project follows the main Requirement Engineering (RE) concept phases, adapted from the OSMOSE requirements Methodology (used in the FP7 OSMOSE project - 610905) (OSMOSE Project, 2014) and in the IEEE Standard 830-1998 (IEEE, 1998). Basically, the methodology iteratively follows five stages, i.e. preparation, requirements elicitation, analysis, specification and validation (Figure 3-1), thoroughly explained in the following subsections. It is a mixed approach that in the early stages of the project follows a traditional Waterfall method until the first mock-up of the minimum viable product and the architecture are specified, and then applies agile methods promoting various elicitation and development sprints thanks to the feedback loops.

Figure 3-1: BDO Requirements Engineering Methodology

The Preparation and Elicitation phases and the step T2.2 of the Analysis phase of the BDO Requirements Engineering Methodology are accomplishing (as illustrated in the figure with the red square) and reported in deliverable D2.1. The work here developed is a preparation work for the sprints in the implementation work packages, and there is a direct connection with step T4.4 (Architecture Specification).

3.1 Preparation Stage

At the Preparation Stage there are four steps envisaged: Stakeholders Characterisation developed in the frame of task 2.2; Identification of Data Sources (T2.2); Definition of Data Value Chain (T2.3); and Gap Identification (T2.2), all described in this deliverable.

The preparation stage provides the necessary information on the stakeholders to support the elaboration of the scenarios and the identification of the requirements for the implementation of the BDO platform and services. It starts with the stakeholders' characterisation that has been conducted

using a “Stakeholders’ and Value Chain Identification Form” available in Annex A.1. The aim is to distribute this form among the various stakeholder related to each of the BigDataOcean pilots, so they can perform their contributions, expressing their own their activities and how they are of interest to the pilot. Based on this input information, formal description of the stakeholders and scenarios is enabled. This step intends to provide the foundations and guidelines for the representation of enterprise activities, so that the current process (AS-IS) may be analysed and improved. The results of this activity are presented in section 4 of this document.

The next step concerns the Identification of the Data Sources, which is an initial and necessary step to understand the different types of data than can be involved in the pilot. Using a supporting form (see Annex A.1) it is possible to identify the data and information sources required for each stakeholder, as well an indication of whether that stakeholder owns the data or needs to get it from external providers. Thanks to this initial data identification, later it will become possible to describe the actual dataset and identify its importance within the BDO concept (during elicitation phase). After this step, the definition of the integrated Data Value Chain describes how the stakeholders are related amongst themselves in terms of business and data interactions. Results can be found in section 4.5.

The GAP identification & Business expectation is an activity performed in parallel with the previously presented ones. Based on the inputs gathered, an analysis of the processes can be performed to clearly identify the gaps between the current business strategy and technological landscape (AS-IS) and the one desired with BDO (TO-BE scenarios). The pilots involved in the project should be able to derive their business expectations through tangible indicators. The expectations extracted from the TO-BE analysis needs to be discussed with all actors involved in the project, so as to avoid project members adopting false or negative expectations. A transparent presentation of the relationship between the different expectations and the relationship between the different users and the targets of TO-BE scenario is an important factor to be rendered by the project members during the next phase of the methodology (requirements elicitation and analysis). This deliverable presents a condensed result of this step-in section 5.3.

3.2 Elicitation Stage

The requirements elicitation phase represents all the actions performed to acquire raw requirements related to what is intended to develop in the BDO project. To perform these actions, it is needed to understand the knowledge related to the involved stakeholders, by describing the scenarios based on the needs of the project and their own needs, as well as their vision of the project concept. After reaching such understanding, a first formalisation approach of the knowledge is accomplished through a set of raw requirements and datasets.

To get all this information, the consortium members decided to conduct a set of workshops (at least one for each pilot), where in each one, the companies involved in the pilot were present, together with some of the stakeholders interested (including organisation external to the project). In this workshop, the different stakeholder expectations are discussed, including their benefits for the business, data processing needs, and so on. The workshops encourage the discussion and presentation of ideas about the stakeholders, value chain and requirements of the pilots. The form developed for the preparation stage can also be applied here to gather further information.

The next step (**raw requirements**, gathered in the frame of task 2.2) actually represents the collection of a major result from this elicitation stage (see section 5). The ultimate goal is to end up with a

commonly agreed upon collection of raw requirements for the data source usage, identifying the needs to know how to process of the retrieved data. Another major result is the initial list of **datasets**. Following and validating (during the workshops) the data-sources previously identified, it is possible to proceed to the detailed specification of the datasets in terms of format, volume, origin, quality and integration difficulty of the date. To facilitate this task a set of forms (see Annex B.1) have been provided to the different stakeholders so that they can provide this information in a structured manner. Results are presented in sections 4.1.3, 4.2.5, 4.3.6 and 4.4.5.

Despite clearly identifying the raw requirements and target datasets of interest for each pilot, those may still be refined while elaborating the proof-of-concepts in the specification stage, and also following other iterations of the methodology.

3.3 Analysis Stage

The third stage of the methodology concerns the analysis of the requirements previously elicited. In their "raw" stage, requirements are typically unorganised and difficult to communicate to technical teams, sometimes even lacking some detail. For this reason, the analysis phase is quite important in the requirements engineering process.

The first step consists in the categorisation of requirements. It is an organisational activity to group requirements by types (e.g., functional, business), data source, or even domain identifying if they are specific to a scenario or generic/ common to any industrial situation. Other categories may apply if needed. After having them categorised, requirements are still in their raw nature, thus a refinement activity helps to avoid repetition. This step also enables to readjust them, clarifying sentences and making them well formed according to the specific BDO user stories parameters, i.e., unambiguous, complete, consistent, verifiable, traceable, relevant and feasible. This step is already outside of the scope of WP2, being developed in the frame of task T4.2.

During the previous two steps, the requirements manager might (unintentionally) change the meaning of some requirements, thus it is important to have an approval of end-user's step before proceeding. Typically, refined requirements are communicated back to the different stakeholders so that they can articulate themselves about the validity.

From this stage of methodology onwards, it is important to keep the notion that there will be some application specific requirements, while others are generalised so that the project solutions can be applied to different industrial domains. For each of them, the derivation of the technical needs and specifications is responsible for bridging with the technical teams of the project.

3.4 Specification Stage

This stage starts with the prioritisation of User Stories to support the definition of the minimum viable product (MVP – T2.4), to identify the core features of BDO. With this strategy, it is possible to avoid building a platform that the clients do not want and avoiding unnecessary development. The MVP is going to be reported in the deliverable D2.2.

Having said that, the Proof-of-Concept Specification (tasks 6.1 and 6.2 of BigDataOcean) step follows the MVP formalisation, using the knowledge to design the necessary implementations and develop & integrate the existing systems to match the requirements (representing the expectations of the To-Be scenarios). In the Proof-of-Concept specification step, the evaluation of the framework and validation strategy is defined based on small scale test cases connected with the different user story requirements,

for obtaining feedback from the end-users. During this specification of the test cases it will become more evident which datasets will really be required, hence a selection of datasets can be performed⁵⁹. The specification stage is concluded with the architecture specification step developed in the frame of task 4.4. With that, it is possible to identify if discrepancies on the requirements in relation to the planed ideas or concepts. Thus, following this multiple loop back to Elicitation and Analysis requirements phases will be executed promoting agile sprint developments in workpackages WP3, WP4 and WP5.

3.5 Validation Stage

The last phase of the methodology is intended to validate implementations. At the Proof-of-concept Implementation step (WP6) solutions are implemented according to the defined specifications, requirements and relating with the Minimum Viable Product defined. Subsequently to the implementation, an Evaluation step follows, executing the evaluation framework previously defined and checks if the project is accurately responding to the stakeholder's needs. If evaluation results are positive, this means that all the developments are valid and have reached their end.

The Technical evaluation verifies if the implementations meet the functional and non-functional requirements defined. This is a task that doesn't belong to this work package. However, if there is any issue, a specific (technical) feedback is provided to developers, which would accomplish reformulations as adequate. If this occurs, a new evaluation cycle is carried out. The socio-business evaluation verifies if the solution(s) implemented are able to accomplish the To-Be scenarios, and especially if they are able to realise the business expectations and indicators defined. In the case of failure, a loop back to requirements Elicitation and Analysis is necessary.

3.6 Agile Feedback

As explained before, the methodology here presented follows a mixed approach, with the agile part being ensured through this feedback loops that can have multiple iterations considered fit. The idea is that after reaching the definition of the MVP and the first architecture, developments are made on sprints (SCRUM-based) on periods that can go from 1 to a couple of months.

In BigDataOcean each sprint begins with a planning meeting (e.g. teleconference), during which the end users and the development team agree upon exactly what work will be accomplished during the sprint. The duration of a sprint is determined by the complexity of the developments agreed and are a bit longer that what is usual in a traditional SCRUM approach. At the end of the sprint, the team presents its work and if necessary can iterate through the elicitation, analysis and specification phases again.

It is not yet being implemented, but on the course of BigDataOcean the sprints validation can be followed by a gamestorming approach to improve the innovation potential of the project. As it is known, a game may be an alternative to the standard business meeting. Involving a limited set of people and lasting from 15 minutes to an hour and a half, the games test the solutions of BigDataOcean and releases the innovation potential within people, making them comfortable to think *out of the box*. Games may require a few preparations such as sticky notes, poster papers, storyline, etc.

Figure 3-2: Agile Feedback

⁵⁹ With the resubmission of D2.1 following the comments received in the first project review meeting, this step has already been executed and the datasets presented in sections 4.1.3, 4.2.5, 4.3.6 and 4.4.5 already reflect such selection.

4 Maritime Data Value Chain

The term “value chain” includes all the activities needed to transform a concept to a product or service through a set of intermediary phases of production, delivery to final users and final disposal after use. Such activities include design, production, marketing, distribution and support services up to the final consumer (and often beyond, when recycling processes are considered). The term ‘value chain’ refers to the fact that value is added to preliminary products through combination with other resources (for example tools, manpower, knowledge and skills, other raw materials or preliminary products). As the product passes through several stages of the value chain, its value increases (Kaplinsky, 2014).

In a Big Data ecosystem, as the BDO platform, there is a big demand of new data management strategies to handle efficiently the vast proliferation of data from various data sources, as well as to discover new ways to transform data to meaningful information and extract value from it through analytics processes. The Big Data value chain incorporates all the steps that are needed to extract value and insights from the collected data (Curry, 2016). Such definition is also in line with the European Commission⁶⁰ which considers the data value chain as the “center of the future knowledge economy, bringing the opportunities of the digital developments to the more traditional sectors (e.g., transport, financial services, health, manufacturing, retail)”.

Figure 4-1: Big Data Meta-Value Chain.

Big Data Value Chain is used to model all the activities required in an information system. Figure 4-1 below captures the key high-level activities in the Big Data Value Chain:

- **Data Acquisition** is the process of identification of a variety of data sources (e.g., structured, unstructured, data-streams) and the infrastructure required to support data collection, data manipulation and processing and information delivery to end users with low (or at least predictable) latency;
- Following the Data Acquisition, a set of pre-processing methods that analyse the data and enable the data exploration, transformation and modelling into linked information for data analytics purposes are used (**Data Pre-Processing**). Such methods may include stream mining, semantic analysis, cross-sectorial data analysis, Linked Data analysis and transformation, information extraction from streaming or batch data etc.;
- **Data Curation** that will assess the quality of the data, perform data validation, classify and transform data to meaning full information is performed. Data curation is responsible to improve the accessibility and quality of data and ensure that data will be trustworthy, reusable, accessible, discoverable and will fit their purpose (Curry, 2016);
- Afterwards, the data should be stored in a persistent and scalable way (**Data Storage**). The selection of the most appropriate Data Base Management System (DBMS) is not a trivial procedure, as there is a plethora of tools and solutions available, each one serving various application scenarios and optimised for specific purposes. One starting point for opting a DBMS is to select which 2 out of 3 factors of the CAP theorem should the platform covers. According

⁶⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cros/content/big-data_en

to CAP theorem, it is not feasible for a DBMS to be Consistent, Available and Partition-tolerant at the same time. Traditional DBMSs were based on relational model and preserved the ACID properties, making them Consistent and Available. However, the 4Vs that characterise Big Data (i.e., Volume, Velocity, Veracity, Variety) make Partition-tolerance needed. Thus, other DBMSs that are flexible to store unstructured or semi-structured data in distributed fashion (i.e., NoSQL systems), or new architecture schemes that boost query performance (i.e., new SQL systems) while maintaining ACID properties have emerged to cover Big Data requirements and realise the 5th V of Big Data (i.e., Value);

- Finally, **Data Usage** covers the business activities such as decision-support, prediction, in use analytics and data visualisation that rely on the underlying data stored in the DBMS.

Taking this into consideration, subsections 4.1-4.4 describe the considered pilot stakeholders and their expected engagement, configuring the basis for the development of the scenarios and test cases that will be further detailed in deliverable D6.2. Subsection 4.5 details the obtained integrated Maritime Data Value Chain. In subsections 4.1-4.4 a special focus is given to the datasets identified as important for the activity of the stakeholders attending each event and the datasets that effectively will be used during the development of each pilot. For the latter, "Dataset Identification", "Format", "Volumes", "Origin", "Quality" and "Integration Difficulty" are used to describe each dataset used in the 4 pilots, being the presented information further detailed in Annex B.2. It should be noted that the field "Quality" is quantified as "Poor", "Acceptable" and "High" based on ponderation⁶¹ of the marks obtained in the Quality Assessment Forms⁶² associated to each dataset also presented in Annex B.2..

4.1 Pilot 1 Stakeholders

Pilot 1 is focused on Fault Prediction and Proactive Maintenance and Fuel Consumption in large ships. Therefore, two scenarios are considered, which are further detailed in deliverable D6.2.

Regarding the first scenario, it focuses Fault Prediction and Proactive Maintenance in order to identify supplies in machine room equipment of each ship prior to its departure, that are needed to be stocked or changed, and ultimately, if possible, to identify the root causes of the equipment malfunction prior to the estimated Time To Live (by the equipment manufacturers). To do so, historical datasets provided by FOINIKAS concerning a 5-year operation of the vessels, inspection and maintenance actions performed, and defects identified referring to the inspection and maintenance of the machine rooms will be processed. Based upon the analysis of these historical datasets, a failure mode and effect analysis will be performed, in an attempt to identify the frequency and root causes of the equipment failure.

The corresponding stakeholders will focus on extracting insights and hopefully concrete conclusions about equipment changes that took place prior to scheduled maintenance programme, thus signalling a mechanical accessory fault. The failure mode and effect analysis will then take place each time additional data from the maintenance and reporting systems of the vessels are made available, focusing on identifying the probability of the equipment failing in the future, thus better predicting the maintenance requirements, towards a smarter and more efficient risk maintenance management strategy. In terms of external datasets, the consortium will try to enrich the datasets made available

⁶¹ Max score = 14; Poor <= 6 Yes; Acceptable: between 7 and 10 yes; High: >=11 Yes

⁶² <https://usaidlearninglab.org/library/data-quality-assessment-checklist-dqa>

from FOINIKAS, with datasets regarding the operation of additional vessels, inspection and maintenance actions performed, and defects identified referring to the inspection and maintenance of the machine rooms. With regards to real time data, the infrastructure will be in place to facilitate regular scheduled analysis if near real time data from the equipment sensors are made available in the future. A second scenario focuses on the identification of the potential for Fuel Consumption Reduction. From the discussions with ANEK and FOINIKAS, the scenario of fuel consumption reduction is considered to be of interest only for ANEK. Therefore, within the context of this scenario, ANEK wishes to investigate the potential for fuel consumption reduction correlating own historical data, open historical meteorological and environmental data, and near-real-time meteorological and environmental data possibly affecting the fuel consumption. More specifically, the company wishes to investigate:

- 1) The relation between the ship displacement and trim, as well as the meteorological and environmental conditions (e.g. sea condition, wind force, wind direction etc.), with the fuel consumption. The company wishes to investigate the relation and the potential impact of the sea condition, the wind force and probably other environmental indicators, on the ships' average speeds and engine RPMs, which is directly associated with the engine fuel consumption, so as to estimate whether based upon the weather forecast updates, the vessel could initiate the trip with reduced initial fuel load, and whether it could reach the destination on time with reduced speed;
- 2) The financial benefit in experimenting with the number of large trucks vs cars resulting in the same displacement and trim, leading to same fuel consumption but with increased profit.

In terms of external datasets, the consortium will enrich the datasets made available from ANEK regarding the vessels' operation (displacement, engine RPMs etc.), with historical and near-real-time meteorological and environmental data.

Taking this into consideration, **Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε.** presents the data value chain associated to Pilot 1.

Figure 4-2: BDO Pilot 1 Value Chain.

4.1.1 Stakeholder 1 – Ship Owners

<p><u>Stakeholder Description</u></p> <p>Ship owners include the owner of a merchant vessel (commercial ship) and are involved in the shipping industry. A ship owner equips and exploits a ship, usually for delivering cargo at a certain freight rate, either as a per freight rate (given price for the transport of a certain cargo between two given ports) or based on hire (a rate per day). Ship owners typically hire a licensed crew and captain rather than take charge of the vessel in person.</p>	<p><u>Data Sources</u></p>	
	<p><i>Own Data:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical data on incidents, casualties, inspections' results; • Feedback received from vessel's crew and domain experts; • Weather data (even in real-time) coming from open sources; • Vessels' routes and related incidents.
	<p><i>External Data:</i></p>	<p>Buoys indicating ripple levels, water speed, water temperature etc.</p>
<p><u>Direct Value Chain</u></p> <pre> graph LR A[Data Acquisition] --> B[Data Pre-Processing] B --> C[Data Curation] C --> D[Data Storage] D --> E[Data Usage] </pre> <p>Stakeholder's activities are active in the whole value chain.</p>	<p><u>To-Be Targets</u></p> <p>The project can provide a powerful tool that provides proactive maintenance and fault prediction of the ships machinery and equipment.</p>	<p><u>BDO Services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service to provide proactive maintenance and fault prediction; • Notification and alerts to visualise maintenance schedule and incidents.
<p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <p>Shipping Companies</p>		
<p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <p>Shipyards, ship owners, ship managers, maritime equipment constructors, maritime surveyors, ship classification societies, charterers</p>		

4.1.2 Stakeholder 2 - Maritime Equipment Constructors

<p><u>Stakeholder Description</u></p> <p>Maritime equipment constructors are manufacturers of the machinery and equipment of the ships that also provide equipment maintenance plans and agreements with ship owners and managers marine equipment, concerning products such as machine engines, navigation systems, electrical and electronic systems, as well as metal products and materials.</p>	<p><u>Data Sources</u></p>	
<p><u>Direct Value Chain</u></p> <p>Stakeholder's activities are active in the whole value chain.</p>	<p><i>Own Data:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical data on incidents, casualties, inspections' results; • Equipment installations and maintenance plans 	
<p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <p>Ship Companies</p>	<p><i>External Data:</i></p> <p>None</p>	
<p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <p>Shipyards, ship owners, ship managers, maritime equipment constructors, maritime surveyors, ship classification societies, charterers</p>	<p><u>To-Be Targets</u></p> <p>The project can provide a powerful tool to manufacturers in order to automatically gather insights and intelligence about the equipment incidents, maximum tolerance, capabilities and faults</p>	<p><u>BDO Services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service to provide visual analytics about the endurance, incidents and faults of specific equipment over different ships

4.1.3 Datasets used in the Pilot

Based on the forms provided by the stakeholders attending the workshop of Pilot 1, the datasets presented in Table 4-1 were identified as relevant for their operation. After a detailed analysis, the datasets presented in Table 4-2 were found to be necessary to implement Pilot 1. These datasets and associated quality forms are fully described in Annex B.2

Table 4-1 – Summary of datasets identified by the Pilot 1 stakeholders

Pilot 1 – Datasets	
Own	External
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical data on incidents, casualties, results of inspections Feedback received from vessels' crews and domain experts Weather data Vessels' routes and related incidents Equipment installations and maintenance plans 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Buoys measurements indicating ripple levels, water speed, water temperature, etc.

Table 4-2 – Data sources associated to Pilot 1

Dataset Identification	Format	Volumes	Origin	Quality	Integration Difficulty
DS_#1 (Vessels' routes)	Data ob RDBMS (SQL Server) and Export to Excel	For a 5 years period for about 8 vessels the database size is about 4gb	ANEK	High	LOW
DS_#2 (Historical data on incidents, casualties, results of inspections)	XLS and PDF	100MB	FOINIKAS	High	LOW(XLS), HIGH(PDF)
DS_#3 (Weather data)	XLS	300MB	FOINIKAS	High	LOW
DS_#4 (Vessels' routes)	XLS	220MB	FOINIKAS	High	LOW
DS_#5 (Equipment installations and maintenance plans)	XLS and PDF	200MB	FOINIKAS	High	LOW(XLS), HIGH(PDF)

4.2 Pilot 2 Stakeholders

Pilot 2 is focusing on dispersion of the oil spill in the marine environment.

Oil spill models constitute an essential element in contingency planning and in preparing effective response strategies to combat hazardous oil spills at sea. Such models rely on the ability to predict meteo-marine conditions of the sea through the use of cross-sectorial data including atmospheric, wave and hydro dynamical numerical models. Integrating and combining the information on the location, rate, nature and characteristics of an oil spill, the derived forecasted fields are used to provide in advance some knowledge on the fate and track that the oil slick will follow in time. Such a chain of numerical model activities can be automated and run in operational mode to provide a round-the-clock service, relying on the sufficient computer power, which is nowadays becoming more affordable.

The above presented numerical modelling activity is widely used to support operational activities in the marine environment and thus the reliability of its output is of crucial importance. The integration of existing systems and data, to a Big Data infrastructure accompanied by proper services and additional datasets of interest could provide additional information that could increase the forecasting skill and improve the effectiveness of the operational activities; and thus, have significant impact on marine, and environment in general, protection.

As already explained above, the oil spill dispersion models rely on the results of other numerical models that provide the necessary atmospheric, hydrodynamic and sea state input. Thus, what would add significant value is the integration and exploitation of additional information coming from different sectors, that would significantly improve the input into the series of this numerical models interconnected system. This pilot includes a hypothetical accident in the Aegean Sea where a standard forecasting service will provide estimation of the oil spill dispersion in the marine environment based on the standard input provided by the numerical models suite (AS-IS situation). Existing data will be imported in the platform and integrated with relevant data available in the Big Data infrastructure coming from different sources and sectors. The additional cross-sectorial data to be ingested into the numerical models system could indicatively, yet not exhaustively, include weather data from ships or from stations, data from fixed stations (coastal/ offshore) about the atmospheric, hydrodynamic and sea state conditions, relevant satellite data, pollution reports from ship and AIS data. After data insertion, there will be a new run of the oil spill forecasting service that it is expected to provide more reliable results for the area of the accident. The data value chain of this pilot is shown in the **Σφάλμα!**

Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε..

Figure 4-3: BDO Pilot 2 Value Chain.

4.2.1 Stakeholder 3 – Emergency Response Companies

<p><u>Stakeholder Description</u></p> <p>Emergency response companies that are responsible to provide environmental protection services and quickly respond to oil spill incidents.</p> <p>The available services include oil and chemical spill response, hazardous waste management, protection and preparedness for ports and installations, management of distressed cargo, design & production of marine equipment and tank cleaning.</p>	<p><u>Data Sources</u></p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="846 312 999 411"><i>Own Data:</i></td> <td data-bbox="999 312 2051 411">None</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="846 411 999 683"><i>External Data:</i></td> <td data-bbox="999 411 2051 683"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vessel Monitoring System (Vessel Position and routing, Weather, Port information); • Oil Spill Dispersion Forecast </td> </tr> </table>		<i>Own Data:</i>	None	<i>External Data:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vessel Monitoring System (Vessel Position and routing, Weather, Port information); • Oil Spill Dispersion Forecast
<i>Own Data:</i>	None					
<i>External Data:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vessel Monitoring System (Vessel Position and routing, Weather, Port information); • Oil Spill Dispersion Forecast 					
<p><u>Direct Value Chain</u></p> <p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AIS data providers; • HCMR <p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shipping companies; • Port Authorities; • Governmental agencies 	<p><u>To-Be Targets</u></p> <p>The project can provide through Pilot 2 enriched data that enhance efficiency in emergency response for the protection and clean-up of the industrial and marine environment, along with lower mobilisation costs.</p>	<p><u>BDO Services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool to provide descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to vessels' movement tracking; • Tool to visualise the Oil Spill dispersion according to the forecasting model that will be used by the Pilot 2. 				

4.2.2 Stakeholder 4 – National Entities

<p>Stakeholder Description</p> <p>Research and Educational Units, or public and governmental entities, under the supervision of the Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change.</p> <p>These entities provide support on marine environment protection and marine safety, while also promoting maritime transport research and development.</p>	<p>Data Sources</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="882 312 1070 368"><i>Own Data:</i></td> <td data-bbox="1070 312 2051 368">None</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="882 368 1070 579"><i>External Data:</i></td> <td data-bbox="1070 368 2051 579"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oil Spill Dispersion Forecast • Vessel routes, Fisheries </td> </tr> </table>		<i>Own Data:</i>	None	<i>External Data:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oil Spill Dispersion Forecast • Vessel routes, Fisheries
<i>Own Data:</i>	None					
<i>External Data:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Oil Spill Dispersion Forecast • Vessel routes, Fisheries 					
<p>Direct Value Chain</p> <pre> graph LR A[Data Acquisition] --> B[Data Pre-Processing] B --> C[Data Curation] C --> D[Data Storage] D --> E[Data Usage] </pre> <p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HCMR <p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <p>None</p>	<p>To-Be Targets</p> <p>The National entities can benefit from the project in the terms of protection and conservation of National and European interest's biotopes, flora and fauna species, enhance marine mammals' and nature 's protection and clean-up of the industrial and marine environment, along with lower mobilisation costs</p>	<p>BDO Services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool to provide analytics regarding the marine ecosystems • Tool to visualise the Oil Spill dispersion according to the forecasting model that will be used by the pilot 2. • Tool to provide areas with fisheries activity. 				

4.2.3 Stakeholder 5 – Non-Governmental Organisation

<p>Stakeholder Description</p> <p>NGOs cooperate with local communities and authorities to develop and apply pilot management and conservation projects aimed at protecting habitats and species of the Greek Seas and the north-eastern Mediterranean.</p> <p>Additionally, they work directly to stop destructive human behaviour, such as illegal fishing practices, explosions at sea, waste dumping, maritime pollution, erosive overgrazing and other threats to biodiversity.</p>	<p>Data Sources</p>	
	<p><i>Own Data:</i></p>	<p>None</p>
	<p><i>External Data:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vessel Monitoring System (Vessel Position and routing); • Oil Spill Dispersion Forecast
<p>Direct Value Chain</p> <p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AIS data providers; • HCMR <p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <p>None</p>	<p>To-Be Targets</p> <p>The project can provide through pilot 2 enriched data that enhance conservation of the Greek Seas and rescuing marine life.</p>	<p>BDO Services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool to provide descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to vessels' movement tracking; • Tool to visualise the Oil Spill dispersion according to the forecasting model that will be used by the pilot 2; • Tool to provide areas with fisheries activity.

4.2.4 Stakeholder 6 – Marine Research Institute

<p>Stakeholder Description</p> <p>Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR) is a governmental research organisation operating under the supervision of the Ministry of Education, Research and Religious Affairs of Greece.</p>	<p>Data Sources</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="864 312 999 411"><i>Own Data:</i></td> <td data-bbox="999 312 2054 411"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oil Spill Dispersion Forecast Poseidon In-Situ product and Forecast product </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="864 411 999 515"><i>External Data:</i></td> <td data-bbox="999 411 2054 515"> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Copernicus Service </td> </tr> </table>		<i>Own Data:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oil Spill Dispersion Forecast Poseidon In-Situ product and Forecast product 	<i>External Data:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Copernicus Service
<i>Own Data:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oil Spill Dispersion Forecast Poseidon In-Situ product and Forecast product 					
<i>External Data:</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Copernicus Service 					
<p>Direct Value Chain</p> <pre> graph LR A[Data Acquisition] --> B[Data Pre-Processing] B --> C[Data Curation] C --> D[Data Storage] D --> E[Data Usage] </pre> <p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Copernicus Service <p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The HCMR is an organisation that develops activities of public service and support to the navy, Other governmental agencies and local NGOs. 	<p>To-Be Targets</p> <p>HCMR is participating as the pilot 2 in the project, which will provide access to a wider range of data and information in order to enhance existing models and tools. Data from the BDO platform will be retrieved and used as input for the computation of the oil spill dispersion in Mediterranean Sea. The expected output should be enhanced both in speed and precision.</p>	<p>BDO Services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tool to visualise the Oil Spill dispersion according to the forecasting model that will be used by the pilot 2. 				

4.2.5 Datasets used in the Pilot

Taking into consideration the information provided by the stakeholders attending the workshop associated to Pilot 2, Table 4-3 presents the datasets identified as important for their activity. In terms of Pilot 2, Table 4-4 summarises the datasets needed for its development, which are further detailed in Annex B.2 that also includes the full set of quality forms associated.

Table 4-3 – Summary of datasets identified by the Pilot 2 stakeholders

Pilot 2 - Datasets	
Own	External
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poseidon in-situ product and forecast data • Oil spill dispersion forecast data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vessel position and routing • Weather data • Port information • Oil spill dispersion forecast data • Fisheries data • Copernicus data

Table 4-4 – Data sources associated to Pilot 2

Dataset Identification	Format	Volumes	Origin	Quality	Integration Difficulty
DS_#6 (CMEMS Insitu products)	NetCDF	Size: ~500GB 30 Days of data: ~3GB	Copernicus Service partners	High	Low
DS_#7 (HCMR forecasting products)	NetCDF	Current size: 150 GB, Annual Archive estimated size: 1,9 TB Increasing daily by: 5GB	Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR)	High	Low
DS_#8 (Natura 2000)	Shapefile, Spatial lite, INSPIRE compliant metadata set	Data size: ~2.5 GB	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	Acceptable	Medium
DS_#9 (Vessel tracking)	CSV	~50GB (approximately 1 billion records) per year	MarineTraffic (Exmille)	Acceptable	Low
DS_#10 (Port location)	MSAccess DB and Shape file	~20MB (approximately 3700 records)	National Geospatial Intelligence Agency (NGIA)	Acceptable	Low

4.3 Pilot 3 Stakeholders

Pilot 3 is focusing on vessel's maritime security and anomaly detection.

Events, activities and threats in the maritime ecosystem could potentially impact global safety, economic activity or the environment. Understanding of such events, activities, and threats, known as Maritime Domain Awareness (MDA), has been ineffective in the past due to the lack of data. However, current tracking technologies have transformed the problem into one of an overabundance of information, leading to a need for automated analysis.

The major challenge to be addressed in this pilot is developing the ability to identify patterns within vast amounts of data, fused from various sources, so as to act proactively and minimise the impact of possible threats. The understanding of the complex maritime ecosystem though, goes far beyond the simple tracking of vessel positions as they travel across the seas. Anomaly detection can be defined as a method that supports situation assessment process by indicating objects and situations that, in some sense, deviate from the expected, known or "normal" behaviour and thus may be of interest for further investigation. This pilot will perform behaviour and pattern analysis of enhanced trajectories/ vessel profiles exploiting vessel movement information (e.g. counts of turns, turn around, halts, speed ups in a given time window, etc.) and assess the risks to accurately predict maritime security or movement anomaly incidents. The data value chain of this pilot is shown in the **Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε..**

Figure 4-4: BDO Pilot 3 Value Chain.

4.3.1 Stakeholder 7 – Port authorities

<p><u>Stakeholder Description</u></p> <p>Ports are public business entities with responsibility of operating ports and other transport infrastructures.</p> <p>Services include execution of the port policies of the government, general coordination with the different bodies of the General State Administration, training, promotion of research and technological development in matters related to the economy, management, logistics and port engineering and other related to the activity that takes place in ports.</p> <p>In some states a single entity is responsible for coordinating and controlling the efficiency of a whole port system and not only a single port. A specific actor operating at Spain, matching this profile and interested in pilot 3 is Puertos del Estado⁶³, which is formed by 28 Port Authorities that manages the 46 ports of general interest.</p>	<p><u>Data Sources</u></p>	
	<p><i>Own Data:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Port Statistics, • Proprietary AIS Terrestrial Network • ATON installations
	<p><i>External Data:</i></p>	<p>None</p>
<p><u>Direct Value Chain</u></p> <pre> graph LR A[Data Acquisition] --> B[Data Pre-Processing] B --> C[Data Curation] C --> D[Data Storage] D --> E[Data Usage] </pre> <p>Stakeholder's activities are active in the whole value chain. However, vessel traffic and meteorological data received by the stakeholder are limited to a National level.</p> <p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <p>None</p>	<p><u>To-Be Targets</u></p> <p>The project can provide a powerful tool that delivers descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to the status of vessels calling ports</p>	<p><u>BDO Services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool to provide descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to the status of vessels calling ports • Tool to visualise the events related to the vessels' calling ports such as "on-schedule", "delayed", "arrived", etc.

⁶³ <http://www.puertos.es/>

<i>Direct Customers:</i> None	(i.e. "on-schedule", delayed or arrived").	
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4.3.2 Stakeholder 8 – Ocean Observatories

<p><u>Stakeholder Description</u></p> <p>Ocean observatories provide oceanographic data, modelling services and new technologies to support oceanography and marine and coastal research towards integrated and science based coastal and ocean management.</p> <p>A specific stakeholder interested in pilot 3 that matches this profile is SOCIB (http://www.socib.eu/), a joint initiative between the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation and the Balearic Islands Government. SOCIB offers a multi-platform distributed and integrated system that provides streams of oceanographic data and modelling services to support operational oceanography in a European and international framework, therefore also contributing to the needs of marine and coastal research in a global change context.</p>	<p><u>Data Sources</u></p>	
	<p><i>Own Data:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observing facilities (research vessel, HF radar, glider, fixed stations, beach monitoring, satellite); • Numerical models (e.g. high-resolution ocean circulation predictions; wave forecasts; extreme sea level oscillations predictions).
	<p><i>External Data:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numerical models (e.g. Metocean parameters); • Vessel monitoring System.
<p><u>Direct Value Chain</u></p> <pre> graph LR A[Data Acquisition] --> B[Data Pre-Processing] B --> C[Data Usage] </pre>	<p><u>To-Be Targets</u></p> <p>The project can provide through pilot 3 data analytics that in conjunction with other monitoring platforms may be used for collision risk with ocean gliders, environmental risk</p>	<p><u>BDO Services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool to provide descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to vessels' movement tracking;
<p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i> None</p>		

<i>Direct Customers:</i> None	assessment, fishing identification; underwater noise monitoring; marine spatial planning, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualisation tool that enables information exchange and in-time accurate alerts on movement anomalies of vessels.
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4.3.3 Stakeholder 9 - Port/ Cargo community systems

<p><u>Stakeholder Description</u></p> <p>Port/ Cargo community systems are complex information systems that optimise logistics processes especially in international trade hub like ports and airports by facilitating and streamlining data flows between international trade players using our information systems for smoother, more traceable and more competitive transactions.</p> <p>Marseille Gyptis International (MGI, http://www.gyptis.fr/en/) is a stakeholder specialised in the development and implementation of such systems that is interested to pilot 3 activities.</p>	<p><u>Data Sources</u></p>	
	<p><i>Own Data:</i></p>	None
	<p><i>External Data:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Logistics Data; • Commercial Data; • Administrative Data.
<p><u>Direct Value Chain</u></p> <pre> graph LR A[Data Pre-Processing] --> B[Data Curation] </pre>	<p><u>To-Be Targets</u></p> <p>This stakeholder aims to utilise BDO services to extract forecasting models, perform door-to-door cargo tracking and deliver a secure logistics process for resilient supply chain.</p>	<p><u>BDO Services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • API that will deliver data analytics related to vessels' movement tracking in cases of anomaly detection to the user.
<p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <p>None</p>		
<p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <p>Logistics communities which are involved in the port activity: Shipping companies, Shipping agents, Handlers, Freight forwarders, Freight consolidators/ de-consolidators, Terminal operators, Carriers (road haulage, river and rail),</p>		

Shippers, Shippers, Customs, Port Authorities, Veterinary inspection bodies, Plant health inspection bodies, Other governmental agencies		
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4.3.4 Stakeholder 10 - Transport and Logistics

<p><u>Stakeholder Description</u></p> <p>Software technology providers have been developing solutions for the Maritime Industry related to Maritime Security, Transport Logistics, etc.</p> <p>A software technology provider that expressed its interest in pilot 3 activities is eBOS (http://www.ebos.com.cy/). Ebos has developed, among other systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The PSMS a web-based automated dashboard that enables a Port Facility Security Officer (PFSO)/ Port Security officer (PSO) to monitor and enhance security plans and corporate procedures, ▪ The NSW (National Single Window) System, a web based tool, developed to enable businesses in the transport logistics domain to submit regulatory information using a standardised reporting application ▪ The NSW Dashboard in which users can view live all recent submissions/ port calls that are made to the system and all recent responses from authorities that are made for specific CRS submissions. 	<p><u>Data Sources</u></p>	
	<p><i>Own Data:</i></p>	None
	<p><i>External Data:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vessel Tracker (Vessel Position and routing, Weather, Port information); • Shipping Information Pipeling (Vessel Position).
<p><u>Direct Value Chain</u></p>	<p><u>To-Be Targets</u></p> <p>Retrieval of real-time data regarding various vessels, events and incidents to be used</p>	<p><u>BDO Services</u></p>

<i>Direct Suppliers:</i> None	for enhancing stakeholder's provided software solutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> API that delivers notification alerts related to vessel position, weather/ event/ incidents
<i>Direct Customers:</i> None		

4.3.5 Stakeholder 11 – Harbour Pilots and Maritime Consultants

<p><u>Stakeholder Description</u></p> <p>Harbour Pilots are primarily concerned with directing the movement of vessels in a harbour environment from an on-board position.</p> <p>John Betz, who has expressed interest in the pilot's activities, is an expert in the area serving as providing maritime piloting services in the Port of Los Angeles for over a decade. He has been a member Los Angeles/ Long Beach Harbor Safety Committee representing the Los Angeles Pilot Service and is also responsible for updating and maintaining the Los Angeles/ Long Beach Harbor Safety Plan.</p>	<p><u>Data Sources</u></p>	
	<p><i>Own Data:</i></p>	None
	<p><i>External Data:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vessel information and tracking data (from AIS data providers)
<p><u>Direct Value Chain</u></p>	<p><u>To-Be Targets</u></p> <p>Harbour pilots can benefit from this pilot's ability to build smart systems that can learn typical vessel movements and then identify those that are a-typical and alert the user. Furthermore, there are benefits to using the platform to exchange detailed information between ships. Initially such detailed real-time information exchange would allow the</p>	<p><u>BDO Services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ship-to-ship and ship-to-shore monitoring services; Visualisation tool that enables information exchange and in-time accurate alerts on
<p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AIS data providers 		

<i>Direct Customers:</i> <i>None</i>	person controlling the movement of one vessel have access to detailed information of other vessels manoeuvring nearby. Long-term it could provide the basis for autonomous operation.	movement anomalies of vessels.
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4.3.6 Datasets used in the Pilot

The information provided by the stakeholders of Pilot 3 during the conducted workshop enabled the identification of the datasets presented in Table 4-5 as important for their activity.

Table 4-5 – Summary of datasets identified by the Pilot 3 stakeholders

Pilot 3 - Datasets	
Own	External
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural port statistics • AIS (Automatic Identification System) terrestrial network • ATON (Aid to Navigation) installations • Observing facilities (research vessel, HF radar, glider, fixed stations, beach monitoring, satellite) • Numerical models (e.g. high-resolution ocean circulation predictions, wave forecasts, extreme sea level oscillations predictions) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numerical models (e.g. metOcean parameters) • Vessel monitoring • Logistics data • Commercial data • Administrative data • Vessel position and routing • Weather data • Port information • Shipping information pipeline (vessel position) • Vessel information and tracking data (AIS data providers) • Security incidents and vessels' implicated Data

The "Security incidents and vessels' implicated Data" (external dataset) was available through SIPRI database on vessel and maritime incidents. The database contained details of over 2500 incidents of any kind of illegal vessel activities including narcotics-related transfers, untaxed or smuggled commodities such as tobacco, oil and timber, unreported and undocumented fishing as well as the movement of undocumented migrants in vessels that constitute a safety risk to their passengers. While interesting for Pilot 3, these the respective database maintenance has been discontinued and is not available online⁶⁴.

Concerning the development of this pilot, Table 4-6 summarises the required datasets. In addition, Annex 8.2 offers the respective detailed description and quality forms.

Table 4-6 – Data sources associated to Pilot 3

Dataset Identification	Format	Volumes	Origin	Quality	Integration Difficulty
DS_#9 (Vessel tracking)	CSV	~50GB (approximately 1 billion records) per year	MarineTraffic (Exmile)	Acceptable	Low
DS_#10 (Port location)	MSAccess DB and Shape file	~20MB (approximately 3700 records)	National Geospatial Intelligence Agency (NGIA)	Acceptable	Low

⁶⁴ www.sipri.org/research/conflict-and-peace/transport-and-security/vessel-and-maritime-incident-database

DS_#11 (Nautical information maps)	Png tiles	420 GB of tiles with different zoom level	OpenStreetMap Foundation	High	Medium
DS_#12 (Vessels' inspection reports)	Excel spreadsheets	~10 MB	Paris MoU on Port State Control	Acceptable	Medium

4.4 Pilot 4 Stakeholders

Pilot 4 is focusing on assess and select new areas of producing energy from waves.

This pilot aims to improve the characterisation of the ocean as a resource for energy, particularly considering wave energy conversion. This industry is still in its infancy with different technological challenges representing key barriers to its further development. Among others, it depends on the availability of large datasets and physical testing facilities to continue its development. Due to the large costs involved, simulation of converters and the accurate choice of plant locations are extremely important. This pilot will consider data from multiple sources and through the outputs of the pilot, improve the characterisation of studied areas. Studies will be focused in an offshore renewable pilot zone in the West coast of Portugal and obtained results can be easily extrapolated to potentiate other pilot zones in Europe. The pilot services will be evaluated throughout a series of well-established KPIs that evaluate the studies locations in terms of suitability for deployment of wave farms.

This pilot's specific value chain is shown in the next figure. It is composed by five main phases and it has made a mapping between the pilot value chain and the BDO value chain, to facilitate the reading of the pilot value chain. The five main phases (see **Σφάλμα! Το αρχείο προέλευσης της αναφοράς δεν βρέθηκε.**) of the pilot value chain are described in the following points:

- **Modelling** – Considers the attributes necessary to characterise a wave energy harvesting zone in terms of wave energy conversion potential, environment impacts introduced by the deployed equipment, equipment loss of life due to external conditions and the converted energy integration into the existing power system;
- **Measurement and Acquisition** – Refers to wave, weather, environmental, and equipment operation related data necessary to the wave energy harvesting zone characterisation;
- **Data Curation** – Data from different sources are filtered, pre-analysed, validated, and made available;
- **Assessment** – Using the developed models, wave energy conversion potential, environment impacts introduced by the deployed equipment, equipment loss of life due to external conditions and the converted energy integration into the existing power system are assessed;
- **Installation Planning** – In the end of the value chain, the data acquired from different sources is made available and site planning together with equipment planning is supported by the provided wave energy harvesting zone characterisation.

Figure 4-5: BDO Pilot 4 Value Chain

4.4.1 Stakeholder 12 – Hydrographical Centre

<p>Stakeholder Description</p> <p>The hydrographical centre is normally a public organisation that carries out activities in the maintenance of official nautical cartography and related marine sciences (oceanography, chemistry and pollution, processing and data integration).</p> <p>A specific actor matching this profile and interested in pilot 4 is Instituto Hidrográfico de Portugal (www.hidrografico.pt/)</p>	<p>Data Sources</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="864 312 1014 632"><i>Own Data:</i></td> <td data-bbox="1014 312 2051 632"> <p>The centre provides this type of data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bathymetric data; • Tide forecast; • Tide observations; • Monitoring networks; • Oceanographic forecasting; • Other parameters (e.g. Geology, chemistry, etc.). </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="864 632 1014 730"><i>External Data:</i></td> <td data-bbox="1014 632 2051 730">None</td> </tr> </table>		<i>Own Data:</i>	<p>The centre provides this type of data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bathymetric data; • Tide forecast; • Tide observations; • Monitoring networks; • Oceanographic forecasting; • Other parameters (e.g. Geology, chemistry, etc.). 	<i>External Data:</i>	None
<i>Own Data:</i>	<p>The centre provides this type of data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bathymetric data; • Tide forecast; • Tide observations; • Monitoring networks; • Oceanographic forecasting; • Other parameters (e.g. Geology, chemistry, etc.). 					
<i>External Data:</i>	None					
<p>Direct Value Chain</p> <pre> graph LR A[Data Acquisition] --> B[Data Pre-Processing] B -.-> C[Data Curation] C -.-> D[Data Storage] </pre> <p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <p>None</p> <p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public service and support to the navy • All other stakeholder using maritime data. 	<p>To-Be Targets</p> <p>New technologies/ approaches in the acquisition, processing and integration of data, which aim to improve the quality and maintenance of the data.</p> <p>This entity has enormous costs in acquiring data and expects that the platform supports in the prediction of the maintenance of the equipment.</p> <p>The platform provides a predictive model that can reduce the amount of equipment</p>	<p>BDO Services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool to improve the quality of the acquiring, processing and integrating of the data; • Tool to predict the maintenance of the equipment; • Service to recommend the minimum viable equipment for a certain data collection requirement. 				

4.4.2 Stakeholder 13 – Offshore Renewables Service Provider

<p>Stakeholder Description</p> <p>This type of provider is a consulting organisation with a strong R&D background. Its activity is targeting services for offshore sectors such as wave and wind energy as well as aquaculture. Services include marine studies of coast characterisation based on numerical models, using raw data (provided by another entity).</p> <p>A specific actor matching this profile and interested in pilot 4 is WavEC (http://www.wavec.org).</p>	<p>Data Sources</p>	
	<p><i>Own Data:</i></p>	<p>None</p>
	<p><i>External Data:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration); • ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts); • Portuguese Hydrographical Institute; • Fugro Oceanor AS; • BMT ARGOSS; • University of Colombo (USA).
<p>Direct Value Chain</p> <pre> graph LR A[Data Curation] --> B[Data Storage] B --> C[Data Usage] </pre>	<p>To-Be Targets</p> <p>The outline of the project will potentially set out a powerful tool on that the provider may base its activity on offshore renewable energy site selection and resource assessment.</p> <p>Access to new data collected (do not need to be processed) and to new numerical models.</p>	<p>BDO Services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool to provide more and new raw data to support the assessment of the coast; • Tool to visualise the coast with the marine data, positions of the buoys and current plant location; • Tool to forecast the best positions to add new plant location (e.g. wave and wind); • Tool to predict equipment maintenance needs.
<p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data providers 		
<p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology Developers; • Governments/ State Agencies; • Zone Concessionaire. 		

4.4.3 Stakeholder 14 – Zone Concessionaire

<p>Stakeholder Description</p> <p>Entity with the concession for the exploitation of a certain geographical region. In the case of pilot 4, it is targeting regions for the production of energy of the waves, with the purpose of implanting the infrastructures and connection to the public energy network.</p> <p>A specific actor matching this profile and interested in pilot 4 is Enondas (http://www.oceanplug.pt/).</p>	<p>Data Sources</p>	
	<p><i>Own Data:</i></p>	<p>None</p>
	<p><i>External Data:</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portuguese Hydrographical Institute; • Offshore Renewables Service Provider.
<p>Direct Value Chain</p> <p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydrographical Centre; • Offshore Renewables Service Provider. <p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy producers 	<p>To-Be Targets</p> <p>The main objective concerns the provision of an infrastructure to allow energy producers to their solutions. This comprises site planning, equipment maintenance, and data publication. Additionally, the assessment of other alternative energies can also be aimed (e.g. Wind or Solar).</p>	<p>BDO Services</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tool to predict the energy production for selective maritime zones; • Tool to predict the maintenance of the equipment; • Tool to forecast the best positions to add new plant location.

4.4.4 Stakeholder 15 – Energy Producer

<p><u>Stakeholder Description</u></p> <p>This type of entity is responsible for the installation of the power converters and for the energy production process management. EDP Renewables is an example of such entity.</p>	<p><u>Data Sources</u></p>	
<p><u>Direct Value Chain</u></p> <div data-bbox="421 549 584 651" style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #4F81BD; color: white; padding: 5px; text-align: center; width: fit-content; margin: 0 auto;">Data Usage</div>	<p><u>To-Be Targets</u></p> <p>Profitable and effective operation of offshore renewable resources.</p>	
<p><i>Direct Suppliers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offshore Renewables Service Provider; • Zone Concessionaire. 	<p><u>BDO Services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Site planning features; • Equipment maintenance planning; • LCOE assessment features. 	
<p><i>Direct Customers:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy utilities (e.g. transmission or distribution) 		

4.4.5 Datasets used in the Pilot

After the workshop of Pilot 4, which counted with the participation of many external stakeholders, the datasets presented in Table 4-7 have been identified as associated to their activities. In addition, further assessment revealed that the datasets summarised in Table 4-8 are also needed for the development of Pilot 4. Complete details are provided in Annex B.2.

Table 4-7 – Summary of datasets identified by the Pilot 4 stakeholders

Pilot 4 - Datasets	
Own	External
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bathymetric data • Tideforecast • Tide observations • Monitoring networks • Oceanographic forecasting data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) data • ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts) • Portuguese Hydrographical Institute • Fugro Oceanor AS • BMT ARGOSS • University of Colombo (USA) • Offshore Renewables Service Provider • Pilot zone concessionaire own studies • Copernicus data

Table 4-8 – Data sources associated to Pilot 4

Dataset Identification	Format	Volumes	Origin	Quality	Integration Difficulty
DS_#9 (Vessel tracking)	CSV	~50GB (approximately 1 billion records) per year	MarineTraffic (Exmile)	Acceptable	Low
DS_#13 (MARETEC WW3 Portugal model)	NetCDF (CSV available for locations that also correspond to buoys locations in the Portuguese coast)	7.679 Mbytes/day	MARETEC/IST	High	Low
DS_#14 (Copernicus Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish- ocean)	NetCDF	58.803 Mbytes/day	COPERNICUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE (CMEMS)	High	Low

wave analysis and forecast)					
DS_#15 (Copernicus Atlantic Iberian Biscay Irish Ocean- in-situ near real time observations)	NetCDF	1 Mbyte/day	COPERNICUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE (CMEMS)	High	Low
DS_#16 (Copernicus Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish- ocean wave hindcast)	NetCDF	58.803 Mbyte/day	COPERNICUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE (CMEMS)	High	Low
DS_#17 (Global ocean L3 significant wave height from nrt satellite measurements)	NetCDF	>1 Mbyte/day	COPERNICUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE (CMEMS)	High	Low
DS_#18 (Global ocean L3 spectral parameters from nrt satellite measurements)	NetCDF	Up to 500 Mbyte/day	COPERNICUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE (CMEMS)	High	Low
DS_#19 (WPDA Portugal protected areas database)	Kml, csv	< 50 Mbytes	Protected Planet	High	Low

It should be noted that some of the datasets referred in Table 4-7 and Table 4-8 can be acquired from different data sources. For instance, the dataset associated to the results of the WW3 model are available in Copernicus. The same results can also be obtained from NOAA, EmodNET, etc. Additionally, data associated with the wave energy converters' power matrix or electric grid (load) may also be necessary for the development of some test cases of the pilot. That will be fully analysed and reported in deliverable D6.2. Nevertheless, such data is not considered as a data source for the maritime data lake of BigDataOcean. It will be provided by the user when using the platform.

4.5 Integrated Maritime Data Value Chain (1st version)

Producing the integrated maritime value chain is the third step of the Preparation Stage presented before in subsection 3.1. During the first two steps of the preparation stage, we have presented an adapted version of the Big Data value chain of (Curry, 2016) to the actors that expressed interest for each pilot and collected valuable information regarding the actors' position on the value chain, their need of data, their competences etc.. The challenge, then, has been to bring all the pieces together and provide a common framework that captures the activities in each phase of the value chain, the involved actors and the interactions among them (i.e., actor needs and inter-dependencies). Figure 4-6 below depicts the Maritime Value Chain. At the top level the steps of the value chain that will transform information and data streams to valuable data for the end users of the Big Data Ocean platform are given. Then these steps are decomposed to a set of activities extracted from the pilot needs as these have been identified in the corresponding workshop of each pilot. Finally, the bottom level of the figure depicts on the one hand the various stakeholders that are linked to the project's pilots and their position(s) in the value chain and on the other hand, the inter-dependencies among them.

As depicted in Figure 4-6, a list of datasets is needed to realise the envisioned services of the BDO pilots. Further analysis of the datasets details is given in Annex B.2. However, in the value chain process several data transformations are conducted to make these datasets meaningful for the corresponding pilots. Vessel Tracking Data are acquired through AIS provider (for pilots 2, 3 and 4) or by a shipping company (for pilot 1). During the data pre-processing step invalid data are filtered out and the positional data are correlated with weather data and vessel inspections. Then, the pre-processed data are correlated with port geometries and grouped per voyage. Voyages with same departure/ arrival are identified and classified together to produce port-to-port routes. Afterwards, the classification output (i.e., centroids or convex hulls) is stored in the platform and finally, it can be used to visualise safe sea lanes and detect, upon streams of data, vessels outside the safe sea lanes. Port Location Data are acquired from World Port Index and during data pre-processing they are transformed into port geometries (i.e., bounding box) using the geolocation information of the acquired data. The data is then stored in the platform and can be used to correlate with other datasets (depending on the pilot).

Although these are expected to be static data (i.e. not changing over time), they will be combined with streaming data such as vessel positions, or weather data and forecasts. Weather Data (atmospheric, hydrodynamic, sea data such as wave data, wind data, etc.) are acquired through Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Services (CMEMS) or other data providers (e.g. vessels' sensors in case of pilot 1) and correlated with other datasets depending on the pilot (further details are given in the Annex). Similarly, weather data forecasts are acquired through the CMEMS, the POSEIDON System and other data providers.

During the data pre-processing step of the value chain, the data are correlated with other data (streaming or not) and used with forecasting models for the project's pilots (especially in the case of pilot 2). Security incidents reports is a dataset acquired for vessels related to pilot 1 from the corresponding ship owner (i.e. ANEK or FNK). Other than that, there isn't any publicly available dataset. The observations/ deficiencies raised during various inspections, such as Port State Control, Vetting and Internal Inspections are used in the data pre-processing and data curation steps for training the models of pilot 1. Nautical Information Maps Data are fetched and served as png tiles from Open Street Maps and are used in case map visualisations are needed. Vessels' inspection reports are acquired from

Paris MoU. Then, during the data pre-processing step, the data are filtered per country, vessel, or defect type to produce aggregate statistics useful for static anomaly detection.

In the data curation step the raw data of this dataset are correlated with vessel tracking data to produce risk indexes and the aggregates (produced during the data pre-processing step) are correlated with vessel static information (e.g. vessel flag) to detect possible static risks. The analysis is stored in the BDO platform and can be used either for data analytics purposes or to bind possible risks with streaming positional data of vessels. Protected Areas dataset is acquired from the World Database of Protected Areas. The data are correlated with streaming weather data and taken into consideration when identifying candidate locations for possible wave farms (i.e., protected areas are excluded from the candidate locations). The dataset is stored in the BDO platform and can be also used in other pilots for correlating protected areas with other historical or streaming positional data of vessels. European Protected Sites are acquired from the Natura 2000 database. This dataset is correlated with forecasting data produced in pilot 2 to assess the consequences of oil spill pollutions and stored in the BDO platform. As in the Protected Areas dataset, this can be used in the context of other pilots for enriching the situation awareness (e.g. a route may be followed by vessels to avoid crossing protected areas, etc.).

It should be noted that the methodology followed for the Maritime Value Chain gives room to enrich the value chain when new business scenarios (besides the ones covered from the BDO pilots) appear or in case additional stakeholders not already identified express their interest for the project’s activities during the project’s lifetime.

Figure 4-6: Maritime Data Value Chain.

Based on the defined maritime value chain, the involved stakeholders their relation to the value chain steps and the identified interactions among them, the added value that comes out of the stakeholders' collaboration and the expected benefits for each of the stakeholders have been identified and are listed in the Table 4-9 below.

Table 4-9 – Benefits from Stakeholders' Collaboration

Stakeholder	Collaboration Role	Goal/ Expected Benefit
Maritime Equipment Constructors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Owners, Data Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Added value for clients, Data quality validation from Data Users, Improve endurance and reduce faults of vessel equipment.
Ship Owners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Owners, Data Users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve fault prediction of the ships machinery and equipment, Reduce maintenance costs, Reduce fuel consumption.
Port Authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Owners, Data Users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More accurate vessel ETAs, Reduced operating costs, Accurate port congestion analytics
Port/ Cargo community system providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perform door-to-door tracking of cargo, More accurate vessel ETAs, Added value for clients, Cargo risk assessment based on anomalies during vessel voyages
Transport and Logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved Supply Chain visibility, Vessels' voyage incidents analysis, More accurate ETAs, Added-value for clients
Harbour Pilots and Maritime Consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved in-port situation awareness, Accurate detection of vessel movement anomalies
Ocean Observatories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data User 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced collision risks of UUVs with vessels, More accurate environmental risk assessment, Fishing activity identification, Monitoring underwater noise, Marine spatial planning
Hydrographical Centres	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Owner, Data Provider 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved quality of data, Accurate equipment maintenance prediction, Reduced cost of equipment
Offshore Renewables Service Providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data analytics provider, Data User 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automated data analysis, Improved coast and marine situation awareness, Reduced maintenance costs, Added value for clients
Zone Concessioners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data analytics provider, Data User 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> More accurate energy production prediction of maritime zones, Reduced equipment maintenance costs, Added value for clients
Energy Producers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data User 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced operation costs of offshore renewable resources, Reduced equipment maintenance costs, More accurate energy plant site planning
National Entities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Provider, Data User 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance public services, Improve accuracy of existing models and tools
Emergency Response Companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data User 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Faster protection and clean-up of the industrial and marine environment, Lower mobilisation costs
NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data User 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve marine conservation projects efficiency, Increase identification of activities threatening biodiversity such as illegal fishing, explosions at sea, maritime pollution etc.

5 BigDataOcean Requirements

This chapter presents the requirements list obtained in close collaboration with the end user (Pilots) of BDO. The requirements engineering methodology described in section 3 has been followed from the "Preparation" to the "Analysis" phase, and the results presented here benefited from different workshops held, as well as from a first exercise categorising requirements by types (e.g., functional, business).

5.1 Elicitation activities (requirements workshops)

Several materials included in annex have been prepared to enable discussion and increase the results needed to identify the stakeholders', value chain and requirements for the BDO project. This section summarises the execution and planning of the different requirement workshops.

Table 5-1 describes the activities performed by the pilots to support the identification of the stakeholders', value chain, and data sources of the different BDO pilots. Four workshops (one for each pilot) have already been executed, some such as the one of pilot 4 has already engaged a significant number of external stakeholders. For the future, other(s) are being prepared for the second iteration of WP2 as a support to the agile loops. These are focused on the execution of game storming activities, where the different stakeholders can play with the prototype/ mock-up of the BDO system to validate developments and elicit new "hidden" requirements.

Table 5-1: Elicitation Activities (planning and execution).

Activity	Location	Dates	BDO Pilot	Companies Involved
Preparation and elicitation workshop	ANEK offices (Athens, Greece)	2/3/2017	Pilot 1	NTUA (workshop driver); ANEK; FOINIKAS
Preparation and elicitation workshop	NTUA premises (Athens, Greece)	23/2/2017	Pilot 2	NTUA (workshop driver); HCMR
Preparation and elicitation workshop	MarineTraffic (Athens, Greece)	2/3/2017	Pilot 3	NTUA (workshop driver); MarineTraffic
Preparation and elicitation workshop	UNINOVA (Caparica, Portugal)	02/03/2017	Pilot 4	UNINOVA (workshop driver); NESTER, WavEC, Enondas, Instituto Hidrográfico
Game Storming Activities		2º semester 2018	All pilots	

5.2 Raw Requirements

As a result of the pilots' workshops, it was possible to prepare a list of raw requirements, which are presented in the Table 5-2. The raw requirements are clustered by common requirements, which are shared by one or more pilots, and by pilot specific. Additionally, the presented raw requirements were further divided by their position in the Big Data Meta-Value Chain and by their type (Business, Functional and Non-Functional).

Table 5-2: Raw Requirements List.

Position in the Value Chain	Raw Requirement	Categorisation
Common Requirements		
Data Acquisition	DA-01: Use weather data from different sources	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-02: Use atmospheric, hydrodynamic and sea state data from difference sources (e.g. fixed coastal/offshore stations)	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-03: Use relevant satellite data	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-04: Use vessel tracking data	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-05: Use detailed sea data	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-06: Identify existing maritime databases	Non-functional
Data Acquisition	DA-07: Capability to collect multi-format data	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-08: Use of existing maritime data models	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-09: Use of vessels Routes	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-10: Identification of maritime data standards (e.g. GRIB)	Non-functional
Data Pre-Processing	DP-01: Access to data filtering services based on pre-defined criteria	Functional
Data Pre-Processing	DP-02: Access to automatic data correlation services	Functional
Data Curation	DC-01: Ensure a quality standard to data	Non-functional
Data Curation	DC-02: Access to data classification services	Functional
Data Curation	DC-03: Access to data transformation services, enabling format independency	Functional
Data Curation	DC-04: Possibility of correlate several models	Functional
Data Curation	DC-05: Data forecast	Functional
Data Curation	DC-06: Data Interpolation (using one or more data sets)	Functional
Data Curation	DC-07: Further validation of temporal series with satellite data and/ or in-situ data	Functional
Data Storage	DS-01: Persistence	Non-functional

Data Storage	DS-02: Availability	Non-functional
Data Storage	DS-03: Consistency	Non-functional
Data Storage	DS-04: Scalability	Non-functional
Pilot 1 Specific Requirements		
Data Acquisition	DA-11: Use of historical data on incidents, causalities, inspections' results	Functional
Data Usage	DU-01: Provide proactive maintenance and fault prediction	Business
Data Usage	DU-02: Provide notifications and alerts	Functional
Data Usage	DU-03: Visualisation of maintenance schedule and incidents	Business
Data Usage	DU-04: Access to analytics about the endurance, incidents and faults of specific equipment over different ships	Business
Pilot 2 Specific Requirements		
Data Acquisition	DA-12: Access to pollution reports	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-13: Access to AIS (Aeronautical Information System) data	Functional
Data Usage	DU-05: Provide descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to vessels' movement tracking	Business
Data Usage	DU-06: Visualisation of Oil Spill dispersion according to the forecasting model	Business
Data Usage	DU-07: Provide analytics regarding the marine ecosystems	Business
Data Usage	DU-08: Ability to provide areas with fisheries activity	Business
Pilot 3 Specific Requirements		
Data Acquisition	DA-14: Access to security incidents and vessels implicated	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-15: Access to nautical information maps	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-16: Access to crew inspection reports	Functional
Data Usage	DU-09: Provide descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to the status of vessels calling ports	Business
Data Usage	DU-10: Visualisation of events related to the vessels' calling ports such as "on schedule", "delayed", "arrived", etc	Business
Data Usage	DU-11: Provide descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to vessels' movement tracking	Business
Data Usage	DU-12: Provide information exchange and in-time accurate alerts on movement anomalies of vessels through Visualisation tool	Business
Data Usage	DU-13: Provide data analytics related to vessels' movement tracking in cases of anomaly detection to the user	Business

Data Usage	DU-14: Provide notification alerts related to vessel position, weather/ event/ incidents	Business
Data Usage	DU-15: Provide ship-to-ship and ship-to-shore monitoring services	Business
Pilot 4 Specific Requirements		
Data Acquisition	DA-17: Identify the type of data required for each pilot	Non-functional
Data Acquisition	DA-18: Use equipment specifications to enable calculations on end of life depending on the installation location	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-19: Use historical databases of equipment corrosion (e.g. telemetry)	Functional
Data Acquisition	DA-20: Use historical data for planning	Functional
Data Acquisition/ Data Curation	DAC-01: Definition of data granularity, frequency suitable for planning	Functional
Data Curation	DC-08: Correlate with areas of restriction (e.g. migration routes, marine corridors)	Functional
Data Curation	DC-09: Include exclusion areas during site planning (e.g. natural parks, maritime routes)	Functional
Data Curation/ Data Usage	DCU-01: Data available after curation should be independent of technology (e.g. wave, offshore wind, tidal)	Functional
Data Usage	DU-15: Provide equipment Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	Business
Data Usage	DU-16: Provide list of criteria of conditions (e.g. site and/ or application)	Business
Data Usage	DU-17: Presentation of results based on the user profile (templates)	Non-functional
Data Usage	DU-18: Enable benchmarking (e.g. technologies, pilot zones)	Business
Data Usage	DU-19: Enable criteria dependent outputs	Functional
Data Usage	DU-20: Enable sensitivity analysis (e.g. to determine how a change in the renewable resource, against the forecast, creates an impact on LCOE)	Functional
Data Usage	DU-21: Uncertainty characterisation (e.g. risk analysis)	Business
Data Usage	DU-22: Provide Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE)	Business
Data Usage	DU-23: Provide pilot zone classification scale (e.g. availability of supporting infrastructures)	Business

5.3 Gap Analysis

This section analyses the Gaps existing between the capabilities offered by Big Data related tools, addressed in Section 2, and the TO-BE needs resulting from the stakeholder analysis and collected requirements. To conduct such an analysis, the existing Gaps are classified as Gap (when a clear difference exists between the capabilities offered by a tool and the identified needs), Partial Gap (when part of the identified needs can be covered by the capabilities offered by a tool), and No Gap (when the capabilities offered by a tool satisfy the identified needs).

Data Acquisition and Data Pre-Processing related requirements presented in Table 5.2 show a clear overlap between maritime related stakeholders data needs (common requirements), strengthening,

therefore, the motivation for the development of a maritime focused Big Data platform like BDO. Having in consideration the Data Formats and Encoding, the Stream Processing, and the Analytics and Notebooks related tools and frameworks described in sections 2.1, 2.5, 2.6 and 2.7, it can be concluded that there is a **Partial Gap** between identified requirements and the referred tools and frameworks. BDO can directly select and use some of the tools from the Data Collection landscape, but with regards to Data Linking, tools such as LinDA are a good starting point but need further development from BDO to enable requirements such as the automatic correlation of data (DP-02).

As verified for Data Acquisition and Data Pre-Processing, also Data Curation related requirements are characterised mostly by requirements common to the majority of the BDO stakeholders. Despite the interesting features of the reviewed Data Curation tools present in sections 2.6 and 2.7 (analytics and analytics execution environments/ notebooks), serious limitations inhibit their direct use on Maritime Big Data contexts and, therefore, a **Gap** is identified. These limitations are related with at least one of the following factors: i) lack of Big Data related features; or ii) lack of maritime Big Data enabling solutions.

Regarding the Data Storage phase, four needs were identified, namely, availability of services to ensure data persistence, data availability, data consistency, and scalability (DS-01, DS-02, DS-03 and DS-04). Considering the literature review conducted in Section 2.3 and the fact that technology is mature and easily configurable, a **No Gap** is acknowledged between capabilities offered by the respective technologies and the identified needs.

The last phase of the BDO Value Chain refers to Data Usage. This configures the phase with the highest number of pilot specific requirements, reflecting the existing differences among them, where a **Gap** is identified as no specific solutions are found for the maritime sector. There are of course several solutions for query processing (section 2.4), stream processing (section 2.5), data analytics (section 2.6), data execution environments and notebooks (section 2.7) and data visualisation (section 2.8) but pilot-specific solutions need to be developed in BDO. These requirements can be further clustered in Notifications and Alerts (Monitoring), Visualisation, Prediction, and Assessment (e.g. DU-15, DU-17, DU-18, etc.).

6 Conclusions and Next Steps

This document presents a state-of-the-art analysis and evaluation on existing Big Data related methods, components and tools focusing ten technology fields (Data Formats and Encoding; Metadata Repositories and Semantics; Data Storage, Query Processing, Stream Processing, Analytics, Analytics Execution Environments/ Notebooks, Visualisations, Cluster Management and, Security). The main objective of this analysis concerns the definition of a Big Data landscape that can support the selection of technologies for the BDO platform implementation.

Additionally, this document addresses the methodology used for the identification of BDO related scenarios and requirements with a special focus on the Preparation, Elicitation, and Analysis phases. Using the referred methodology, 15 different types of stakeholders were identified together with the relevant datasets. Together with some of these stakeholders, four pilot specific workshops have been conducted, leading to the elicitation of 65 Raw Requirements for the BDO platform (later categorised into business, functional and non-functional requirements). With the collected information, a first version of the Integrated Maritime Data Value Chain and Gap Analysis, relating the Big Data landscape and the stakeholders' expectations, has been achieved.

Other WP2 deliverables, especially D2.2, delivered at month 6 of the project, continued the work, reporting subsequent requirements engineering phases (namely the definition of the MVP, within the Specification phase). D2.3 will report future iterations of the methodology, fine-tuning and validating the results with the support of a more agile approach. Finally, work packages WP4 and WP6 will also be involved in the execution of the remaining steps of the methodology, making the connection between user requirements and technical specifications and implementations, as well as validating BDO with the pilot cases.

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Annexes

A. Requirements Questionnaire

A.1. Template

Pilot Name:	
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Stakeholder	
Name:	
Contact Person:	
Contact e-mail:	
Country:	
Industry Code Activity/Type of Stakeholder:	
Description:	
Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	

Value Chain	
Position in Data Value Chain (Make a circle around your choice):	<pre> graph LR A[Data Acquisition] --> B[Data Analysis] B --> C[Data Curation] C --> D[Data Storage] D --> E[Data Usage] </pre>
Identify your direct suppliers (business relationship)	
What they are supplying?	
Is it a data provider?	
Which data is exchanged?	
Identify your direct customers (business relationship)	
What you are supplying?	
Are you a data provider?	
Which data is exchanged?	

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility

External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility

A.2. Pilot 1 Results

A.2.1. First Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
(Instantiate this tab as many times as the stakeholders identified)	
Name:	ANEK and FOINIKAS
Country:	Greece
Industry Code Activity/Type of Stakeholder:	Ship Owners
Description:	Ship owners include the owner of a merchant vessel (commercial ship) and are involved in the shipping industry. A ship-owner equips and exploits a ship, usually for delivering cargo at a certain freight rate, either as a per freight rate (given price for the transport of a certain cargo between two given ports) or based on hire (a rate per day). Ship owners typically hire a licensed crew and captain rather than take charge of the vessel in person.
Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	Descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to proactive maintenance and fault prediction of the ships machinery and equipment.

Stakeholder in Value Chain			
Where would you position yourself in respect to data in your business?	Stakeholder's activities are active in the whole value chain. Data acquisition, data pre-processing, data curation, data storage and data usage.		
What type of answers are you interested in getting from your data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How often do I need to change part of a ship equipment? • Was is the most efficient, cost-effective maintainance ship plan 		
Identify your direct suppliers (in a business relationship)			
What they are supplying?	None		
Is it a data provider?	None		
Which data is exchanged?	None		
Identify your direct customers (in a business relationship)			
What you are supplying?	None		
Are you a data provider?	None	Which data is exchanged?	None

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
Historical data on incidents, casualties, inspections' results;	Proprietary	Maintenance planning	Particulars, repairs & performance per machinery	Daily	Spread sheet, relational database and reports
Feedback received from vessel's crew and domain experts	Proprietary	Maintenance planning	Incidents, repairs & performance per machinery / equipment	Daily	Spreadsheet, relational database and reports

Ship Log Data	Proprietary	Measure ship characteristics (GPS, echo sounder, gyro compass, anemometer)	Per sec	Daily	Real-time through API
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External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
–	–	–	–	–	–

A.2.2. Second Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
(Instantiate this tab as many times as the stakeholders identified)	
Name:	ANEK and FOINIKAS
Country:	Greece
Industry Activity/Type Stakeholder:	Code of Maritime Equipment Constructors Manufacturers
Description:	Maritime equipment constructors are manufacturers of the machinery and equipment of the ships that also provide equipment maintenance plans and agreements with ship owners and managers marine equipment, concerning products such as machine engines, navigation systems, electrical and electronics systems, as well as metal products and materials.
Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	automatically gather insights and intelligence about the equipment incidents, maximum tolerance, capabilities and faults

Stakeholder in Value Chain	
Where would you position yourself in respect to data in your business?	<pre> graph LR A[Data Acquisition] --> B[Data Analysis] B --> C[Data Curation] C --> D[Data Storage] D --> E[Data Usage] </pre> <p>Stakeholder's activities are active in the whole value chain.</p>

What type of answers are you interested in getting from your data?	What are the common vulnerabilities of the equipment? Unexpected incidents regarding the equipment? Equipment support planning		
Identify your direct suppliers (in a business relationship)			
What they are supplying?	None		
Is it a data provider?	None		
Which data is exchanged?	None		
Identify your direct customers (in a business relationship)			
What you are supplying?	Equipment standards and characteristics		
Are you a data provider?	No	Which data is exchanged?	-

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
Historical data on incidents, casualties, inspections' results;	Proprietary	Keep a tracking record of incidents of the equipment in order to improve the products in the near future	Global	Active	Relational Database
Equipment installations and maintenance plans	Proprietary		Global	Active	Spreadsheet and Relational Database

External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
-	-	-	-	-	-

A.3. Pilot 2 Results

A.3.1. First Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
(Instantiate this tab as many times as the stakeholders identified)	
Name:	HCMR – Hellenic Centre for Marine Research
Country:	Greece
Industry Code Activity/Type of Stakeholder:	Research / Education
Description:	http://poseidon.hcmr.gr/
Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	Gain access to a wider range of data and information in order to enhance existing models and tools. Data from the BDO platform will be retrieved and used as input for the computation of the oil spill dispersion in Mediterranean Sea. The expected output should be enhanced both in speed and precision.

Stakeholder in Value Chain	
Position in Data Value Chain (Make a circle around your choice):	<pre> graph LR A[Data Acquisition] --> B[Data Analysis] B --> C[Data Curation] C --> D[Data Storage] D --> E[Data Usage] </pre>
Identify your query processing needs	
Identify your direct suppliers (in a business relationship)	
No business relationships!	
What they are supplying?	-
Is it a data provider?	

Which data is exchanged?	-		
Identify your direct customers (in a business relationship)			
What you are supplying?	-		
Are you a data provider?	-	Which data is exchanged?	-

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
In-Situ measurements from POSEIDON platforms	Oceanographic and atmospheric measurements		Time: since 2000 up to today, Ongoing operation Spatial coverage: Ionian, Aegean and Cretan seas	Operational	NetCDF, json, csv
Forecast product	Weather, sea-state, sailing, sea-level and ocean forecasts.		Time: Spatial coverage: Ionian, Aegean, Cretan seas and Mediterranean Sea	Daily update with 5 days forecasts	NetCDF

External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
Copernicus Service	In-situ oceanographic and meteorological data,		Temporal coverage:	Actively maintained	NetCDF (free

	forecast, real-analysis data, etc More info at: http://marine.copernicus.eu/		1990 - today Spatial coverage: Global		registration required)
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A.4. Pilot 3 Results

A.4.1. First Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
(Instantiate this tab as many times as the stakeholders identified)	
Name:	Puertos del Estado (Spanish State Ports)
Country:	Spain
Industry Code of Activity/Type of Stakeholder:	Ports
Description:	<p>Puertos del Estado (Spanish State Ports) is a public business entity under the Ministry of Development of Spain, with global responsibilities over the state-owned port system as a whole. It is in charge of the execution of the port policy of the Government of the Nation and of the coordination and control of efficiency of the port system, formed by 28 Port Authorities that manage the 46 ports of general interest. Main competences include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The execution of the port policy of the government and the coordination and control of efficiency of the state-owned port system, under the terms provided in this Law. – The general coordination with the different bodies of the General State Administration that establish controls in the port areas and with the modes of transport in the scope of state competition, from the point of view of port activity. – Training, promotion of research and technological development in matters related to the economy, management, logistics and port engineering and other related to the activity that takes place in ports. – The planning, coordination and control of the Spanish maritime signalling system, and the promotion of training, research and technological development in these matters. The coordination in maritime signalling will be carried out through the Lighthouse Commission, whose structure and operation will be determined by the Ministry of Public Works.

Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	Descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive analytics related to the status of vessels calling ports (i.e. "on-schedule, delayed or arrived")
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Stakeholder in Value Chain	
Where would you position yourself in respect to data in your business?	Data acquisition, data pre-processing, data curation, data storage and data usage. We collect, analyse, curate, store and model vessel traffic and meteorological data received at a National level.
What type of answers are you interested in getting from your data?	
Identify your direct suppliers (in a business relationship)	
What they are supplying?	
Is it a data provider?	
Which data is exchanged?	
Identify your direct customers (in a business relationship)	
What you are supplying?	
Are you a data provider?	Which data is exchanged?

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
National Port Statistics, Proprietary AIS Terrestrial Network and	Vessel traffic and meteorological data, and port statistics	Port Services Observatory: provide real-time information, multi-day	Territorial waters	Active	Online Visualisation and monthly/annual

ATON installations		forecasts, historical information and climatic characterisation of different physical parameters.			reports of port statistics
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External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
–	–	–	–	–	–

A.4.2. Second Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
(Instantiate this tab as many times as the stakeholders identified)	
Name:	SOCIB (Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System)
Country:	Spain
Industry Activity/Type of Stakeholder:	Ocean observatory
Description:	SOCIB is a multi-platform distributed and integrated system that provides streams of oceanographic data and modelling services to support operational oceanography in a European and international framework, therefore also contributing to the needs of marine and coastal research in a global change context.
Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	Collision risk with ocean gliders and other monitoring platforms; environmental risk assessment; fishing identification; underwater noise monitoring; marine spatial planning

Stakeholder in Value Chain

Where would you position yourself in respect to data in your business?	<p>Data Pre-Processing; data usage</p>		
What type of answers are you interested in getting from your data?	Assess collision risk of vessels with ocean gliders; Mapping human pressures on marine ecosystems		
Identify your direct suppliers (in a business relationship)			
What they are supplying?	Vessel monitoring information		
Is it a data provider?	Yes		
Which data is exchanged?	AIS data		
Identify your direct customers (in a business relationship)			
What you are supplying?	Oceanographic data		
Are you a data provider?	Yes	Which data is exchanged?	In-stiu observations, numerical models, satellite-derived products

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
Observing facilities (research vessel, HF radar, glider, fixed stations, beach monitoring, satellite)	Metocean parameters	Coastal and ocean monitoring	2009-present; W Mediterranean	Updated periodically	netCDF, free and open
Numerical models	high-resolution ocean circulation predictions;	Operational forecasting systems	2009-present; W Mediterranean	Updated periodically	netCDF, free and open

	wave forecasts; extreme sea level oscillations predictions				
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External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
Numerical models	Metocean parameters	Operational forecasting systems	2009-present; W Mediterranean	Accessed periodically	netCDF, restricted
Vessel monitoring System	AIS data	Mapping human activities	2015-present; W Mediterranean	Accessed periodically	API, restricted

A.4.3. Third Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
(Instantiate this tab as many times as the stakeholders identified)	
Name:	Marseille Gyptis International
Country:	FRANCE
Industry Code of Activity/Type of Stakeholder:	ICT provider (Port Community System)
Description:	MGI is specialised in the development and implementation of cargo community system which are complex information systems that optimise logistics processes especially in international trade hub like ports and airports by facilitating and streamlining data flows between international trade players using our information systems for smoother, more traceable and more competitive transactions.
Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	Our vision is to connect supply chains through an information system to offer a door-to-door cargo tracking. We are developing a new system, Ci5, which seeks to go well beyond what recent CCSs have offered up to now.

	<p>MGI has kept all the best features of its previous product with new functions that look ahead to future usages.</p> <p>Among the new functionalities, some could benefit from the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forecasting model - Door-to-door cargo tracking - Secure logistics process for resilient supply chain
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Stakeholder in Value Chain	
Where would you position yourself in respect to data in your business?	<p>Data Pre-Processing – Data curation</p> <pre> graph LR A[Data Acquisition] --> B[Data Analysis] B --> C[Data Curation] C --> D[Data Storage] D --> E[Data Usage] </pre>
What type of answers are you interested in getting from your data?	
Identify your direct suppliers (in a business relationship)	
What they are supplying?	Logistics communities which are involved in the port activity: Shipping companies, Shipping agents, Handlers, Freight forwarders, Freight consolidators/deconsolidators, Terminal operators, Carriers (road haulage, river and rail), Shippers, Shippers, Customs, Port Authorities, Veterinary inspection bodies, Plant health inspection bodies, Other governmental agencies
Is it a data provider?	Yes, in our specific business relationship
Which data is exchanged?	Logistics Data Commercial Data Administrative Data
Identify your direct customers (in a business relationship)	
	Logistics communities which are involved in the port activity: Shipping companies, Shipping agents, Handlers, Freight forwarders, Freight consolidators/deconsolidators, Terminal operators, Carriers (road haulage, river and rail), Shippers, Shippers, Customs, Port Authorities, Veterinary inspection bodies, Plant health inspection bodies, Other governmental agencies
What you are supplying?	Logistics Data Commercial Data Administrative Data

Are you a data provider?	Yes	Which data is exchanged?	Logistics Data Commercial Data Administrative Data
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Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility

External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
Logistics Data	Movement report, Movement instruction, schedule, status, ...				
Commercial Data	Shipping order, Shipping release, status, ...				
Administrative Data	Customs declarations, customs clearance, status, ...				

A.4.4. Fourth Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
(Instantiate this tab as many times as the stakeholders identified)	
Name:	eBOS Technologies

Country:	Cyprus
Industry Activity/Type of Stakeholder:	Transport and Logistics technology solutions
Description:	<p>Software technology provider:</p> <p>The PSMS: The PSMS has been developed for the Maritime Industry to consolidate Maritime security related material into a handbook as input. It is a web-based automated dashboard that enables a Port Facility Security Officer (PFSO)/ Port Security officer (PSO) to monitor and enhance security plans and corporate procedures. The PSMS is mending to enable a PFSO / PSO to monitor, assess, evaluate and upgrade existing security measures and not to replace existing plans or documentation.</p> <p>The NSW: The NSW (National Single Window) System is a web based tool, developed to enable businesses in the transport logistics domain to submit regulatory information using a standardised reporting application called the Common Reporting Gateway (CRG) and also to receive, though the system, related response messages from authorities. The CRG application accepts the information in a standardised format called the Common Reporting Schema (CRS). NSW features include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Creating and Submitting new Notification through XML: the user can create and save new Pre-Arrival or Pre-Departure Notification information by uploading an XML file to the system (Figure 1). Then by pressing the "Save" button the system will process the XML and save the new notification to the system. – Creating and Submitting new Notification through filling information in Forms: through Submission System, under 'New Ship Notification' menu, users can create and save new Pre-Arrival or Pre-Departure Notification information. After filling in the required information, the user can Save or directly Submit via Web Service the notification by pressing "Submit" for the Authorities to view it. – Management of Submitted Information: under "Manage Ship Notifications" menu, users can view all information saved to CRG. The user can view the list with all Ships entered in to the System – NSW Dashboard: through Dashboard (Figure 4), users can view live all recent submissions/port calls that are made to the system and all recent responses from authorities that are made for specific CRS submissions. Each row or item in the Outgoing Ship Notifications table represents one notification and by entering one item in the list, the user can view all the information for the specific notification. Each row or item in the Recent Authorities Responses represents an approval status

	<p>response sent by an authority for a specific notification submitted and by entering one item of the list, the user can view the responses received from all authorities for the selected submitted notification.</p> <p>–NSW Risk Management Module: Through Risk Management System, users can specify their own rules to the System in order to assess new submitted information by receiving email and alerts notifications whenever these rules apply. The rules apply whenever a submission to the System satisfies the conditions that were set by the user who specified that rule. Through View Rules Menu under Risk Management, there is a list of the rules specified by the user. Several actions are available for the user for each rule, such as View, Modify and Generate Report.</p>
<p>Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):</p>	<p>Retrieval of real-time data regarding various vessels, events and incidents to be used for enhancing our provided software solutions</p>

Stakeholder in Value Chain			
<p>Where would you position yourself in respect to data in your business?</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Data storage and usage</p>		
<p>What type of answers are you interested in getting from your data?</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Vessel position, weather/event/incident information</p>		
<p>Identify your direct suppliers (in a business relationship)</p>			
<p>What they are supplying?</p>			
<p>Is it a data provider?</p>			
<p>Which data is exchanged?</p>			
<p>Identify your direct customers (in a business relationship)</p>			
<p>What you are supplying?</p>			
<p>Are you a data provider?</p>		<p>Which data is exchanged?</p>	

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
-	-	-	-	-	-

External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
Vessel Tracker	Vessel Position and routing, Weather, Port information	To be utilised in our software solutions			JSON messages through API service
Shipping Information Pipeling	Vessel Position	To be utilised in our software solutions			JSON messages through API service

A.4.5. Fifth Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
(Instantiate this tab as many times as the stakeholders identified)	
Name:	Port Pilot and Maritime Consultant
Country:	USA
Industry Code of Activity/Type of Stakeholder:	Harbour Pilot
Description:	Harbour Pilot
Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	My group is primarily concerned with directing the movement of vessels in a harbour environment from an on-board position. I believe we could benefit from MDA's ability to build smart systems that can learn typical vessel movements and then identify those that are atypical and alert the user. As an example, if MDA system identified a vessel that was entering a maneuverer outside of the normal parameters of speed, position, predicted track, etc., it could alert the user to the abnormality and the user could take action. I also believe there are benefits to using MDA platforms to exchange detailed information between ships. Example, allow Pilot "A" on

	SHIP "A" to "See" SHIP "B's" bridge information, such as rudder angle indicator, ROT indicator, Engine Control, etc. Initially such detailed real-time information exchange would allow the person controlling the movement of one vessel access to detailed information about other vessels manoeuvring nearby. Long-term it could provide the basis for autonomous operation.
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Stakeholder in Value Chain				
Where would you position yourself in respect to data in your business?	<p>DATA USER</p>			
What type of answers are you interested in getting from your data?	As described above, we are primarily interested in seeing more sophisticated information exchange ship-to-ship and ship-to-shore (e.g. between ships and a VTS shore station)			
Identify your direct suppliers (in a business relationship)				
What they are supplying?	At present we are using NORCONTROL to provide ship information and movement information. It is primarily an AIS based system			
Is it a data provider?				
Which data is exchanged?				
Identify your direct customers (in a business relationship)				
What you are supplying?				
Are you a data provider?	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 25%; text-align: center;">NO</td> <td style="width: 25%;">Which data is exchanged?</td> <td style="width: 50%;"></td> </tr> </table>	NO	Which data is exchanged?	
NO	Which data is exchanged?			

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility

External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility

A.5. Pilot 4 Results

A.5.1. Photos

A.5.2. First Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
Name:	Wavec Offshore Renewables
Country:	Portugal
Industry Code Activity/ Type of Stakeholder:	Consultant
Description:	Wavec is a consulting organisation with a strong R&D&I background. Its activity starts in wave energy (since 2003) and has now extended to other sectors such as offshore wind energy and aquaculture.
Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	The outline of the project will potentially set out a powerful tool on that Wavec may base its activity on offshore renewable energy site selection and resource assessment

Value Chain	
Position in Data Value Chain (Make a circle around your choice):	
Identify your query processing needs:	Currently, Wavec does not have operational means to run wind-wave numerical models; Data retrieving is a very time-consuming activity within site selection and energy resource assessment studies
Identify your direct suppliers (business relationship)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology Developers 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consultants 			
What they are supplying?	Ocean Data		
Is it a data provider?	Yes	Which data is exchanged?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wind-wave numerical models reanalysis Seabed geology Maritime infrastructures characteristics and locations, etc.
Identify your direct customers (business relationship)			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology Developers Governments/State Agencies 			
What you are supplying?	Offshore renewable energy site selection and detailed resource assessment for planning purposes		
Are you a data provider?	Not literally	Which data is exchanged?	Wavec provides demand statistical post-processing and analysis, together with data validation

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
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External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration)	Wavewatch III Wind-wave model	Site selection and energy resource assessment	Global	Active	ASCII via SOWFIA project DMP, Open Access
ECMWF (European Centre for Medium-Range)	WAM Wind-wave model	Site selection and energy resource assessment	Global	Active	GRIB Open Access for research purpose (COARSE Grid)

Weather Forecasts)					
Portuguese Hydrographic Institute	Nearshore Wave model Swan (Simulating Waves Nearshore)	Site selection and energy resource assessment	Local	Active	Purchase
Fugro Oceanor AS	Wave Statistics	Site selection and energy resource assessment	Mostly Global	Active	Purchase
BMT ARGOSS	Wind and wave statistics	Site selection and energy resource assessment	Global and Local	Active	Purchase
University of Colombo (USA)	Seabed geology (DB seabed)	Site selection	N/A	Active	Purchase

A.5.3. Second Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
Name:	Instituto Hidrográfico
Country:	Portugal
Industry Code Activity/ Type of Stakeholder:	National Hydrographic Institute (Public organisation)
Description:	The hydrographical institute carries out activities in the maintenance of official nautical cartography and in the field of related marine sciences (oceanography, chemistry and pollution, marine geology and navigation)
Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	New technologies / approaches in the acquisition, processing and integration of data

Value Chain			
Position in Data Value Chain (Make a circle around your choice):			
Identify your query processing needs:	The interest of the institution is to obtain new knowledge and technologies in the areas of data acquisition and processing		
Identify your direct suppliers (business relationship)			
What they are supplying?			
Is it a data provider?		Which data is exchanged?	
Identify your direct customers (business relationship)			
The hydrographical institute is an organisation that develops activities of public service and support to the navy			
What you are supplying?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Official nautical cartography • Marine information 		
Are you a data provider?	Yes	Which data is exchanged?	Data and information on the marine domain

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
Bathymetric data		Cartographic update	Global according to the global map coverage	Relational databases	According to the Hydrographic Institute's data policy
Tide forecast		Support for maritime activities	Annual, national doors indexed in the table of tides	Relational databases	According to the Hydrographic Institute's data policy
Tide observations		Observation and determination	n real time at the positions of the tide gauge	Relational databases	According to the Hydrographic

		of marine constants			Institute's data policy
Monitoring networks		1. Calibration of models 2. Creation of time series	In real time in the positions of the buoys	Relational databases	According to the Hydrographic Institute's data policy
Oceanographic forecasting		Support for maritime activities	Daily with global coverage and different	Relational databases	According to the Hydrographic Institute's data policy
Other parameters (e.g. Geology, chemistry, etc.)		Support for development projects	Depends on the technical requirements of the customers	Relational databases	According to the Hydrographic Institute's data policy

External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility
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A.5.4. Third Stakeholder

Stakeholder	
Name:	Enondas
Country:	Portugal
Industry Code Activity/ Type of Stakeholder:	Concessionaire of the Portuguese pilot zone
Description:	Enondas do the concession for the production of energy of the waves in the pilot zone, with the purpose of implanting the infrastructures and connection to the public network.
Benefit (What benefits this stakeholder expects from the project? To-Be case):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Able to explore another kind of sea energy (e.g. Wind, Solar). • To know which zone of the Portuguese coast is more viable at the level of maintenance cost of the material

Value Chain			
Position in Data Value Chain (Make a circle around your choice):			
Identify your query processing needs:			
Identify your direct suppliers (business relationship)			
What they are supplying?			
Is it a data provider?		Which data is exchanged?	
Identify your direct customers (business relationship)			
What you are supplying?			
Are you a data provider?		Which data is exchanged?	

Own Data Sources (If you a data provider)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility

External Data Sources (If you are using someone else data, e.g. Weather)

Identify the data sources	Type of data provided	Objective of the data	Temporal and Spatial coverage	Status / Maintenance	Data format and accessibility

B. Data Source Description and Quality Assessment Forms

B.1. Templates

Data Sources description form:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	
Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	
Data provider URI	
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	
Data administrator	

<i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	
Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	
Ontologies / Vocabularies used	

<i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	
Raw data sample	
Data schema and documentation	
<i>Main data fields:</i>	

Data Sources quality assessment form:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				

1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2. Pilot Data Sources

B.2.1. Data Source #1 (DS_#1)

Vessels' routes - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	Vessels' routes

Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	-
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	Vessels' routes onmap Online – Realtime Data on RDBMS
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	-
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Some aspects of the dataset are being updated every minute with new data from Vessel's GPS, while others are manually entered at the end of the trip by an operator.
Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	ANEK
Data provider URI	-
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	ANEK
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	-
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	Private, accessible only to the members of BigDataOcean project consortium
Partner	
Pilot case	Pilot 1

<i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
This dataset can potentially be correlated with other datasets from other sources. e.g. weatherdata	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data ob RDBMS (SQL Server) 2. Export to Excel.
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Captured in to XML 2. Transmitted in to RDBMS and stored.
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	-
Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	-
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	-
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	For a 5 years period for about 8 vessels the database size is about 4gb.

<p>Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation</p> <p><i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised?</i></p> <p><i>If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i></p>	The data can be used freely apart from the <u>vessels name</u> which must be anonymised.
<p>Data collection frequency</p> <p><i>State how often the data is collected</i></p>	Online, every minute per Vessel.

Vessels' routes and related incidents - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	n/a
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.2. Data Source #2 (DS_#2)

Historical data on incidents, casualties, results of inspections - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	Inspections historical data of MT NICOS I.V. and MT KRITI JADE
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	-
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	Observations/deficiencies raised during various inspections such as Port State Control, Vetting, Internal Inspections
Temporal and Spatial coverage	Vetting data for KRITI JADE for the period 2008 - today and for NICOS I.V. for the period 2013 - today

<i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Other data mentioned above for KRITI JADE for the period 2008 - today and for NICOS I.V. for the period 2002 - today
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Updated/maintained regularly
Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	FOINIKAS
Data provider URI	-
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	FOINIKAS
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	-
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	Private, accessible only to the members of BigDataOcean project consortium
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	Pilot 1
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	

Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	XLS and PDF
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	-
Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	-
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	-
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	100MB
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised?</i> <i>If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	-
Data collection frequency	Continuously

<i>State how often the data is collected</i>	
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Historical data on incidents, casualties, results of inspections - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	n/a
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.3. Data Source #3 (DS_#3)

Weather data - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	Data from Signals database
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	-
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	Data for wind direction / force and sea condition during voyage, of KRITI JADE and NICOS I.V. vessels.
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Data from both vessels for the period 2013 up to 2016
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Updated/maintained regularly
Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	FOINIKAS
Data provider URI	
Data Owner	FOINIKAS

<i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	-
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	Private, accessible only to the members of BigDataOcean project consortium
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	Pilot 1
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	XLS
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	-
Standard	-

<i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	-
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	300MB
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	-
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	During each voyage, continuously

Weather data - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	n/a
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.4. Data Source #4 (DS_#4)

Vessels' routes - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	Data from Signals database
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	-
General description of dataset	Vessels' routes - Data for the routes/voyages of KRITI JADE and NICOS I.V. vessels

<i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Data for both vessels for the period 2013 up to 2016
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Updated/maintained regularly
Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	FOINIKAS
Data provider URI	-
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	FOINIKAS
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	-
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	Private, accessible only to the members of BigDataOcean project consortium
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	Pilot 1
Possible scenario coverage	

<i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	XLS
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	-
Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	-
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	-
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	220MB
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised?</i> <i>If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	-

Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	During each voyage, continuously
---	----------------------------------

Vessels' routes - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	n/a
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				

1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.5. Data Source #5 (DS_#5)

Equipment installations and maintenance plans - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	Plan Maintenance System Database Defects Database
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	PMS
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	Plan maintenance and defects of the vessels' machinery
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Data from both vessels (KRITI JADE and NICOS I.V.) for the period 2013 - 2016
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Updated/maintained regularly
Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	FOINIKAS
Data provider URI	

Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	FOINIKAS
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	-
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	Private, accessible only to the members of BigDataOcean project consortium
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	Pilot 1
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	XLS and PDF
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	-
Standard	-

<i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	-
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	200MB
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	-
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	Continuously

Equipment installations and maintenance plans - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	n/a
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.6. Data Source #6 (DS_#6)

CMEMS Insitu products - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	Copernicus Marine Environment monitoring service, Insitu Thematic Assembly Center Alternate title: COPERNICUS – CMEMS Insitu TAC
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	CMEMS INSTAC
General description of dataset	http://marine.copernicus.eu/

<i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Temporal coverage: 1990 - today Spatial coverage: Global
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	onGoing: data is continually being updated continual maintenance -> data is repeatedly and frequently updated
Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	Copernicus Service partners
Data provider URI	http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/access-to-products/
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	Information is provided in the relative metadata when downloading products
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/contact-us/
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	Accessible at Registration required (free): http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/register-now/ License: Any users of the data from HCMR are required to display citation in any publication or product using data. User must contact PI prior to any commercial use of data. : "These data were collected and made freely available by Copernicus and the programs that contribute to it." If relevant, also credit other organisations involved in collection of this particular datastream (as listed in 'citation' in the metadata record).
Partner	
Pilot case	Dataset contains dataset from Pilot 2

<i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	Could be probably reused in Pilot 1
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
Evaluation of the forecasting products using nearby near real time data	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	available in netCDF
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	These data were obtained using a range of sensors. The raw data were processed to produce a single netCDF file per instrument. The processing includes: * Pre-processing tasks like local time to UTC time conversion; * Calculation of a depth parameter based on pressure values. * Automatic quality control (QC) procedures, checking for impossible date or location, measurements taken out of water, outliers, spikes and flatlines (suspect data are flagged but never removed); * A visual check of the data and Delayed mode QC flags by the operator; * Writing the data and QC flags to Oceansites compliant NetCDF files containing QC'd data sets. For more details, please see the OceanSITES User's Manual (http://www.oceansites.org/docs/oceansites_user_manual_ver1_1.pdf) and the metadata attached to each data set.
Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	Copernicus system requirements and main list of parameters distributes (http://doi.org/10.13155/40846)
Ontologies / Vocabularies used	Concepts from OceanSITES (http://www.oceansites.org/docs/oceansites_user_manual_ver1_1.pdf)

<p><i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i></p>	<p>Parameters in In Situ TAC parameters list version 3.0.0 (http://doi.org/10.13155/40846) http://oceanobs.mongoos.eu/page_parameters.php</p> <p>CF conventions: http://cfconventions.org/cf-conventions/v1.6.0/cf-conventions.html</p>
<p>Data Size</p> <p><i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i></p>	<p>Size: ~500GB</p> <p>30Days data: ~3GB</p>
<p>Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation</p> <p><i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i></p>	<p>These data follow Copernicus standards; they are public and free of charge. User assumes all risk for use of data. User must display citation in any publication or product using data. User must contact PI prior to any commercial use of data.</p> <p>No fields are set under access control, no data has to be anonymised.</p>
<p>Data collection frequency</p> <p><i>State how often the data is collected</i></p>	<p>For operating stations, data update is done on daily basis</p>
<p>Raw data sample (or complete raw data if possible)</p>	
<p><i>Provide data sample as a separate file. If the dataset is available in different formats provide different sample files.</i></p> <pre>netcdf MO_LATEST_TS_MO_SARON_20170125 { dimensions: TIME = UNLIMITED ; // (8 currently) LATITUDE = 8 ; LONGITUDE = 8 ; POSITION = 8 ; DEPTH = 2 ; data: TIME = 24496, 24496.125, 24496.25, 24496.375, 24496.5, 24496.625, 24496.75, 24496.875 ; TIME_QC = 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1 ;</pre>	

LATITUDE = 37.5968, 37.5968, 37.5968, 37.5968, 37.5968, 37.5968, 37.5968,
37.5968 ;

LONGITUDE = 23.5615, 23.5615, 23.5615, 23.5615, 23.5615, 23.5615, 23.5615,
23.5615 ;

POSITION_QC = 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 1 ;

GPS_LATITUDE = 37.60742, 37.60742, 37.60742, 37.60742, 37.60742, 37.60742,
37.60742, 37.60742 ;

GPS_LONGITUDE = 23.56934, 23.56934, 23.56934, 23.56689, 23.56689, 23.56689,
23.56689, 23.56689 ;

GPS_POSITION_QC = 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0 ;

DEPH =

0, 3,
0, 3,
0, 3,
0, 3,
0, 3,
0, 3,
0, 3,
0, 3,
0, 3 ;

DEPH_QC =

1, 1,
1, 1,
1, 1,
1, 1,
1, 1,
1, 1,
1, 1,
1, 1,
1, 1 ;

```
DEPH_DM =
```

```
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR" ;
```

```
TEMP =
```

```
_ , 14.47876,  
_ , 14.58252,  
_ , 14.53369,  
_ , 14.552,  
_ , 14.55811,  
_ , 14.5459,  
_ , 14.53979,  
_ , 14.53979 ;
```

```
TEMP_QC =
```

```
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 4 ;
```

```
TEMP_DM =
```

```
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",
```

```
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR" ;  
  
PSAL =  
_, 37.84424,  
_, 37.87598,  
_, 37.93213,  
_, 37.84668,  
_, 37.77832,  
_, 37.72705,  
_, 37.90039,  
_, 37.87842 ;  
  
PSAL_QC =  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1 ;  
  
PSAL_DM =  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR" ;  
  
HCSP =
```

```
_, 1.169678,  
_, 0.7697754,  
_, 2.252197,  
_, 0.5163574,  
_, 0.8510742,  
_, 1.129395,  
_, 1.071533,  
_, 0.4057617 ;
```

HCSP_QC =

```
9, 4,  
9, 4,  
9, 4,  
9, 4,  
9, 3,  
9, 4,  
9, 4,  
9, 0 ;
```

HCSP_DM =

```
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR" ;
```

HCDT =

```
_, 243.6328,  
_, 248.4668,  
_, 315.0879,  
_, 348.4863,  
_, 97.29492,  
_, 27.07031,
```

```
_, 111.9727,  
_, 344.0039 ;
```

```
HCDT_QC =
```

```
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 1,  
9, 3,  
9, 3,  
9, 1,  
9, 3,  
9, 0 ;
```

```
HCDT_DM =
```

```
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR" ;
```

```
ATMS =
```

```
1013.027, _,  
1013.885, _,  
1015.466, _,  
1018.673, _,  
1018.763, _,  
1019.847, _,  
1021.067, _,  
1022.286, _ ;
```

```
ATMS_QC =
```

```
1, 9,  
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
0, 9 ;
```

```
ATMS_DM =
```

```
"RR",
```

```
"RR" ;
```

```
DRYT =
```

```
14.2749, _
```

```
14.05518, _
```

```
14.2627, _
```

```
14.05518, _
```

```
14.18945, _
```

```
13.94531, _
```

```
13.44482, _
```

```
13.53027, _ ;
```

```
DRYT_QC =
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
0, 9 ;
```

```
DRYT_DM =
```

```
"RR",
```

```
"RR" ;
```

```
WSPD =
```

```
6.1084, _,
```

```
7.57324, _,
```

```
9.12598, _,
```

```
8.8916, _,
```

```
6.5332, _,
```

```
8.0127, _,
```

```
6.00586, _,
```

```
6.24023, _ ;
```

```
WSPD_QC =
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
0, 9 ;
```

```
WSPD_DM =
```

```
"RR",
```

```
"RR" ;
```

```
GSPD =
```

```
8.36426, _,
```

```
9.3457, _,
```

```
11.92383, _,
```

```
11.61621, _,
```

```
9.12598, _,
```

```
11.08887, _,
```

```
7.57324, _,
```

```
8.11523, _ ;
```

```
GSPD_QC =
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
0, 9 ;
```

```
GSPD_DM =
```

```
"RR",
```

```
"RR" ;
```

```
WDIR =
```

```
336.4453, _  
329.4141, _  
336.2695, _  
350.4199, _  
343.0371, _  
357.0117, _  
355.6055, _  
346.9043, _ ;
```

```
WDIR_QC =
```

```
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
0, 9 ;
```

```
WDIR_DM =
```

```
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR" ;
```

```
VTZA =
```

```
3.39111, _  
3.31055, _  
3.42773, _  
3.5083, _  
3.5376, _  
3.59619, _
```

```
3.28857, _ ,
```

```
3.28857, _ ;
```

```
VTZA_QC =
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
1, 9,
```

```
0, 9 ;
```

```
VTZA_DM =
```

```
"RR",
```

```
"RR" ;
```

```
VTPK =
```

```
3.98438, _ ,
```

```
4.16016, _ ,
```

```
4.14551, _ ,
```

```
4.48975, _ ,
```

```
4.67285, _ ,
```

```
4.19678, _ ,
```

```
3.86719, _ ,
```

```
3.39844, _ ;
```

```
VTPK_QC =
```

```
0, 9,
```

```
0, 9,
```

```
0, 9,  
0, 9,  
0, 9,  
0, 9,  
0, 9,  
0, 9 ;  
  
VTPK_DM =  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR" ;  
  
VTDH =  
0.76172, _  
0.76172, _  
0.82031, _  
0.87402, _  
0.92773, _  
0.98633, _  
0.78125, _  
0.78613, _ ;  
  
VTDH_QC =  
1, 9,  
4, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
0, 9 ;
```

```
VTDH_DM =
```

```
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR" ;
```

```
VDIR =
```

```
5.97656, _  
6.24023, _  
15.82031, _  
12.12891, _  
9.4043, _  
11.60156, _  
22.14844, _  
49.6582, _ ;
```

```
VDIR_QC =
```

```
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
1, 9,  
0, 9 ;
```

```
VDIR_DM =
```

```
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",
```

```
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR",  
"RR" ;  
}
```

Data schema and documentation

Provide data schema, description of data fields and other documentation related to the dataset as a separate file.

```
netcdf MO_LATEST_TS_MO_SARON_20170125 {
```

```
dimensions:
```

```
    TIME = UNLIMITED ; // (8 currently)
```

```
    LATITUDE = 8 ;
```

```
    LONGITUDE = 8 ;
```

```
    POSITION = 8 ;
```

```
    DEPTH = 2 ;
```

```
variables:
```

```
    double TIME(TIME) ;
```

```
        TIME:long_name = "time" ;
```

```
        TIME:standard_name = "time" ;
```

```
        TIME:units = "days since 1950-01-01T00:00:00Z" ;
```

```
        TIME:valid_min = 0.f ;
```

```
        TIME:valid_max = 90000.f ;
```

```
        TIME:QC_indicator = 1b ;
```

```
        TIME:QC_procedure = 1b ;
```

```
        TIME:uncertainty = " " ;
```

```
        TIME:comment = " " ;
```

```
        TIME:axis = "T" ;
```

```
    byte TIME_QC(TIME) ;
```

```
        TIME_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
```

```
        TIME_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
```

```
        TIME_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
```

```
        TIME_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
```

```
        TIME_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
```

```
        TIME_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
```

```
TIME_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
float LATITUDE(LATITUDE) ;
    LATITUDE:long_name = "Latitude of each location" ;
    LATITUDE:standard_name = "latitude" ;
    LATITUDE:units = "degrees_north" ;
    LATITUDE:_FillValue = 99999.f ;
    LATITUDE:valid_min = -90.f ;
    LATITUDE:valid_max = 90.f ;
    LATITUDE:QC_indicator = 1b ;
    LATITUDE:QC_procedure = 1b ;
    LATITUDE:uncertainty = " " ;
    LATITUDE:comment = " " ;
    LATITUDE:axis = "Y" ;
    LATITUDE:reference = "WGS84" ;
    LATITUDE:coordinate_reference_frame = "urn:ogc:crs:EPSG::4326" ;
float LONGITUDE(LONGITUDE) ;
    LONGITUDE:long_name = "Longitude of each location" ;
    LONGITUDE:standard_name = "longitude" ;
    LONGITUDE:units = "degrees_east" ;
    LONGITUDE:_FillValue = 99999.f ;
    LONGITUDE:valid_min = -180.f ;
    LONGITUDE:valid_max = 180.f ;
    LONGITUDE:QC_indicator = 1b ;
    LONGITUDE:QC_procedure = 1b ;
    LONGITUDE:uncertainty = " " ;
    LONGITUDE:comment = " " ;
    LONGITUDE:axis = "X" ;
    LONGITUDE:reference = "WGS84" ;
    LONGITUDE:coordinate_reference_frame = "urn:ogc:crs:EPSG::4326" ;
byte POSITION_QC(POSITION) ;
    POSITION_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
    POSITION_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
    POSITION_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
    POSITION_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
    POSITION_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
```

```
POSITION_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
POSITION_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
float GPS_LATITUDE(LATITUDE) ;
GPS_LATITUDE:long_name = "GPS Latitude of each location" ;
GPS_LATITUDE:standard_name = "gps_latitude" ;
GPS_LATITUDE:units = "degrees_north" ;
GPS_LATITUDE:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
GPS_LATITUDE:valid_min = -90.f ;
GPS_LATITUDE:valid_max = 90.f ;
GPS_LATITUDE:QC_indicator = 1b ;
GPS_LATITUDE:uncertainty = " " ;
GPS_LATITUDE:comment = " " ;
GPS_LATITUDE:axis = " " ;
float GPS_LONGITUDE(LONGITUDE) ;
GPS_LONGITUDE:long_name = "GPS Longitude of each location" ;
GPS_LONGITUDE:standard_name = "gps_longitude" ;
GPS_LONGITUDE:units = "degrees_east" ;
GPS_LONGITUDE:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
GPS_LONGITUDE:valid_min = -180.f ;
GPS_LONGITUDE:valid_max = 180.f ;
GPS_LONGITUDE:QC_indicator = 1b ;
GPS_LONGITUDE:uncertainty = " " ;
GPS_LONGITUDE:comment = " " ;
GPS_LONGITUDE:axis = " " ;
byte GPS_POSITION_QC(POSITION) ;
GPS_POSITION_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
GPS_POSITION_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
GPS_POSITION_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
GPS_POSITION_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
GPS_POSITION_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
GPS_POSITION_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
GPS_POSITION_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data
probably_good_data bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used
nominal_value interpolated_value missing_value" ;
float DEPH(TIME, DEPTH) ;
```

```
DEPH:long_name = "Depth of each measurement" ;
DEPH:standard_name = "depth" ;
DEPH:units = "meter" ;
DEPH:_FillValue = -99999.f ;
DEPH:axis = "Z" ;
DEPH:positive = "down" ;
DEPH:QC_procedure = 1b ;
DEPH:valid_min = 0.f ;
DEPH:valid_max = 12000.f ;
DEPH:comment = "" ;
DEPH:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
DEPH:sensor_mount = "" ;
DEPH:sensor_orientation = "" ;
DEPH:ancillary_variables = "DEPH_QC" ;
DEPH:uncertainty = 0.f ;
DEPH:accuracy = 0.f ;
DEPH:precision = 0.f ;
DEPH:resolution = 0.f ;
DEPH:cell_methods = "" ;
DEPH:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte DEPH_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    DEPH_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
    DEPH_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
    DEPH_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
    DEPH_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
    DEPH_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
    DEPH_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
    DEPH_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char DEPH_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    DEPH_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
    DEPH_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
    DEPH_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
    DEPH_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
    DEPH_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float TEMP(TIME, DEPTH) ;
```

```
TEMP:long_name = "sea temperature" ;
TEMP:standard_name = "sea_water_temperature" ;
TEMP:units = "degree_Celsius" ;
TEMP:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
TEMP:QC_procedure = 1b ;
TEMP:valid_min = -2.f ;
TEMP:valid_max = 40.f ;
TEMP:comment = "" ;
TEMP:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
TEMP:sensor_mount = "" ;
TEMP:sensor_orientation = "" ;
TEMP:ancillary_variables = "TEMP_QC" ;
TEMP:uncertainty = 0.01f ;
TEMP:accuracy = 0.f ;
TEMP:precision = 0.f ;
TEMP:resolution = 0.001f ;
TEMP:cell_methods = "" ;
TEMP:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte TEMP_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    TEMP_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
    TEMP_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
    TEMP_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
    TEMP_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
    TEMP_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
    TEMP_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
    TEMP_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char TEMP_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    TEMP_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
    TEMP_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
    TEMP_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
    TEMP_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
    TEMP_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float PSAL(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    PSAL:long_name = "practical salinity" ;
    PSAL:standard_name = "sea_water_salinity" ;
```

```
PSAL:units = "psu" ;
PSAL:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
PSAL:QC_procedure = 1b ;
PSAL:valid_min = 0.f ;
PSAL:valid_max = 42.f ;
PSAL:comment = "" ;
PSAL:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
PSAL:sensor_mount = "" ;
PSAL:sensor_orientation = "" ;
PSAL:ancillary_variables = "PSAL_QC" ;
PSAL:uncertainty = 0.f ;
PSAL:accuracy = 0.f ;
PSAL:precision = 0.f ;
PSAL:resolution = 0.f ;
PSAL:cell_methods = "" ;
PSAL:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte PSAL_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    PSAL_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
    PSAL_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
    PSAL_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
    PSAL_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
    PSAL_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
    PSAL_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
    PSAL_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char PSAL_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    PSAL_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
    PSAL_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
    PSAL_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
    PSAL_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
    PSAL_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float HCSP(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    HCSP:long_name = "horizontal current speed" ;
    HCSP:standard_name = "sea_water_speed" ;
    HCSP:units = "meter/second" ;
    HCSP:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
```

```
HCSP:QC_procedure = 1b ;
HCSP:valid_min = 0.f ;
HCSP:valid_max = 60.f ;
HCSP:comment = "" ;
HCSP:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
HCSP:sensor_mount = "" ;
HCSP:sensor_orientation = "" ;
HCSP:ancillary_variables = "HCSP_QC" ;
HCSP:uncertainty = 0.f ;
HCSP:accuracy = 0.f ;
HCSP:precision = 0.f ;
HCSP:resolution = 0.f ;
HCSP:cell_methods = "" ;
HCSP:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte HCSP_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    HCSP_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
    HCSP_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
    HCSP_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
    HCSP_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
    HCSP_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
    HCSP_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
    HCSP_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char HCSP_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    HCSP_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
    HCSP_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
    HCSP_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
    HCSP_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
    HCSP_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float HCDT(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    HCDT:long_name = "current to direction relative true north" ;
    HCDT:standard_name = "direction_of_sea_water_velocity" ;
    HCDT:units = "degree" ;
    HCDT:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
    HCDT:QC_procedure = 1b ;
    HCDT:valid_min = 0.f ;
```

```
HCDT:valid_max = 360.f ;
HCDT:comment = "" ;
HCDT:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
HCDT:sensor_mount = "" ;
HCDT:sensor_orientation = "" ;
HCDT:ancillary_variables = "HCDT_QC" ;
HCDT:uncertainty = 0.f ;
HCDT:accuracy = 0.f ;
HCDT:precision = 0.f ;
HCDT:resolution = 0.f ;
HCDT:cell_methods = "" ;
HCDT:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte HCDT_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
  HCDT_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
  HCDT_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
  HCDT_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
  HCDT_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
  HCDT_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
  HCDT_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
  HCDT_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char HCDT_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
  HCDT_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
  HCDT_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
  HCDT_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
  HCDT_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
  HCDT_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float ATMS(TIME, DEPTH) ;
  ATMS:long_name = "atmospheric pressure at sea level" ;
  ATMS:standard_name = "air_pressure_at_sea_level" ;
  ATMS:units = "hectopascal" ;
  ATMS:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
  ATMS:QC_procedure = 1b ;
  ATMS:valid_min = 900.f ;
  ATMS:valid_max = 1040.f ;
  ATMS:comment = "" ;
```

```
ATMS:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
ATMS:sensor_mount = "" ;
ATMS:sensor_orientation = "" ;
ATMS:ancillary_variables = "ATMS_QC" ;
ATMS:uncertainty = 0.f ;
ATMS:accuracy = 0.f ;
ATMS:precision = 0.f ;
ATMS:resolution = 0.f ;
ATMS:cell_methods = "" ;
ATMS:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte ATMS_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
  ATMS_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
  ATMS_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
  ATMS_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
  ATMS_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
  ATMS_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
  ATMS_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
  ATMS_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char ATMS_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
  ATMS_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
  ATMS_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
  ATMS_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
  ATMS_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
  ATMS_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float DRYT(TIME, DEPTH) ;
  DRYT:long_name = "air temperature in dry bulb" ;
  DRYT:standard_name = "air_temperature" ;
  DRYT:units = "degree_Celsius" ;
  DRYT:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
  DRYT:QC_procedure = 1b ;
  DRYT:valid_min = -5.f ;
  DRYT:valid_max = 50.f ;
  DRYT:comment = "" ;
  DRYT:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
  DRYT:sensor_mount = "" ;
```

```
DRYT:sensor_orientation = "" ;
DRYT:ancillary_variables = "DRYT_QC" ;
DRYT:uncertainty = 0.f ;
DRYT:accuracy = 0.f ;
DRYT:precision = 0.f ;
DRYT:resolution = 0.f ;
DRYT:cell_methods = "" ;
DRYT:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte DRYT_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
  DRYT_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
  DRYT_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
  DRYT_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
  DRYT_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
  DRYT_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
  DRYT_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
  DRYT_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char DRYT_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
  DRYT_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
  DRYT_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
  DRYT_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
  DRYT_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
  DRYT_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float WSPD(TIME, DEPTH) ;
  WSPD:long_name = "horizontal wind speed" ;
  WSPD:standard_name = "wind_speed" ;
  WSPD:units = "meter/second" ;
  WSPD:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
  WSPD:QC_procedure = 1b ;
  WSPD:valid_min = -5.f ;
  WSPD:valid_max = 50.f ;
  WSPD:comment = "" ;
  WSPD:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
  WSPD:sensor_mount = "" ;
  WSPD:sensor_orientation = "" ;
  WSPD:ancillary_variables = "WSPD_QC" ;
```

```
WSPD:uncertainty = 0.f ;
WSPD:accuracy = 0.f ;
WSPD:precision = 0.f ;
WSPD:resolution = 0.f ;
WSPD:cell_methods = "" ;
WSPD:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte WSPD_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
WSPD_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
WSPD_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
WSPD_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
WSPD_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
WSPD_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
WSPD_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
WSPD_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char WSPD_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
WSPD_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
WSPD_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
WSPD_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
WSPD_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
WSPD_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float GSPD(TIME, DEPTH) ;
GSPD:long_name = "gust wind speed" ;
GSPD:standard_name = "wind_speed_of_gust" ;
GSPD:units = "meter/second" ;
GSPD:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
GSPD:QC_procedure = 1b ;
GSPD:valid_min = 0.f ;
GSPD:valid_max = 50.f ;
GSPD:comment = "" ;
GSPD:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
GSPD:sensor_mount = "" ;
GSPD:sensor_orientation = "" ;
GSPD:ancillary_variables = "GSPD_QC" ;
GSPD:uncertainty = 0.f ;
GSPD:accuracy = 0.f ;
```

```
GSPD:precision = 0.f ;
GSPD:resolution = 0.f ;
GSPD:cell_methods = "" ;
GSPD:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte GSPD_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
GSPD_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
GSPD_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
GSPD_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
GSPD_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
GSPD_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
GSPD_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
GSPD_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char GSPD_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
GSPD_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
GSPD_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
GSPD_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
GSPD_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
GSPD_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float WDIR(TIME, DEPTH) ;
WDIR:long_name = "wind from direction relative true north" ;
WDIR:standard_name = "wind_from_direction" ;
WDIR:units = "degree" ;
WDIR:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
WDIR:QC_procedure = 1b ;
WDIR:valid_min = 0.f ;
WDIR:valid_max = 360.f ;
WDIR:comment = "" ;
WDIR:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
WDIR:sensor_mount = "" ;
WDIR:sensor_orientation = "" ;
WDIR:ancillary_variables = "WDIR_QC" ;
WDIR:uncertainty = 0.f ;
WDIR:accuracy = 0.f ;
WDIR:precision = 0.f ;
WDIR:resolution = 0.f ;
```

```
WDIR:cell_methods = "" ;
WDIR:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte WDIR_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
WDIR_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
WDIR_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
WDIR_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
WDIR_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
WDIR_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
WDIR_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
WDIR_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char WDIR_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
WDIR_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
WDIR_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
WDIR_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
WDIR_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
WDIR_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float VTZA(TIME, DEPTH) ;
VTZA:long_name = "aver zero crossing wave period" ;
VTZA:standard_name = "sea_surface_wave_zero_upcrossing_period" ;
VTZA:units = "second" ;
VTZA:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
VTZA:QC_procedure = 1b ;
VTZA:valid_min = 0.f ;
VTZA:valid_max = 20.f ;
VTZA:comment = "" ;
VTZA:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
VTZA:sensor_mount = "" ;
VTZA:sensor_orientation = "" ;
VTZA:ancillary_variables = "VTZA_QC" ;
VTZA:uncertainty = 0.f ;
VTZA:accuracy = 0.f ;
VTZA:precision = 0.f ;
VTZA:resolution = 0.f ;
VTZA:cell_methods = "" ;
VTZA:DM_indicator = "R" ;
```

```
byte VTZA_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    VTZA_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
    VTZA_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
    VTZA_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
    VTZA_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
    VTZA_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
    VTZA_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
    VTZA_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char VTZA_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    VTZA_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
    VTZA_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
    VTZA_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
    VTZA_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
    VTZA_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float VTPK(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    VTPK:long_name = "wave spectrum peak period" ;
    VTPK:standard_name = "" ;
    VTPK:units = "second" ;
    VTPK:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
    VTPK:QC_procedure = 1b ;
    VTPK:valid_min = 0.f ;
    VTPK:valid_max = 20.f ;
    VTPK:comment = "" ;
    VTPK:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
    VTPK:sensor_mount = "" ;
    VTPK:sensor_orientation = "" ;
    VTPK:ancillary_variables = "VTPK_QC" ;
    VTPK:uncertainty = 0.f ;
    VTPK:accuracy = 0.f ;
    VTPK:precision = 0.f ;
    VTPK:resolution = 0.f ;
    VTPK:cell_methods = "" ;
    VTPK:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte VTPK_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    VTPK_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
```

```
VTPK_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
VTPK_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
VTPK_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
VTPK_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
VTPK_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
VTPK_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char VTPK_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
VTPK_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
VTPK_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
VTPK_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
VTPK_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
VTPK_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float VTDH(TIME, DEPTH) ;
VTDH:long_name = "significant wave height" ;
VTDH:standard_name = "sea_surface_wave_significant_height" ;
VTDH:units = "meter" ;
VTDH:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
VTDH:QC_procedure = 1b ;
VTDH:valid_min = 0.f ;
VTDH:valid_max = 8.f ;
VTDH:comment = "" ;
VTDH:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
VTDH:sensor_mount = "" ;
VTDH:sensor_orientation = "" ;
VTDH:ancillary_variables = "VTDH_QC" ;
VTDH:uncertainty = 0.f ;
VTDH:accuracy = 0.f ;
VTDH:precision = 0.f ;
VTDH:resolution = 0.f ;
VTDH:cell_methods = "" ;
VTDH:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte VTDH_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
VTDH_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
VTDH_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
VTDH_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
```

```
VTDH_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
VTDH_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
VTDH_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
VTDH_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
char VTDH_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
VTDH_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
VTDH_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
VTDH_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
VTDH_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
VTDH_DM:_FillValue = " " ;
float VDIR(TIME, DEPTH) ;
VDIR:long_name = "wave direction rel. true north" ;
VDIR:standard_name = "sea_surface_wave_from_direction" ;
VDIR:units = "degree" ;
VDIR:_FillValue = -9999.99f ;
VDIR:QC_procedure = 1b ;
VDIR:valid_min = 0.f ;
VDIR:valid_max = 360.f ;
VDIR:comment = "" ;
VDIR:sensor_depth = 0.f ;
VDIR:sensor_mount = "" ;
VDIR:sensor_orientation = "" ;
VDIR:ancillary_variables = "VDIR_QC" ;
VDIR:uncertainty = 0.f ;
VDIR:accuracy = 0.f ;
VDIR:precision = 0.f ;
VDIR:resolution = 0.f ;
VDIR:cell_methods = "" ;
VDIR:DM_indicator = "R" ;
byte VDIR_QC(TIME, DEPTH) ;
VDIR_QC:long_name = "quality flag" ;
VDIR_QC:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 2" ;
VDIR_QC:_FillValue = -128b ;
VDIR_QC:valid_min = 0b ;
VDIR_QC:valid_max = 9b ;
```

```
    VDIR_QC:flag_values = 0b, 1b, 2b, 3b, 4b, 5b, 6b, 7b, 8b, 9b ;
    VDIR_QC:flag_meanings = "no_qc_performed good_data probably_good_data
bad_data_that_are_potentially_correctable bad_data value_changed not_used nominal_value
interpolated_value missing_value" ;
    char VDIR_DM(TIME, DEPTH) ;
    VDIR_DM:long_name = "method of data processing" ;
    VDIR_DM:conventions = "OceanSITES reference table 5" ;
    VDIR_DM:flag_values = "R, P, D, M" ;
    VDIR_DM:flag_meanings = "realtime post-recovery delayed-mode mixed" ;
    VDIR_DM:_FillValue = " " ;

// global attributes:
    :data_type = "OceanSITES time-series data" ;
    :format_version = "1.2" ;
    :platform_code = "SARON" ;
    :institution = "HELLENIC CENTER FOR MARINE RESEARCH (HCMR)" ;
    :institution_edmo_code = "164" ;
    :date_update = "2017-01-26T01:15:04Z" ;
    :site_code = "SARON" ;
    :wmo_platform_code = "6101001" ;
    :source = "BUOY/MOORING: SURFACE, MOORED: observation" ;
    :history = "2017-01-26T01:15:04Z : Creation" ;
    :data_mode = "R" ;
    :quality_control_indicator = "6" ;
    :quality_index = "A" ;
    :references = "http://www.oceansites.org, http://www.poseidon.hcmr.gr" ;
    :comment = " " ;
    :conventions = "OceanSITES Manual 1.2, InSituTac-Specification-Document" ;
    :netcdf_version = "3.5" ;
    :title = "Med Sea - NRT in situ Observations" ;
    :summary = " " ;
    :naming_authority = "OceanSITES" ;
    :id = "MO_LATEST_TS_MO_SARON_20170125" ;
    :cdm_data_type = "Time-series" ;
    :area = "Mediterranean" ;
    :geospatial_lat_min = "37.5968" ;
    :geospatial_lat_max = "37.5968" ;
```

```

:geospatial_lon_min = "23.5615" ;
:geospatial_lon_max = "23.5615" ;
:geospatial_vertical_min = "0.0" ;
:geospatial_vertical_max = "3.0" ;
:time_coverage_start = "2017-01-25T00:00:00Z" ;
:time_coverage_end = "2017-01-25T21:00:00Z" ;
:institution_references = "http://www.hcmr.gr" ;
:contact = "achalk@hcmr.gr, cmems-service@hcmr.gr" ;
:author = "Antonis Chalkiopoulos" ;
:data_assembly_center = "HCMR" ;
:pi_name = "Leonidas Perivoliotis" ;
:distribution_statement = "These data follow Copernicus standards; they are public and
free of charge. User assumes all risk for use of data. User must display citation in any publication or
product using data. User must
contact PI prior to any commercial use of data." ;
:citation = "These data were collected and made freely available by the Copernicus
project and the programs that contribute to it" ;
:update_interval = "daily" ;
:qc_manual = "OceanSITES User\'s Manual v1.2" ;

```

CMEMS Insitu products - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	All the sensors used for the data collection are routinely being calibrated
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	The data collection and analysis procedures described in the CMEMS (Copernicus Service) and EuroGOOS documentation
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Data are transmitted through telecommunication protocols in Near real Time (few hours maximum after being collected)
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not applicable to this data set
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.7. Data Source #7 (DS_#7)

HCMR forecasting products - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	POSEIDON System Forecasting product - Weather, sea-state, sailing, sea-level and ocean forecasts
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	IMOS - AN

<p>General description of dataset</p> <p><i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i></p>	<p>http://poseidon.hcmr.gr/listview_gr.php?id=114</p>
<p>Temporal and Spatial coverage</p> <p><i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i></p>	<p>Temporal coverage: 5 days forecast (daily provision), Archive data: 1year</p> <p>Spatial coverage: Ionian, Aegean and Cretan Seas, Mediterranean Sea</p>
<p>Status / Maintenance</p> <p><i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i></p>	<p>onGoing: data is continually being updated</p>
Provider	
<p>Data provider</p> <p><i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i></p>	<p>Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR)</p>
<p>Data provider URI</p>	<p>http://poseidon.hcmr.gr/listview.php?id=17</p>
<p>Data Owner</p> <p><i>Provide the ownership of the dataset along with any contact information</i></p>	<p>Hellenic Center for Marine Research (HCMR)</p> <p>Address: 46.7km Athens Sounio Ave.</p> <p>City: Anabyssos</p> <p>Administrative area: Attiki</p> <p>Postal code: 19013</p> <p>Country: Greece</p> <p>Electronic mail address: lperiv@hcmr.gr</p>
<p>Data administrator</p> <p><i>Provide this information only if different from above</i></p>	<p>The data administrator is the same as the data owner.</p>
<p>Permission status</p> <p><i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i></p>	<p>Accessible at: http://poseidon.hcmr.gr/listview.php?id=17</p> <p>License: Citation is required to be displayed in any publication or product using POSEIDON data.</p>
Partner	
<p>Pilot case</p>	<p>Dataset is from Pilot 2</p>

<i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	Could be possibly used also in Pilots 1 and 3
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
Used by the Oil Spill Model for the production of the oil spill dispersion forecast.	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	available in NetCDF
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	These data were produced with the use of the ocean hydrodynamic and the ecosystem models of the POSEIDON system. More details can be found in http://poseidon.hcmr.gr/listview.php?id=16
Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	CF conventions
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	NetCDF CF Standard Name Table (http://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-standard-names/57/build/cf-standard-name-table.html)
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give</i>	Current size: 150 GB, Annual Archive estimated size: 1,9 TB Increasing daily by: 5GB

<i>information about this increase</i>	
<p>Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation</p> <p><i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised?</i></p> <p><i>If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i></p>	No fields are set under access control, no data has to be anonymised.
<p>Data collection frequency</p> <p><i>State how often the data is collected</i></p>	data update is done on daily basis
Raw data sample (or complete raw data if possible)	
<p><i>Provide data sample as a separate file. If the dataset is available in different formats provide different sample files.</i></p> <p>Dataset is too big to be displayed.</p>	
Data schema and documentation	
<p><i>Provide data schema, description of data fields and other documentation related to the dataset as a separate file.</i></p>	

Data Source quality assessment:

HCMR- Forecasting products		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	The forecasting products are the results of the numerical models integration. They can deviate from the real conditions but they are systematic efforts in place (data assimilation procedures) to minimise this discrepancy.
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	The numerical models that produce the results are academic public domain models with extended and detailed documentation
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	The forecasting products are available in daily basis providing information for the next 5 days
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not applicable to this dataset
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	The numerical models used for the mare pilot case are implemented in adequate resolution to evaluate the oil spill dispersion in Aegean/Ionian and the Mediterranean Sea
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.8. Data Source #8 (DS_#8)

Natura 2000 - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	Natura 2000 data – The European network of protected sites
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	Natura2000

<p>General description of dataset</p> <p><i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i></p>	<p>https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/natura-9</p>
<p>Temporal and Spatial coverage</p> <p><i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i></p>	<p>Temporal coverage: 1979 up to reported period 2017</p> <p>Spatial coverage: EU</p>
<p>Status / Maintenance</p> <p><i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i></p>	<p>Updated yearly</p>
<p>Provider</p>	
<p>Data provider</p> <p><i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i></p>	<p>European Environmental Agency (EEA)</p>
<p>Data provider URI</p>	<p>http://ec.europa.eu</p>
<p>Data Owner</p> <p><i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i></p>	<p>https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data-providers-and-partners/directorate-general-for-environment</p>
<p>Data administrator</p> <p><i>Provide this information only if different from above</i></p>	
<p>Permission status</p> <p><i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i></p>	<p>EEA standard re-use policy: unless otherwise indicated, re-use of content on the EEA website for commercial or non-commercial purposes is permitted free of charge, provided that the source is acknowledged (https://www.eea.europa.eu/legal/copyright). Copyright holder: Directorate-General for Environment (DG ENV).</p>

Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	Dataset is from Pilot 2 Could be probably reused in Pilot 4
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
Develop alerting system on danger of the Natura2000 regions from nearby oil spill dispersion	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	Shapefile, Spatial lite, INSPIRE compliant metadata set
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English, EU
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/natura-9#tab-metadata
Standard	N/A

<i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	N/A
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	~2.5GB
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/natura-9#tab-additional-information
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	yearly
Raw data sample (or complete raw data if possible)	
<i>Provide data sample as a separate file. If the dataset is available in different formats provide different sample files.</i>	
Data schema and documentation	
<i>Provide data schema, description of data fields and other documentation related to the dataset as a separate file.</i>	
https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/natura-9#tab-additional-information https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/natura-9#tab-metadata	

Natura 2000 - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	The EEA is depending on the regional partners to provide the data and remove any inconsistencies detected
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not applicable for this data set
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A it is reported at most yearly
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Not applicable
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.9. Data Source #9 (DS_#9)

Vessel tracking - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	Vessel Tracking Data collected from the Automatic Identification System (AIS)
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	MarineTraffic (Exmile)-AIS
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	The dataset includes the positional data of vessels that have been received by the MarineTraffic(Exmile) private AIS receivers network during the 2011-2018 period. This data collection contains dynamic information such as time-series observations of latitude, longitude, course over ground, speed over ground as well as a set of static information such as vessel's identification information (e.g., IMO, MMSI, etc.) that are periodically transmitted from vessels.
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Temporal coverage: 2011-2018 Spatial coverage: National
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Dataset includes vessels' positions during the 2011-2018 period. It can be used as streaming/live data
Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	MarineTraffic (Exmile)
Data provider URI	www.marinetraffic.com
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	EXMILE City: London, UK Country: United Kingdom Electronic mail address: research@marinetraffic.com
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	The data administrator is the same as the data owner.

<p>Permission status</p> <p><i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i></p>	<p>Accessible at https://www.marinetraffic.com</p> <p>License: Data and Services are available to subscribed users through various product plans</p>
Partner	
<p>Pilot case</p> <p><i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i></p>	<p>Dataset is from Pilot 3</p> <p>Could be probably reused in Pilots 1, 2 and 4</p>
<p>Possible scenario coverage</p> <p><i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i></p>	
<p>AIS data are collected through the Automatic Identification System (AIS) which was developed primarily as a tool for maritime safety and vessel collision avoidance and is an integral component of various Vessel Traffic Services (VTS), Vessel Traffic Management Systems (VTMS) and Vessel Traffic Monitoring & Information Systems (VTMIS). This kind of data when collected on a global scale (a solution offered by EXMILE through the MarineTraffic platform) open possibilities of advancing maritime security far beyond simple collision prevention. In pilot III the data will be used in conjunction with other datasets to support situation assessment process and identify anomalies in vessels' routes.</p> <p>Furthermore, this kind of data may be used for polluter identification in the oil spill pilot case (i.e., Pilot Case II).</p>	
Details	
<p>Data format(s)</p> <p><i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i></p>	<p>available in CSV</p>
<p>Data language</p> <p><i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i></p>	<p>English</p>
<p>Assumptions</p> <p><i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i></p>	<p>The AIS data is collected from MarineTraffic platform operated by EXMILE. The platform is based on private receivers' network, comprising of over 2,000 coastal AIS stations around the globe, the world's largest proprietary AIS network. At any given time, MarineTraffic is tracking over 100,000 vessels at realtime with 130,000 vessels reporting daily. With its Big Data infrastructure, EXMILE processes the data received through MarineTraffic platform to extract knowledge and offer business intelligence solutions to the maritime industry.</p>

Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	Character set used is UTF-8 (8-bit variable size UCS Transfer Format, based on ISO/IEC 10646)
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	The data are relying on the semantics/vocabulary as defined in ITU M1371-4 specification
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	~50GB (approximately 1 billion records) per year
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	The dataset is available through product plans for the subscribed users of MarineTraffic platform. Data already anonymised
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	Data are continuously collected through the AIS private network.
Raw data sample	
SHIP_ID,STATUS,STATUS_NAME,SPEED,LON,LAT,COURSE,HEADING,TIMESTAMP,LENGTH,WIDTH,FLAG_CODE,SHIPTYPE,TYPE_NAME 443351,15,Default,0,-58.34315,-34.62647,65,511,06-05-11 0:00,30,8,0,52,Tug 112529,15,Default,0,8.423387,55.47182,198,511,06-05-11 0:00,0,0,219,10,Reserved 620056,15,Default,1,5.65851,51.96186,320,511,06-05-11 0:00,31,5,230,99,Other 598505,98,Aid to Navigation,0,-3.508397,53.48074,0,0,06-05-11 0:00,10,10,232,103,OffShore Structure 59826,14,Nav Aid - SART - MOB,0,27.17805,40.68861,0,0,06-05-11 0:00,NULL,NULL,271,130,Manned VTS 1039551,15,Default,0,-122.4541,45.59897,211,511,06-05-11 0:00,38,7,101,73,Cargo - Hazard C (Minor) 634335,99,Class B,57,120.3334,26.99601,46,511,06-05-11 0:00,20,4,110,30,Fishing 104047,99,Class B,40,-90.26355,38.52704,356,511,06-05-11 0:00,70,31,118,52,Tug	

9910,0,Underway using Engine,47,19.02991,47.82034,278,511,06-05-11 0:00,23,9,203,79,Cargo
 10247,0,Underway using Engine,93,15.69047,48.38525,58,511,06-05-11 0:00,23,9,203,74,Cargo -
 Hazard D (Recognizable)

Data schema and documentation

Main data fields:

data_column_name, ITU_standard_name ,unit_name,unit_short_name

#SHIP_ID, --

#STATUS, Navigational Status, Integer, Int

#STATUS_NAME, Navigational Status Description, ASCII characters, char

#SPEED, speed over ground, knots (equals speed/10)

#LON, longitude,Longitude east,Degrees,deg,

LAT,latitude,Latitude north,Degrees,deg,

#COURSE, course over ground, Degrees,deg,

#HEADING, true heading, Degrees, deg

Vessel tracking - data source quality assessment:

Vessel Tracking Data		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.10. Data Source #10 (DS_#10)

Port location - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	World Port Index
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	World Port Index (Pub 150)
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	The World Port Index (Pub 150) contains the location and physical characteristics of, and the facilities and services offered by major ports and terminals world-wide (approximately 3700 entries), in a tabular format. Entries are organised geographically, in accordance with the diagrams located in the front of the publication.
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial</i>	Temporal coverage: 2017 Spatial coverage: Global

<i>information provide which period or area it covers</i>	
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Dataset is updated regularly

Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	National Geospatial Intelligence Agency (NGIA)
Data provider URI	https://www.nga.mil/Pages/Default.aspx
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	United States government Country: United States of America
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	The data administrator is the same as the data provider.
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	License: No copyright claimed. The data are public and accessible at https://msi.nga.mil/NGAPortal/MSI.portal?nfpb=true&pageLabel=msi_portal_page_62&pubCode=0015
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	Dataset is related to Pilot 3 Could be probably reused in all the other Pilots
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
This dataset gives the location, characteristics, known facilities, and available services of a many ports and shipping facilities and oil terminals throughout the world. The selection of these places is based on criteria established by the NGIA and not random choices. The applicable chart and Sailing Directions is given for each	

<p>place listed. Thus, this dataset is related to all the pilot cases of BDO, as it includes knowledge related to port locations and activities.</p>	
Details	
<p>Data format(s)</p> <p><i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i></p>	<p>available in MSAccess DB and Shape file</p>
<p>Data language</p> <p><i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i></p>	<p>English</p>
<p>Assumptions</p> <p><i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i></p>	<p>--</p>
<p>Standard</p> <p><i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i></p>	<p>--</p>
<p>Ontologies / Vocabularies used</p> <p><i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i></p>	<p>--</p>
<p>Data Size</p> <p><i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i></p>	<p>~20MB (approximately 3700 records)</p>
<p>Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation</p> <p><i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised?</i></p> <p><i>If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i></p>	<p>The dataset is available online. Anonymisation is not needed</p>

<p>Data collection frequency</p> <p><i>State how often the data is collected</i></p>	<p>Data collection is done by the National Geospatial Intelligence Agency.</p>
<p>Raw data sample</p>	
<p>World_port_index_number,Region_index,Main_port_name,Wpi_country_code,Latitude_degrees,Lati tude_minutes,Latitude_hemisphere,Longitude_degrees,Longitude_minutes,Longitude_hemisphere,P ublication,Chart,Harbor_size_code,Harbor_type_code,Shelter_afforded_code,Entrance_restriction_ti de,Entrance_restriction_swell,Entrance_restriction_ice,Entrance_restriction_other,Overhead_limits,C hannel_depth,Anchorage_depth,Cargo_pier_depth,Oil_terminal_depth,Tide,Maxsize_vessel_code,G ood_holding_ground,Turning_area,First_port_of_entry,Us_representative,Eta_message,Pilotage_co mpulsory,Pilotage_available,Pilotage_local_assist,Pilotage_advisable,Tugs_salvage,Tugs_assist,Quar antine_pratique,Quarantine_deratt_cert,Quarantine_other,Communications_telephone,Communicati ons_telegraph,Communications_radio,Communications_radio_tel,Communications_air,Communicati ons_rail,Load_offload_wharves,Load_offload_anchor,Load_offload_med_moor,Load_offload_beach _moor,Load_offload_ice_moor,Medical_facilities,Garbage_disposal,Degauss,Dirty_ballast,Cranes_fix ed,Cranes_mobile,Cranes_floating,Lifts_100_tons_plus,Lifts_50_100_tons,Lifts_25_49_tons,Lifts_0 _24_tons,Services_longshore,Services_elect,Services_steam,Services_navig_equip,Services_elect_re pair,Supplies_provisions,Supplies_water,Supplies_fuel_oil,Supplies_diesel_oil,Supplies_deck,Supplie s_engine,Repair_code,Drydock,Railway</p> <p>760,545,AASIAAT,GL,68,42,N,52,52,W,181,38482,S,CN,G,N,N,Y,Y,,A,A,L,,3,M,N,,N,N,Y,N,Y,Y,Y,N,N ,,,,,Y,,Y,,Y,,,,,Y,N,,N,,Y,,,,,Y,,,,,Y,Y,Y,,,,C,,S</p> <p>48430,48410,ABADAN,IR,30,20,N,48,17,E,172,62438,M,RN,G,Y,N,N,Y,,K,K,K,,1,M,,Y,Y,N,Y,Y,Y,,Y,N ,Y,Y,Y,,Y,Y,Y,,Y,,Y,,,,,Y,,,N,,Y,Y,Y,,Y,Y,,,,,Y,Y,Y,,,C,S,S</p> <p>61120,61100,ABASHIRI KO,JP,44,1,N,144,17,E,158,96906,S,CB,G,,Y,Y,Y,Y,M,G,J,,2,M,,,Y,Y,Y,N,Y,,,,,Y,Y,,,Y,Y,Y,,Y,Y,Y,,,,Y, ,,,,,N,,,,,Y,,,,,Y,,Y,,,C,,</p> <p>30100,30020,ABENRA,DK,55,3,N,9,26,E,194,44062,S,CB,G,Y,N,,Y,,J,A,M,K,2,L,Y,Y,N,Y,Y,Y,Y,,,Y,, Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,,Y,,,,,Y,Y,,Y,,Y,,,,,Y,Y,,,,,Y,Y,Y,Y,,,A,,S</p> <p>17060,16000,ABERDEEN,US,46,59,N,123,49,W,CP07,18502,S,RN,E,N,N,N,Y,Y,L,,K,L,8,,,,Y,,,Y,,,Y,,, Y,,,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,,,,,Y,Y,,,Y,Y,,,Y,,Y,N,N,N,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,C,,M</p> <p>32220,31870,ABERDEEN,GB,57,9,N,2,5,W,141,35013,M,RB,G,Y,N,N,,Y,N,K,K,M,4,L,Y,,Y,N,Y,Y,Y,,Y,, Y,Y,Y,,Y,Y,,Y,Y,Y,,,,,Y,Y,,Y,Y,,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,C,S,</p> <p>46000,45960,ABIDJAN,CI,5,15,N,4,1,W,123,57064,L,LC,E,Y,Y,N,Y,Y,H,A,H,K,1,L,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,,Y,N, Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,,,,,Y,Y,,N,Y,,Y,Y,,Y,Y,N,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,B,S,</p> <p>45350,45200,ABU KHAMMASH,LY,33,4,N,11,49,E,132,52160,V,CN,N,,,,,L,,,L,0,,,Y,,,Y,,,,,,Y,Y,,Y,,,,,,N,,,,,,Y, ,,,,,</p>	

48278,48260,ABU ZABY,AE,24,30,N,54,20,E,172,62463,M,CB,G,Y,N,N,Y,,G,C,H,H,2,L,,Y,Y,N,Y,Y,Y,,Y,,Y,Y,,Y,,N,Y,Y,Y,Y ,Y,Y,,,,Y,Y,,Y,,Y,,Y,Y,Y,Y,,,,Y,Y,Y,N,Y,B,M,
Data schema and documentation
<i>Main data fields:</i> In the data listing for each port, the letter "Y" indicates Yes and "N" indicates No; where there is a blank, no information is available. By tabulation and codification, specific information for each port is confined to a single line. The data is listed under the column headings given above. Detailed analysis of each column is given at pages 6-9 of the specification: https://msi.nga.mil/MSISiteContent/StaticFiles/NAV_PUBS/WPI/Pub150bk.pdf

Port location - data source quality assessment:

Port Location		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	The dataset provides GPS location of the centres of ports. However, in order to produce port calls, this is transformed into geometries (e.g. bounding boxes)

2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.11. Data Source #11 (DS_#11)

Nautical information maps – data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	OpenSeaMap
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	OSM
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	OpenSeaMap was created in 2009 in response to a great need for freely-accessible seafaring maps. Its goal is to add nautical and tourism information that would interest sailors into OSM and to present this in a pleasing and usable way. This includes beacons, buoys and other seamarks, port information, repair shops, ship supplies and much more, but also shops, restaurants and places of interest. OpenSeaMap is part of OpenStreetMap and uses its database.
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Spatial coverage: Global Temporal: N/A
Status / Maintenance	The dataset is updated/maintained regularly

<i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	
Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	OpenStreetMap Foundation
Data provider URI	https://wiki.osmfoundation.org/wiki/Main_Page
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	OpenStreetMap Foundation
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	The data administrator is the same as the data owner
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	The data is publicly available and can be used under the Open Database License (ODbL)
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	Can be used for all the pilots.
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
The OpenSeaMap provides free maps with nautical information and can be used in any visualisation of the pilots that would demonstrate vessels' positions or routes on a map.	
Details	
Data format(s)	Png tiles

<i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	N/A
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	
Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	IHO-S-57 published by International Hydrographic Organisation.
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	N/A
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	420 GB of tiles with different zoom level
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	The data can be freely served in any website through the OpenSeetMap Tile Server: http://t1.openseamap.org/seamark/ http://tiles.openseamap.org/seamark/
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	N/A
Raw data sample	
N/A	
Data schema and documentation	

Main data fields:

N/A

Nautical information maps - data source quality assessment:

Nautical Information Maps		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				

1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.12. Data Source #12 (DS_#12)

Vessels' inspection reports - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	Title: Vessels Detentions and Inspections
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	Paris MoU on Port State Control – Detention List
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	This dataset includes the detention information of vessels
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Spatial coverage: Global Temporal coverage: 2009- 2018 (published per month)
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	New dataset with detentions is produced every month

Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	Paris MoU on Port State Control (agreement signed by 27 Maritime Authorities)

Data provider URI	https://www.parismou.org/
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	The maritime authorities that have signed the Paris MoU agreement
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	The data administrator is the same as the data provider.
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	The dataset is public but no part of the information contained in the Paris MoU site may be stored in a retrieval system, or transmitted in any form, or by any means without prior authorisation in writing from the owners of the data.
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	Pilot 3
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	This dataset will be combined with vessel's static information such as vessel's flag, ship's owner, vessel's name, IMO and MMSI and with vessel's dynamic information such as destination reported, speed/course changes, proximity to other vessels etc. and create risk profile indicator for the vessel.
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	Excel spreadsheets
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	--
Standard	--

<i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	--
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	~ 10 MB
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	The dataset is available online. Anonymisation is not needed
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	Data collection is done by Maritime Authorities that have signed the Paris MoU
Raw data sample	
N/A	
Data schema and documentation	
<i>Main data fields:</i>	
N/A	

Vessels' inspection reports - Data Source quality assessment:

Vessels' Inspection Reports		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	N/A
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.13. Data Source #13 (DS_#13)

MARETEC WW3 Portugal model - data source description:

Overview

Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	PORTUGAL_0.05DEG_1L_1H
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	-
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	Numerical Model WaveWatch3 (WW3) instantiated for the Portuguese coast. Provides wave characteristics (wave significant height, wave average period, wave mean direction).
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Spatial coverage: Long: -12.6° to -5.5°; Lat: 34.4° to 45.0° (grid of 0.05°) Temporal coverage: from 2012-06-05 to present
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Dataset is maintained and updates regularly. It can be used as streaming/live data.

Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	MARETEC/IST
Data provider URI	http://www.maretec.org/en/
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	MARETEC/IST
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	
Permission status	Public dataset: data provider only requires acknowledgement.

<i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4.
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
Data being used in test case: P4SC1_1 in the BDO platform	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	NetCDF (CSV available for locations that also correspond to buoys locations in the Portuguese coast)
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	
Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	CF1.0
Data Size	7.679 Mbytes/day

<i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	Data does not have any particular needs regarding permissions or anonymisation.
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	Data can be collected in real-time.

MARETEC WW3 Portugal model - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.14. Data Source #14 (DS_#14)

Copernicus Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish- ocean wave analysis and forecast - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	ATLANTIC-IBERIAN BISCAY IRISH- OCEAN WAVE ANALYSIS AND FORECAST
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	IBI_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_WAV_005_005
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	Provides short-term (5-days) high-resolution wave forecast product for the IBI (Iberian Biscay Irish) area. The wave model system is daily run by Puertos del Estado and it is based on a numerical model runned by Meteo-France (MFWAM model). It runs on a grid of 10 km of horizontal resolution and forced with the ECMWMF wind data.
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Spatial coverage: Long: -19° to 5°; Lat: 26° to 56° (grid of 0.1°) Temporal coverage: from 2015-01-01T00:00:00Z to Present

<p>Status / Maintenance</p> <p><i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i></p>	<p>Dataset is maintained and updates regularly. It can be used as streaming/live data.</p>
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Provider	
<p>Data provider</p> <p><i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i></p>	<p>COPERNICUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE (CMEMS)</p>
<p>Data provider URI</p>	<p>http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/access-to-products/?option=com_csw&view=details&product_id=IBI_ANALYSIS_FORECAST_WAV_005_005</p>
<p>Data Owner</p> <p><i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i></p>	<p>CMEMS</p>
<p>Data administrator</p> <p><i>Provide this information only if different from above</i></p>	<p>CMEMS</p>
<p>Permission status</p> <p><i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i></p>	<p>Public dataset</p>
Partner	
<p>Pilot case</p> <p><i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i></p>	<p>This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4.</p>
<p>Possible scenario coverage</p> <p><i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i></p>	
<p>This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4. Usage will depend on users' choices of datasets.</p>	

Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	NetCDF
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	
Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	CF1.0
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	58.803 Mbytes/day
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	Data does not have any particular needs regarding permissions or anonymisation.
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	Data can be collected in real-time.

Copernicus Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish- ocean wave analysis and forecast - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
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B.2.15. Data Source #15 (DS_#15)

Copernicus Atlantic Iberian Biscay Irish Ocean- in-situ near real time observations - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	ATLANTIC IBERIAN BISCAY IRISH OCEAN- IN-SITU NEAR REAL TIME OBSERVATIONS
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	INSITU_IBI_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_013_033
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	For the Iberia-Biscay-Ireland seas- The In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre (INS TAC) integrates near real-time in situ observation data. These data are collected from the IBI-ROOS members and complemented by the observation collected by the Global INS TAC in the area. The data are quality controlled using automated procedures. It is updated continuously and provides observations with 24-48 hours from acquisition in average.
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Spatial coverage: Long: -30° to 0.05°; Lat: 20° to 55° (several buoy locations) Temporal coverage: 2010-01-04T00:00:00Z to Present
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Dataset is maintained and updates regularly. It can be used as streaming/live data.

Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	COPERNICUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE (CMEMS)

Data provider URI	http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/access-to-products/?option=com_csw&view=details&product_id=INSITU_IBI_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_013_033
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	CMEMS
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	CMEMS
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	Public dataset
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4.
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4. Usage will depend on users' choices of datasets.	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	NetCDF
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions	

Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?	
Standard Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data	
Ontologies / Vocabularies used Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data	CF1.0
Data Size Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase	1 Mbyte/day
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?	Data does not have any particular needs regarding permissions or anonymisation.
Data collection frequency State how often the data is collected	Data can be collected in real-time.

Copernicus Atlantic Iberian Biscay Irish Ocean- in-situ near real time observations - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.16. Data Source #16 (DS_#16)

Copernicus Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish- ocean wave hindcast - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	ATLANTIC-IBERIAN BISCAY IRISH- OCEAN WAVE HINDCAST
Data source acronym	IBI_REANALYSIS_WAV_005_006

<i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	
<p>General description of dataset</p> <p><i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i></p>	The IBI MFC provides a Multi-year (24-years) high-resolution wave hindcast product for the IBI (Iberian Biscay Irish) area. The IBI MY wave model product covers the time period 1992-2016 and the model system was run by AEMET and Puertos del Estado in the IBI-MFC production machine (CESGA Finisterrae-II).
<p>Temporal and Spatial coverage</p> <p><i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i></p>	<p>Spatial coverage: Long: -19° to 5°; Lat: 26° to 56° (grid 0.1°)</p> <p>Temporal coverage: from 1992-01-01T00:00:00Z to 2016-12-31T00:00:00Z</p>
<p>Status / Maintenance</p> <p><i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i></p>	Dataset is updated annually.
Provider	
<p>Data provider</p> <p><i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i></p>	COPERNICUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE (CMEMS)
Data provider URI	http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/access-to-products/?option=com_csw&view=details&product_id=IBI_REANALYSIS_WAV_005_006
<p>Data Owner</p> <p><i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i></p>	CMEMS
<p>Data administrator</p> <p><i>Provide this information only if different from above</i></p>	CMEMS
<p>Permission status</p> <p><i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i></p>	Public dataset
Partner	

<p>Pilot case</p> <p><i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i></p>	<p>This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4.</p>
<p>Possible scenario coverage</p> <p><i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i></p>	
<p>This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4. Usage will depend on users' choices of datasets.</p>	
<p>Details</p>	
<p>Data format(s)</p> <p><i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i></p>	<p>NetCDF</p>
<p>Data language</p> <p><i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i></p>	<p>English</p>
<p>Assumptions</p> <p><i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i></p>	
<p>Standard</p> <p><i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i></p>	
<p>Ontologies / Vocabularies used</p> <p><i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i></p>	<p>CF1.0</p>
<p>Data Size</p> <p><i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i></p>	<p>58.803 Mbyte/day</p>

<p>Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation</p> <p><i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised?</i></p> <p><i>If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i></p>	Data does not have any particular needs regarding permissions or anonymisation.
<p>Data collection frequency</p> <p><i>State how often the data is collected</i></p>	According to its update.

Copernicus Atlantic-Iberian Biscay Irish- ocean wave hindcast - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.17. Data Source #17 (DS_#17)

Global ocean L3 significant wave height from nrt satellite measurements - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	GLOBAL OCEAN L3 SIGNIFICANT WAVE HEIGHT FROM NRT SATELLITE MEASUREMENTS
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	WAVE_GLO_WAV_L3_SWH_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_014_001
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	This product is processed by the WAVE-TAC multimission altimeter data processing system. It serves in near-real time the main operational oceanography and climate forecasting centers in Europe and worldwide. It processes data from the following altimeter missions: Jason-3, Sentinel-3A and SARAL/AltiKa. All the missions are homogenised with respect to a reference mission, which is currently Jason-3.
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Spatial coverage: Global (needs to be filtered for areas of interest) Temporal coverage: from 2017-07-09T00:00:00Z to Present
Status / Maintenance	Dataset is updated daily. It can be used as streaming/live data.

<i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	
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Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	COPERNICUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE (CMEMS)
Data provider URI	http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/access-to-products/?option=com_csw&view=details&product_id=WAVE_GLO_WAV_L3_SWH_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_014_001
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	CMEMS
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	CMEMS
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	Public dataset
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4.
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4. Usage will depend on users' choices of datasets.	
Details	

<p>Data format(s)</p> <p><i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i></p>	NetCDF
<p>Data language</p> <p><i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i></p>	English
<p>Assumptions</p> <p><i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i></p>	
<p>Standard</p> <p><i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i></p>	
<p>Ontologies / Vocabularies used</p> <p><i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i></p>	CF1.0
<p>Data Size</p> <p><i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i></p>	>1 Mbyte/day
<p>Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation</p> <p><i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised?</i></p> <p><i>If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i></p>	Data does not have any particular needs regarding permissions or anonymisation.
<p>Data collection frequency</p> <p><i>State how often the data is collected</i></p>	Data can be collected in real-time.

Global ocean L3 significant wave height from nrt satellite measurements - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.18. Data Source #18 (DS_#18)

Global ocean L3 spectral parameters from nrt satellite measurements - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	GLOBAL OCEAN L3 SPECTRAL PARAMETERS FROM NRT SATELLITE MEASUREMENTS
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	WAVE_GLO_WAV_L3_SPC_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_014_002
General description of dataset <i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	For the Global Ocean - Monomission satellite-based spectral integral parameters. Only valid data are included, based on a rigorous editing combining quality flags and thresholds. Included wave parameters are partition significant wave height, partition peak period and partition peak or principal direction. Those parameters are propagated in space and time at a 3-hour timestep, providing information along the swell propagation path, from source to land. One file gathers one swell system, gathering observations originating from the same storm source.
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Spatial coverage: Global (needs to be filtered for areas of interest) Temporal coverage: from 2018-03-15T00:00:00Z to Present
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Dataset is updated daily. It can be used as streaming/live data.

Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	COPERNICUS MARINE ENVIRONMENT MONITORING SERVICE (CMEMS)
Data provider URI	http://marine.copernicus.eu/services-portfolio/access-to-products/?option=com_csw&view=details&product_id=WAVE_GLO_WAV_L3_SPC_NRT_OBSERVATIONS_014_002
Data Owner	CMEMS

<i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	CMEMS
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	Public dataset
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4.
Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
This dataset can be used in all scenarios envisaged for Pilot 4. Usage will depend on users' choices of datasets.	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	NetCDF
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	
Standard	

<i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	CF1.0
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	Up to 500 Mbyte/day (satellites only focus in specific areas) only areas of interest should be selected
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised? If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	Data does not have any particular needs regarding permissions or anonymisation.
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	Data can be collected in real-time.

Global ocean L3 spectral parameters from nrt satellite measurements - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				
1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

B.2.19. Data Source #19 (DS_#19)

WPDA Portugal protected areas database - data source description:

Overview	
Data source title <i>Give the data source title</i>	Protected Area Profile for Portugal from the World Database of Protected Areas
Data source acronym <i>Give the dataset acronym if exists</i>	PT_WPDA
General description of dataset	Dataset includes a description of Portuguese protected areas (maritime and in-land).

<i>Give a short description of the dataset, e.g., purpose, type of data, etc.</i>	
Temporal and Spatial coverage <i>If the dataset contains temporal or spatial information provide which period or area it covers</i>	Spatial coverage: Portugal Temporal Coverage: N/A
Status / Maintenance <i>State if dataset is old or is updated/maintained regularly</i>	Dataset is a static database (not updated).

Provider	
Data provider <i>Give the name of the data provider (e.g., organisation, company, etc.)</i>	Protected Planet
Data provider URI	https://www.protectedplanet.net/country/PT
Data Owner <i>Provide the ownership of of the dataset along with any contact information</i>	Protected Planet
Data administrator <i>Provide this information only if different from above</i>	Protected Planet
Permission status <i>Is the dataset private, public, accessible under license or specific conditions?</i>	Public dataset
Partner	
Pilot case <i>Give the number of the pilot case or pilot cases this dataset relates or can be related to</i>	This dataset can be used in different test cases of Scenario 2 of Pilot 4, namely those considering the choice of locations for wave farms, considering environmental data.

Possible scenario coverage <i>Give examples about how this dataset is currently being used or will be used</i>	
This dataset can be used in different test cases of Scenario 2 of Pilot 4, namely those considering the choice of locations for wave farms, considering environmental data.	
Details	
Data format(s) <i>Give the data format(s) in which the dataset is available</i>	Kml, csv
Data language <i>Provide the language used for the data and metadata</i>	English
Assumptions <i>Are there any assumptions made with regard to the data?</i>	-
Standard <i>Provide any standards that have been used for producing the data</i>	-
Ontologies / Vocabularies used <i>Provide any ontologies or vocabularies used to describe the data</i>	
Data Size <i>Give the size of the dataset in MB. If the dataset increases regularly give information about this increase</i>	< 50 Mbytes
Accessibility, Permissions, Anonymisation <i>Include access control and permission details. Should the data be anonymised?</i>	Data does not have any particular needs regarding permissions or anonymisation.

<i>If so, which fields should be protected/anonymised?</i>	
Data collection frequency <i>State how often the data is collected</i>	Data was collected once. Does not require regular updates. Maybe one update an year is advisable, to be sure that protected areas description and locations are up to date.
Raw data sample	
Data schema and documentation	
<i>Main data fields:</i> TYPE; WDPA_ID; ORIG_NAME; IUCN_CAT; MARINE; REP_M_AREA; GIS_M_AREA; REP_AREA; NO_TAKE; NO_TK_AREA	

WPDA Portugal protected areas database - data source quality assessment:

		YES	NO	COMMENTS
VALIDITY – Data should clearly and adequately represent the intended result.				
1	Does the information collected measure what it is supposed to measure?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Do results collected fall within a plausible range?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is there reasonable assurance that the data collection methods being used do not produce systematically biased data (e.g. consistently over- or under-counting)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
RELIABILITY – Data should reflect stable and consistent data collection processes and analysis methods over time.				
1	When the same data collection method is used to measure/observe the same thing multiple times, is the same result produced each time? (E.g. A ruler used over and over always indicates the same length for an inch.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are data collection and analysis methods documented in writing and being used to ensure the same procedures are followed each time?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
TIMELINESS – Data should be available at a useful frequency, should be current, and should be timely enough to influence management decision-making.				
1	Are data available frequently enough to support the pilot's needs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Are the data reported the most current practically available?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are the data reported as soon as possible after collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
ACCURACY – Data have a sufficient level of detail, e.g. the margin of error is acceptable.				

1	Is the precision of data sufficient to support the pilot objectives?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Has the margin of error been reported along with the data? (Only applicable to results obtained through statistical samples.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Is the data collection method/tool being used to collect the data fine-tuned or exact enough to register the expected change? (E.g. A yardstick may not be a precise enough tool to measure a change of a few millimeters.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
INTEGRITY – Data collected should have safeguards to minimise the risk of transcription error or data manipulation.				
1	Are procedures or safeguards in place to minimise data transcription errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2	Is there independence in key data collection, management, and assessment procedures?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
3	Are mechanisms in place to prevent unauthorised changes to the data?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	